

Passion for Mission:

A Journal of Utilized Studies

VOL 3 (2026)
ISSN: 3027-9623

Passion for Mission:

A Journal of Utilized Faculty Researches

Volume 3 (2026)

ISSN: 3027-9623

Editorial Board

Melanie G. Sarmiento,, PhD
Editor-in-Chief

Rhodora M. Aquino, MA
Technical Staff

Gelyne P. Gallangi, BSOA
Clerical Staff

John Octavious S. Palina, PhD, DBA
Supervising Head
University President

Preface

The *Passion for Mission: Journal of Utilized Studies* highlights how research can make a real difference in people's lives. This journal presents studies conducted by faculty researchers of Saint Mary's University that have been applied to address community needs, improve programs and services, support policy development, and promote positive change.

The projects featured in this volume show that research is not only about generating knowledge but also about finding practical solutions to real-world challenges. Through collaboration with schools, local government units, communities, organizations, and other partners, these studies have been transformed into meaningful actions that benefit society.

The title "*Passion for Mission*" reflects our researchers' dedication to using their knowledge, skills, and expertise to serve others. Their work demonstrates the University's commitment to excellence, innovation, and social responsibility.

This journal is also a celebration of the strong partnerships among researchers, community members, government agencies, and other stakeholders who worked together to turn research findings into useful programs, projects, and initiatives.

We hope that the stories and experiences shared in this journal will inspire others to see the value of research as a tool for learning, service, and community development. May this collection encourage more researchers to continue creating knowledge that leads to meaningful and lasting impact.

Editor-in-Chief

Community Extension Projects.....	1
SALUN-aTEM: Sustainable Actions for Landfill Upgrading Nurturing a Transformative Eco-landfill Management.....	1
<i>Elsa L. Cajucom, David M. Gayadang, Michael S. Catacutan, Julieta A. Villanueva, and Shiela G. Gilo.....</i>	<i>1</i>
A Tapestry of Faith: The Stories of Our Lady of Victory Pilgrimage Site through a Coffee Table Book.....	10
<i>Mayvelyn S. Covita, John Michael C. Ibarra, and Mark Ian J. Soriano.....</i>	<i>10</i>
Project NURTURE: Navigating Unified Responsible Parenting Towards an Upgraded Resilient Education System.....	16
<i>Sherylou A. Benig, Marissa Lyn A. Labangcoc, Mary Rose C. Jontilano, and Geneveive R. Bendoy.....</i>	<i>16</i>
Digital Discipleship: Shaping Critical Minds and Joyful Gospel-Based Values in Youth (A School-Parish-Based Youth Encounter Project).....	20
<i>Henry F. Gamboa, Epifanio Delbert G. Galima III, Edjohn B. Antonino, Benito D. Buyacco, Jr., Bryan Benedict D. Olarte, and Victor M. Abijay.....</i>	<i>20</i>
LINK for LIFE Initiative: Fostering Care and Connection for Filipino Elderly through Health Awareness Drives and Wellness Promotion, Creating Informative Brochures for Community Impact.....	27
<i>Melchora M. Bautista, May Juliet S. Palina, and Brent Jericko P. Narciso.....</i>	<i>27</i>
Beyond the Classroom: Empowering Leaders through SDG-Focused Advocacy and Project Development for Real-World Impact (Seminar-Workshop with a.....	29
<i>Kenneth L. Maslang, Darwin Don M. Dacles, and Armand N. Camhol.....</i>	<i>29</i>
Speak Easy: A Public Speaking Anxiety Reduction Support Mechanism.....	36
<i>Lysel I. Haloc, Mr. Christian Jos M. Obaña, and Ma. Ines R. Minia.....</i>	<i>36</i>
Project 360 Branding FEAT: A Digital Marketing Feedback & Assessment Tool for Philippine Higher Education.....	42
<i>Monaloufel Rosario Jasmin, Rocel Audrey J. Batara, and Rheena Niña S. Salinas.....</i>	<i>42</i>
Project LINGKOD: Local Initiatives for Normative Governance and Kapwa-Driven Organizing for Development.....	46
<i>Christopher Allen S. Marquez, Domingo T. Guntalilib Jr., Luther F. Castillo, Elson Boie B. Tumaneng, and Ramel S. Salon.....</i>	<i>46</i>
Project CITRUS: Collaboratively Implemented Technology in Robotics Utilized for Satsuma Citrus Post-harvest.....	51
<i>Teofilo M. Sagabaen, Angelino A. Pimentel, & Gerene-Leigh C. Almazan.....</i>	<i>51</i>
Project EASTeR: Enhancing Accountability in Stewardship of Time, Talent, and Resources (Treasure).....	60
Jonathan P. Vergara, Loreta V. Garlitos, Romulo C. Felix, Roy B. Lumidao, and Frans T. Balinggan.....	60
Capacity Building for SDG Integration in Business: A Coffee Table Book Showcasing Localized Impact through Stories and Testimonials.....	63
<i>Harrison T. Villanueva, Sheryl A. Adducul-Baria, Dorilyn C. Tiongson, & Francis Leo Tugab.....</i>	<i>63</i>
Enhancing Local Capacity Through a Procedural Guide: A Community-Based Demonstration of Topical Herbal Ointment Formulation.....	70
<i>Cathelyn C. Mariano, Ma. Shiela M. Ramos, & Gabrielle Christoph Eraña.....</i>	<i>70</i>

Implementing ERP Systems to Improve Data-Driven Governance and Operational Efficiency in Barangays.....	76
<i>Adonis V. Garces, Milagros Constantino, & Reynaldo Valdez.....</i>	
Project BRIDGE (Building Resilient Initiatives for Development and Greener Environments): A University-Community Partnership for Strengthening Grassroots Climate Action.....	80
<i>Felipe V. Nantes, Jr., Haydee D. James, Alona C. Costales, & Elizabeth R. Lumidao.....</i>	
Kabataang Inhinyero Ng Lokal Na Ordinansa At Serbisyo: Harnessing Sk Legislative Competency To Ignite Youth Involvement In A First-Class Municipality (Project Kilos).....	83
<i>Erwin D. Naval, Ernest L. Esmeralda, Diwata Donato, Xaviery Brent Galima, & Carlo Noel Gines.....</i>	
Institutional Project Beneficiaries (IPB).....	87
Growing Together: An Upskilling Initiative for Child Development Workers.....	87
<i>Ma. Cristeta M. Aduca, Lilibeth V. Cajimat, & Caroline P. Navarrete.....</i>	
TALAS (Tulong at Alaga sa Lahat ng Estudyante): TeleSupport Program for Empowered Student Wellness.....	92
<i>Pearl Via S. Coballes, Kristine Ann L. Israel, Leslie Doris M. Divina, Joman J. Baliton, & Faridah Kristi C. Wetherick.....</i>	
Project GREEN MIND: Generating Responsible Environmental Education for Nurturing Minds In Nature and Development.....	102
<i>Samuel B. Damayon, Edwin Edilberto N. Mania, Nicole Anne P. Aquino, & Ruthie Maye R. Padilla.....</i>	
Implementing a Sustainable E-Waste Management Framework for an HEI to Foster a Circular Economy: Designing Informational Brochures.....	117
<i>Gertrude G. Danao, Mildios Meeds Ciriaco Blando, Irish E. Reginalde, Carina S. Mallillin, & Sheila Marie G. Gilo.....</i>	
Science-Math Educators' PRESENT (Promoting Resilience through diverse Experience, academic Support, Excogitation, exploring Notion, and providing educational Training).....	120
<i>Analyn A. Guevara, Lorna C. Aban, Domingo T. Guntalilib, Ronnie B. Bibas, & Florentino A. Aban Jr.....</i>	
Innovative Science Instruction: Creating Enrichment Modules to Elevate Junior High School Education and Advance Curriculum Development.....	126
<i>Agnes N. Madamba, Judy Ann F. Sunday, Zayda S. Asuncion, Jimmy E. Valdez, & Weyalein L. Balonquita.....</i>	
Project STEP: Shaping Tomorrow's Environment through Pathways for Wellness: A Seminar-Forum cum IEC Materials.....	128
<i>Mary Grace M. Bulatao, Jones K. Liwan, Jojie Mar M. Valdez, Michael A. Gabriel, Zayda S. Asuncion, Madonna Dionx C. Gonzales, & Joseph Bubod.....</i>	
PROJECT PEACE HUB: Promoting Empathy, Acceptance, and Civic Engagement By Harnessing Unity And Building Belongingness Among Marians.....	131
<i>Susan A. Galamay, Brian M. Baristo, & Benyamin Messakaraeng.....</i>	
Project ALLIES: Advancing Links for Learning, International Engagement, and Support.....	133
<i>Clara M. Gonzales, Martin Manuel, Gerome Bautista, Katelijne Demeyere, & Elly Verstraete.....</i>	

I-TUDU 2.0 Project ROOTS: Realigning Outcomes and Orientations in the Teaching System.....	141
<i>Vince Errol J. Lucas, Marites B. Querol, Federicia C. Calauagan, and Krizelle Nova A. Lazam.....</i>	
STEP UP WELLNESS: A Research-Based Brochure for Mental and Social Fitness Among HEI Dance Troupe Members.....	145
<i>Ronda L. Navalta, Niño N. Baldonado, Dalarry L. Duldulao, & Ronna Chiehann J. Vidal... 145</i>	
Re-appropriating and Recalibrating Learning Packet on Diversified Planning and Design Initiatives Towards an Enhanced Internship Program in a University.....	148
<i>Liberty A. Rosario, Candido Joseph T. Rosario Jr., and Rianna Joy L. Agrimor..... 148</i>	
PROJECT B2B: Building Sustainable Campuses From Bins To Behavior.....	153
<i>Regina D. Ramel, John Lindy R. Soriano, Jeanette R. Mania, and Jeniviv V. Pascual (COA). 153</i>	
Institutional Policy-Oriented Studies (IPOS).....	158
From Classroom to Career: Evaluating the Employability of SAB Graduates.....	159
<i>Regina D. Ramel..... 159</i>	
Curriculum Insights: Accountancy and Business Graduates' Perspectives on Skill Development and Program Effectiveness.....	160
<i>Regina D. Ramel..... 160</i>	
Information Technology (IT) Students' Perspective on Artificial Intelligence: A Boon or a Bane?.....	161
<i>Gertrude G. Danao..... 161</i>	
Gender Responsiveness Of The Community Development Center Of A Private Catholic Educational Institution In The Philippines.....	162
<i>Christopher Allen S. Marquez, Elvira G. Tongson, and Marnuela Q. Dela Cruz.....162</i>	
Mind the Waste: Assessing Awareness and Attitudes Towards Solid Waste Management Among University Students.....	163
<i>Shenna Mae B. Decoro & Elsa L. Cajucom.....163</i>	
Development of Environment and Christian Values-Oriented Chemistry Modules (ECCM) for Junior High School Special Science Program Learners.....	165
<i>Elsa L. Cajucom..... 165</i>	
Safeguarding Campus Water: A Preliminary Assessment of Microplastics and Microbial Pollution in SMU Groundwater System.....	166
<i>Elsa L. Cajucom, Michael S. Catacutan, Regidor L. Almendral, Vincent Carlo C. Boniol, David M. Gayadang, Arcelle Mae Pablo, Hannah Mae Q. Lim, Leana B. Alap, Aila Laurice C. Panganiban, Gregg Austine M. Balanag, and Lady Fatima C. Reganit..... 166</i>	
From Insights to Action: Policy Recommendations Based on Learner Satisfaction and Net Promoter Score Analysis.....	168
<i>Harrison T. Villanueva & Pearl Via S. Coballes..... 168</i>	
Pre-Feasibility Study Of Offering News Programs At Saint Mary's University Based On Student Preferences.....	169
<i>Clara M. Gonzales, Madonna A. Blando, Mark Noren U. de Vera, Monaloufel Rosario F. Jasmin, Rocel Audrey J. Batara, Martin Gabriel T. Manuel, & Nicole Anne P. Aquino..... 169</i>	
Exploring the Career Wellness of Marian Students through the Career Wellness and Inventory Test (CaWIT).....	171
<i>Richelle D. Francisco, Edwin Edilberto N. Mania, Meca Jade M. Corpuz, Leslie Doris M.</i>	

Divina, May Juliet S. Palina, Jennifer Ann M. Torres, Florizza Lorraine B. Galamay, Marc Gail M. Cornejo, Deophile Jeffnorson A. Magday, Berlyn B. Pihulon, & Bryant M. Soliven...
171

Understanding Student Attrition at SMU: A Three-Year Review of Trends and Reasons..... 172

Richelle D. Francisco, Edwin Edilberto N. Mania, Meca Jade M. Corpuz, Leslie Doris M. Divina, May Juliet S. Palina, Jennifer Ann M. Torres, Florizza Lorraine B. Galamay, Marc Gail M. Cornejo, Deophile Jeffnorson A. Magday, Berlyn B. Pihulon, & Bryant M. Soliven...
172

Assessing and Refining the Policy on Responsible AI Use in Research, Instruction, and Extension: A Collaborative Approach..... 173

Melanie G. Gurat, Ivonny Lorvin M. Adducul, John Octavious S. Palina, John G. Tayaban, Ma. Nympha B. Joaquin, & Crist John M. Pastor..... 173

Community Extension Projects

CEP-01

SALUN-aTEM: Sustainable Actions for Landfill Upgrading Nurturing a Transformative Eco-landfill Management

Elsa L. Cajucom, David M. Gayadang, Michael S. Catacutan, Julieta A. Villanueva, and Shiela G. Gilo

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A sanitary landfill must be properly designed and managed to minimize environmental risks and protect surrounding ecosystems. Mismanagement can result in soil contamination, disrupted nutrient cycling, and long-term ecological degradation. This study assessed the physicochemical properties of soils from four landfill cells at the Bayombong Sanitary Landfill in Purok 7, Barangays Magsaysay and Busilac, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, to support the development of a localized soil remediation and management plan. Soil samples were analyzed for pH, nitrogen, phosphorus, and heavy metal concentrations. Results showed slightly acidic soil conditions (pH 5.2 to 6.0), which may reduce nutrient availability and limit microbial activity. Nitrogen levels varied across cells, with Cell 1, which has been closed the longest, exhibiting the highest concentration (106.65 kilograms per hectare), likely due to vegetation growth and organic matter accumulation over time. Phosphorus values fluctuated, with Cell 3 falling below optimal fertility ranges. Heavy metals, including cadmium (11.26 to 15.66 micrograms per kilogram) and lead (0.42 to 0.99 milligrams per kilogram), remained below EPA hazardous thresholds, indicating limited industrial or toxic inputs. The clay loam soil structure of the landfill area likely contributed to the immobilization of heavy metals, reducing potential ecological and human health risks. The study concludes that although heavy metal contamination is minimal, nutrient imbalance and soil acidity require intervention. Recommended management strategies include compost-based soil enrichment, pH correction using agricultural lime, and ecological rehabilitation through native and nitrogen-fixing plant species. Regular soil monitoring and community awareness programs are also advised to support sustainable landfill operations in accordance with national environmental standards.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

I. Dissemination of Findings

The Training on Research Methodologies for Policy Making, Management Case, and Innovation Research was successfully conducted on October 2–3, 2025, through the initiative of the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) Region II, in collaboration with the Cagayan Valley Health Research and Development Consortium (CVHRDC) and the Medical Colleges of Northern Philippines (MCNP). The activity aimed to strengthen participants' capacity to apply research methodologies in health policy development, case management, and innovation research.

The program formally commenced at 8:00 AM following the registration of participants. The opening ceremony featured the Prayer, National Anthem, DOST Hymn, and MCNP Hymn, setting a professional and solemn tone for the activity. The Acknowledgment of Participants was led by the moderator, followed by Welcome Remarks and inspirational messages from Mr. Christian R. Guzman, President of MCNP; Dr. Virginia G. Bilgera, Regional Director of DOST Region II and Chairperson of CVHRDC; and Dr. Julius T. Capili,

Executive Director of CVHRDC. The speakers emphasized the crucial role of research in strengthening health systems, improving case management practices, and guiding evidence-based policy making.

During the group discussion sessions, Mr. David M. Gayadang shared the team's findings on landfill management, highlighting how evidence-based data can inform policy decisions, environmental management strategies, and sustainable innovations. His participation underscored the practical application of the research methodologies discussed during the training, particularly in addressing real-world environmental and public health concerns, which were later applied in crafting the research team's Sustainable Remediation Plan.

II. Crafting of Sustainable Remediation Plan (SRP)

Building on the knowledge and methodological insights gained from the Training on Research Methodologies for Policy Making, Management Case, and Innovation Research, the research team subsequently undertook the crafting of the Sustainable Remediation Plan (SRP). The training strengthened the team's capacity to translate research evidence into policy-relevant, implementation-ready outputs to support local government decision-making.

Dr. Cajucom facilitated the development of the SRP through a series of structured group discussions. These sessions enabled the team to critically analyze landfill research findings, identify priority environmental and public health concerns, and formulate sustainable remediation strategies grounded in established Philippine waste management laws and policies. The plan was anchored on key national frameworks, including Republic Act No. 9003 (Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000), Republic Act No. 8749 (Philippine Clean Air Act), and Republic Act No. 9275 (Philippine Clean Water Act), ensuring regulatory compliance and alignment with national environmental standards.

Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA) was also integrated as a core analytical basis of the SRP, allowing the team to systematically evaluate potential environmental and human health risks associated with landfill operations. The application of ERA supported evidence-based prioritization of remediation measures and informed the selection of appropriate, sustainable interventions suited to local conditions.

Through this collaborative, evidence-driven process, the Sustainable Remediation Plan was positioned as a practical, science-based tool to guide local government units (LGUs) in strengthening landfill management practices, informing strategic planning, and enhancing environmental protection and public health safeguards.

III. Content Validation of the SRP

The Sustainable Remediation Plan (SRP) developed by the research team underwent a rigorous content validation process to ensure its scientific soundness, technical accuracy, regulatory alignment, and practical applicability. The validation was conducted by a panel of experts with extensive professional experience in engineering, environmental management, and safety and pollution control, thereby providing a multidisciplinary assessment of the plan.

One of the content validators is a registered Chemical Engineer and licensed Chemical Technician currently working at the Department of Science and Technology – Philippine Textile Research Institute (DOST-PTRI). The expert evaluated the technical components

of the SRP, particularly the chemical processes, waste characterization, and proposed remediation strategies, ensuring that these were grounded in established engineering principles and aligned with national environmental standards.

Another validator is the Dean of the College of Forestry and Environmental Management from a state university. This expert assessed the ecological and environmental management aspects of the plan, including sustainability considerations, ecosystem protection, and the integration of Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA). The evaluation emphasized the plan's alignment with environmental management frameworks and its relevance to long-term ecological sustainability.

The third content validator is a Safety and Pollution Officer from a university, who reviewed the SRP regarding occupational safety, environmental compliance, and pollution control measures. This assessment ensured that the proposed remediation strategies complied with safety protocols, regulatory requirements, and best practices for environmental risk mitigation.

Overall, the content validation process affirmed the relevance, clarity, and feasibility of the Sustainable Remediation Plan. The validators' comments and recommendations were carefully considered and incorporated to enhance the plan's quality further, strengthening its potential as a science-based, policy-relevant tool for local government units and other stakeholders involved in landfill management and environmental remediation.

IV. Presentation of the SRP to MENRO Officials

Opening and Welcome Remarks

The activity commenced with a welcome message from the MENRO representative, Ms. Gilo, who highlighted the importance of using research-based evidence to strengthen local environmental management initiatives.

Introduction of the Research Team and Objectives of the Presentation

The research team, led by Dr. Elsa Cajucom, presented the purpose of the engagement. The presentation aimed to disseminate the results of the environmental risk assessment and to assist the MENRO Office in understanding the potential effects of landfill leachate and heavy metals on surrounding land and groundwater systems.

Presentation of Research Findings

Mr. Gayadang discussed the study's background, methodology, key findings, conclusions, and recommendations. Emphasis was placed on the assessed vulnerability of the land to leachate contamination, the identified heavy metals as potential risks, and the varying levels of environmental risk in areas adjacent to the landfill site, using the HEI-MLGU assessment framework. Maps, tables, and assessment indicators were utilized to present and support the findings effectively.

Discussion and Clarifications

MENRO personnel, through Mr. Pastores, raised questions and provided insights regarding:

- The implications of the findings on local environmental management
- Possible sources of contamination
- The applicability of the results to existing waste management and monitoring programs

The research team addressed these queries and clarified technical aspects of the assessment.

Recommendations and Policy Implications

Dr. Elsa Cajucom outlined the study's intent. She presented key recommendations, which included enhancing soil monitoring near the landfill site, improving leachate management and control mechanisms, and adopting the results as baseline information for future environmental planning and decision-making. Additional recommendations involved conducting a separate study on the possible contamination and safety of fruits harvested in nearby areas and strengthening overall solid waste management practices.

Acknowledgment and Closing Remarks

The MENRO Office, through Mrs. Juan, acknowledged the research team's contribution and expressed appreciation for the collaboration between the HEI and the LGU. The meeting concluded with MENRO's commitment to consider the study findings in future environmental planning and monitoring efforts. The office also expressed openness to LGU assistance for certain study-related expenditures, including laboratory testing fees, subject to existing policies. She further added that increasing awareness of potential environmental and public health risks associated with landfill operations and identifying possible areas for policy action, monitoring, and further study are important.

Documentation of Utilization

1. Dissemination (Sharing) of Findings to the Government Agency Towards Policy Brief Making

2. Request Letters for Content Validation of the Sustainable Remediation Plan

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

January 23, 2026

Engr. Aika Fritz Y. Bejosano, RChT
Project Technical Assistant
DOST-PTRI
South Compound, Bicutan, Taguig City

Dear Engr. Bejosano:

A Blessed day!

We are respectfully requesting your expertise to serve as a validator for the *Sustainable Remediation Plan for the Bayombong Sanitary Landfill*. Your extensive experience and recognized competence in the fields of environmental management, waste management, and sustainable remediation make your insights highly valuable to this undertaking.

The purpose of this expert validation is to assess the plan in terms of its technical soundness, environmental sustainability, regulatory compliance, feasibility of implementation, and overall effectiveness in mitigating environmental and public health risks associated with sanitary landfill operations. Your evaluation and recommendations will play a crucial role in strengthening the quality, credibility, and applicability of the proposed remediation strategies.

Should you agree, we will provide you with the full copy of the Sustainable Remediation Plan, along with an expert validation instrument to guide your review. All feedback will be treated with utmost confidentiality and used solely for academic, research, and policy-improvement purposes.

We sincerely hope for your favorable consideration of this request. Thank you for your time, support, and commitment to advancing sustainable environmental practices.

Should you need further information or clarification, please feel free to contact us this email, ecajucum@smu.edu.ph and mobile number 0977 803 3684.

Respectfully yours,
 Dr. Elsa Cajucum
Project Lead
 David M. Gayadang
Member
 Julieta C. Villanueva
Member
 Shiela Marie G. Gilo
Member

Noted by:
 Dr. Melagie G. Gurat
University Research Director

*Inspired by Mission,
Driven by Excellence*

UB115, First Floor, Constant Jurgens Building
SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street
Bayombong, 1905 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
www.smu.edu.ph | 1098181810 (0977) 803-3684
079332-3108 | (+63)934-288-7289

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

January 23, 2026

Dr. Wilfredo A. Dumale Jr.
University President
Nueva Vizcaya State University

Attn: Dr. Jayson Q. Caranza
Dean, College of Forestry, Environment and Natural Resources Management
Nueva Vizcaya State University
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

Dear President Dumale:

A Blessed day!

We are respectfully requesting your approval to allow Dr. Caranza to serve as a validator for the *Sustainable Remediation Plan for the Bayombong Sanitary Landfill*. Dr. Caranza's extensive experience and recognized competence in the fields of environmental management, waste management, and sustainable remediation make his insights highly valuable to this undertaking.

The purpose of this expert validation is to assess the plan in terms of its technical soundness, environmental sustainability, regulatory compliance, feasibility of implementation, and overall effectiveness in mitigating environmental and public health risks associated with sanitary landfill operations. Your evaluation and recommendations will play a crucial role in strengthening the quality, credibility, and applicability of the proposed remediation strategies.

Should you agree, we will provide Dr. Caranza with the full copy of the Sustainable Remediation Plan, along with an expert validation instrument to guide him in the review. All feedback will be treated with utmost confidentiality and used solely for academic, research, and policy-improvement purposes.

We sincerely hope for your favorable consideration of this request. Thank you for your time, support, and commitment to advancing sustainable environmental practices.

Should you need further information or clarification, please feel free to contact us to this email, ecajucum@smu.edu.ph and mobile number 0977 803 3684.

Respectfully yours,
 Dr. Elsa Cajucum
Project Lead
 David M. Gayadang
Member
 Julieta C. Villanueva
Member
 Shiela Marie G. Gilo
Member

Noted by:
 Dr. Melagie G. Gurat
University Research Director

*Inspired by Mission,
Driven by Excellence*

UB115, First Floor, Constant Jurgens Building
SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street
Bayombong, 1905 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
www.smu.edu.ph | 1098181810 (0977) 803-3684
079332-3108 | (+63)934-288-7289

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

January 23, 2026

Engr. Aika Fritz Y. Bejosano, RChT
Project Technical Assistant
DOST-PTRI
South Compound, Bicutan, Taguig City

Dear Engr. Bejosano:

A Blessed day!

We are respectfully requesting your expertise to serve as a validator for the *Sustainable Remediation Plan for the Bayombong Sanitary Landfill*. Your extensive experience and recognized competence in the fields of environmental management, waste management, and sustainable remediation make your insights highly valuable to this undertaking.

The purpose of this expert validation is to assess the plan in terms of its technical soundness, environmental sustainability, regulatory compliance, feasibility of implementation, and overall effectiveness in mitigating environmental and public health risks associated with sanitary landfill operations. Your evaluation and recommendations will play a crucial role in strengthening the quality, credibility, and applicability of the proposed remediation strategies.

Should you agree, we will provide you with the full copy of the Sustainable Remediation Plan, along with an expert validation instrument to guide your review. All feedback will be treated with utmost confidentiality and used solely for academic, research, and policy-improvement purposes.

We sincerely hope for your favorable consideration of this request. Thank you for your time, support, and commitment to advancing sustainable environmental practices.

Should you need further information or clarification, please feel free to contact us this email, ecajucum@smu.edu.ph and mobile number 0977 803 3684.

Respectfully yours,
 Dr. Elsa Cajucum
Project Lead
 David M. Gayadang
Member
 Julieta C. Villanueva
Member
 Shiela Marie G. Gilo
Member

Noted by:
 Dr. Melagie G. Gurat
University Research Director

*Inspired by Mission,
Driven by Excellence*

UB115, First Floor, Constant Jurgens Building
SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street
Bayombong, 1905 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
www.smu.edu.ph | 1098181810 (0977) 803-3684
079332-3108 | (+63)934-288-7289

24 January 2026

DR. ELSA L. CAJUCOM
Project Lead
Saint Mary's University
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

Dear Dr. Cajucom:

This refers to your letter requesting my assistance in assessing the technical and environmental aspects of the project titled **Sustainable Remediation Plan for the Bayombong Sanitary Landfill**. I deeply appreciate the opportunity to contribute my expertise to your study.

In reference to this, I am willing to provide an independent review of the project. To proceed with the assessment, I kindly request for a copy of the Sustainable Remediation Plan, along with the validation instrument that will guide the review process. These documents will allow me to conduct an objective and informed evaluation that is aligned to the objectives of the study.

I also request for the expected timeline of the review and any confidentiality requirements that may apply. Once these details are clarified, I will be able to confirm my availability and deliverables accordingly.

Thank you for considering me for this role. I look forward to a productive collaboration with your Team.

Respectfully,
 AIKA FRITZ Y. BEJOSANO
Registered Chemical Engineer

3. Presentation and Meeting with MENRO Officers

4. Sharing of Findings and Utilization Report through the SMU Website

Feedback from Clients

1. From Experts Validator

E. OVERALL ASSESSMENT

Indicator	4	3	2	1
Overall quality of the Sustainable Remediation Plan.	/			
Likelihood of adoption by LGU/DENR.	/			

Comments and Recommendations: ^{REQ}
 TO INCLUDE WHEN IS THE TIME TO APPLY AGRICULTURAL FERTILIZER & HOW LONG WILL IT TAKE TO PULL UP ADJUST THE SOIL PH. MONITORING ALSO IS HIGHLY RECOMMENDED. T.Y.

Name of Evaluator:	MARCEN T. VILVANUEVA
Highest Educational Attainment:	MAST
Institutional Affiliation:	SMU
Position:	JPGD HEAD
Signature:	<i>[Signature]</i>
Date:	01-30-2026

*Inspired by Mission,
Driven by Excellence*

Second Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Building
 SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, District IV
 Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
 www.smu.edu.ph / ddacles@smu.edu.ph
 (078) 392-8150

E. OVERALL ASSESSMENT

Indicator	4	3	2	1
Overall quality of the Sustainable Remediation Plan.	✓			
Likelihood of adoption by LGU/DENR.	✓			

Comments and Recommendations:
 Add quantitative targets; identify specific bamboo species and spacing; include simple cost range per major activity;
 Add contingency actions for extreme rainfall and prolonged drought scenarios (climate change impacts)

Name of Evaluator:	JAYSON Q. CARANZA
Highest Educational Attainment:	Post Doc.
Institutional Affiliation:	Nueva Vizcaya State University
Position:	Dean, College of Forestry, Environment and Resources Management
Signature:	
Date:	February 04, 2026

Second Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Building
 SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, District IV
 Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
 www.smu.edu.ph / ddacles@smu.edu.ph
 (078) 392-8150

*Inspired by Mission,
Driven by Excellence*

E. OVERALL ASSESSMENT

Indicator	4	3	2	1
Overall quality of the Sustainable Remediation Plan.	✓			
Likelihood of adoption by LGU/DENR.		✓		

Comments and Recommendations:
 The Plan is elegantly simple and sustainable. However, challenges lie on the enforcement of the Plan and the continuity of LGU support.

Name of Evaluator:	Aika Fritz Y. Bejosano
Highest Educational Attainment:	College Graduate - BS Chemical Engineering
Institutional Affiliation:	DOST - Philippine Textile Research Institute
Position:	Project Technical Assistant
Signature:	
Date:	27 January 2026

Second Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Building
 SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, District IV
 Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
 www.smu.edu.ph / ddacles@smu.edu.ph
 (078) 392-8150

*Inspired by Mission,
Driven by Excellence*

<p>Evidence-based research took center stage as Saint Mary's University (SMU) formally presented its research-driven remediation plan for the Bayombong Sanitary Landfill to the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) on January 28, 2026. The initiative highlighted how scientific data can directly inform local environmental governance, strengthen waste management practices, and safeguard public health.</p> <p>The study confirmed that current landfill management systems are generally functioning well, with cadmium and lead levels remaining below hazardous thresholds. However, the research also identified areas needing improvement, including slightly acidic soil conditions and uneven nutrient distribution in surrounding areas. These findings became the foundation of Project Salun-aTEM (Sustainable Actions for Landfill Upgrading Nurturing a Transformative Eco-landfill Management), a remediation framework that promotes targeted soil pH correction, nutrient enhancement, and phytoremediation using resilient species such as bamboo to support long-term soil health and ecological stability.</p> <p>The presentation was attended by key MENRO officials, including Mrs. Marilyn A. Juan, MGADH-MENRO, and Engr. Gilbert S. Pastores, Engineering Assistant. The SMU research team was led by Dr. Elsa L. Cajucom, Director of the Center for Natural Sciences, with research members Mr. David M. Gayadang, Mrs. Juliet A. Villanueva, Mr. Michael S. Catacutan, Ms. Vivienne Junelle R. ALmendra, and with MENRO collaborator Mrs. Shiela Marie G. Gilo.</p> <p>During the session, the research team outlined the objectives of the activity, which included informing local environmental authorities of land and groundwater vulnerability to leachate and heavy metal contamination, supporting evidence-based decision-making, identifying high-risk areas requiring intervention, and strengthening collaboration between higher education institutions (HEIs) and local government units (LGUs). The study also aims to contribute baseline data for long-term environmental monitoring and promote sustainable waste management practices.</p> <p>Mr. Gayadang presented the study's background, methodology, key findings, and recommendations, utilizing maps, tables, and assessment indicators based on the HEI-MLGU environmental risk assessment framework. Discussions that followed focused on the implications of the findings for existing waste management programs, possible sources of contamination, and how the results could be integrated into MENRO's monitoring and policy initiatives.</p> <p>Dr. Cajucom emphasized the policy relevance of the research, recommending enhanced soil and leachate monitoring, improved control mechanisms, and the adoption of the findings as baseline information for future planning. She also proposed further studies on the safety of fruits grown near the landfill and the continued strengthening of solid waste management practices.</p> <p>In her closing remarks, Mrs. Juan acknowledged the value of the collaboration and expressed MENRO's commitment to considering the</p>	<p>Grade School Junior High School and Science High School Senior High School Undergraduate Programs Graduate Programs College of LAW Scholarships</p>
--	---

2. From MENRO

The study concluded with MENRO's commitment to consider the findings in future environmental planning and monitoring efforts. The office also expressed openness to LGU assistance for certain study-related expenditures, including laboratory testing fees, subject to existing policies. Mrs. Juan further added that increasing awareness of potential environmental and public health risks associated with landfill operations and identifying possible areas for policy action, monitoring, and further study are important.

CEP-02**A Tapestry of Faith: The Stories of Our Lady of Victory Pilgrimage Site through a Coffee Table Book**

Mayvelyn S. Covita, John Michael C. Ibarra, and Mark Ian J. Soriano

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Developing a community's local tourism has always been regarded as a sustainable tool for equitable sharing of benefits among stakeholders, as well as for the appreciation visitors gain from participating in a destination's local tourism efforts. Local tourism assets may take many forms, from natural features to organized events held at designated community sites. This qualitative study described the Mangkelleb Hill of Villaverde, Nueva Vizcaya, as a pilgrimage site since the start of its initial development up to its current state, the challenges the management encountered in developing it as a known pilgrimage site in the province, and eventually yielded a recommended plan of action for the realization of the project's further development. Responses from key stakeholders, including interviews and focus group discussions with community members in the area where the site is located, were solicited to address the set objectives. The study was conducted in the first semester of the academic year 2024-2025, and it likewise endeavored to unfold the key elements that contribute and may further continue to support a desired level or extent of partnership among key stakeholders to achieve set goals in relation to a community project anchored on religious and tourism purposes and activities.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Photos were captured during the Holy Week, particularly on Good Friday of 2024 (March 29) and 2025 (April 18). On these particular dates, random conversations with individuals who joined as spectators and organizers of the re-enactment of the Passion of the Christ were held, noting relevant information essential to the crafting and layout of the coffee table book. Additional insights were also noted from church volunteers and from the Parish Priest at that time, Fr. Crispin A. Costales. Afterward, the researchers collaboratively designed the coffee table book, entering the captured images and notes. Enhancements were later integrated through suggestions, culminating in its final version. Copies of the final output were then given and received by the current Our Lady

of Fatima Parish Priest, Fr. Evedi B. Awidan, and by Villaverde Mayor Hon. Atty. Ronelie U. Valtoribio, through her Executive Assistant, Mrs. Rubyrose U. Barrientos, on November 13, 2025. The soft copy of the coffee table book was also sent via email later that day. The above photo is with Executive Assistant to the Villaverde Mayor, Mrs. Rubyrose U. Barrientos, and the right photo is with Our Lady of Fatima Parish Priest Fr. Evedi B. Awidan.

Documentation of Utilization

HTM Faculty Researchers Share Coffee Table Book with Villaverde Stakeholders

On November 13, 2025, our HTM Faculty Researchers had the honor of sharing a labor of love—a beautiful Coffee Table Book celebrating Mangkelleb Hill, a cherished pilgrimage site in Villaverde. Fr. Evedi B. Awidan received this meaningful gift for Our Lady of Fatima Parish and for Mrs. Rubyrose U. Barrientos, on behalf of Mayor Atty Ronelie U. Valtoribio and the community.

Guided by the vision of Dr. Mayvelyn S. Covita, alongside collaborators Mr. John Michael C. Ibarra, Mr. Mark Ian J. Soriano, and Rev. Fr. Crispin A. Costales, this project grew from heartfelt research called “Faithful Stewardship: A Community-Centric Pilgrimage Site Revitalization.” Their dedication shines through this book, created to honor and uplift one of Villaverde’s most treasured landmarks, inspiring pride, preserving history, and encouraging sustainable tourism that supports the community.

A Tapestry of Faith: The Stories of Our Lady of Victory Pilgrimage Site beautifully captures the spirit, history, and devotion woven into this sacred place. Through stunning images and touching stories of the pilgrims, it invites everyone to connect with the power of faith, the strength of community, and the timeless journey of hope and renewal. This project advances Sustainable Development Goal 11 by promoting sustainable cities and communities through the preservation of cultural heritage and inclusive local tourism. It also supports Goal 15 by encouraging the protection and restoration of terrestrial ecosystems through community stewardship of this important natural and spiritual site.

More than just a book, this is a celebration of faith, a call to stewardship, and a testament to what can be achieved when passion, research, and community unite to protect and cherish our shared heritage.

Write-up by: Dr. Mayvelyn S. Covita & Mr. John Michael C. Ibarra

Photos by: Mr. John Michael C. Ibarra

GDrive Folder Link for Document and Photos:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/11OZ7dqVFTQX_ymkP9DbstWF0finmGqrP?usp=sharing

Soft copy of the Coffee Table Book also sent through email.

The Coffee Table Book

GROTTO MAIN ENTRANCE

From the road going up to the grotto may take around 15 minutes of regular walking with more or less a climb of 200 steps.

It has become a focal point for the annual dramatization of the Via Crucis or Stations of the Cross, reflecting the deep-rooted religious traditions of the community. Parishioners described the place like a church.

OUR JOURNEY

Reenactment of the Passion of Christ at Mangkelleb Hill held in 2010

Snapshots of the annual conduct of the "Stations of the Cross" in the early 2010. The re-enactment was held on the foot of the hill, with permission from the land owners. For three years now, the re-enactment goes up to the hill's summit, starting from the Our Lady of Fatima Parish.

ALTAR AND REST AREA
Mangkelleb Hill in Villaverde, Nueva Vizcaya

IN 2025, MANGKELLEB GROTTO STANDS AS A MOUNTAIN OF HOPE AND A TESTAMENT TO THE DEVOTION TO THE BLESSED MOTHER, ENCOURAGING VISITORS TO CONNECT WITH THE COMMUNITY'S RELIGIOUS HISTORY WHILE JOURNEYING WITH CHRIST TOWARD CALVARY.

DRAMATIZATION OF THE PASSION OF CHRIST

The crucifixion of Jesus.

Angel of the Lord telling the disciples that Jesus has risen.

A community-driven cast of the Passion of Christ at Mangkelleb Hill.

THE CAST

At the heart of Villaverde, Mangkelleb Hill rises as more than just a peak—it is a place where earth meets the heavens. Locals and pilgrims alike ascend its path not only to marvel at the sweeping views of Nueva Vizcaya's valleys, but also to find quiet moments of prayer before the Our Lady of Victory Grotto. Here, the wind seems to carry whispers of faith, the sky opens wide in blessing, and every step upward feels like a journey both inward and divine. As the sun dips behind the hills, casting a golden glow over the valley, Mangkelleb Hill stands as a gentle reminder: victories are not always loud or grand—sometimes, they are found in the stillness of the soul.

Feedback from Clients

Both beneficiaries, as represented by the Executive Assistant of the Municipal Mayor, Mrs. Rubyrose U. Barrientos, and the Our Lady of Fatima Parish Priest, Fr. Evedi B.

Awidan, expressed their gratitude for the Researchers' engagement in a research project that had benefitted their town, Villaverde.

The article has been uploaded to the Saint Mary's University website with the full story and link below. The same was posted on the University's Facebook account on November 27, 2025, with photos as shown above.

See full story: <https://smu.edu.ph/htm-faculty-unveil-a-tapestry-of-.../>

Further, the Local Government Unit of Villaverde, particularly the Sangguniang Bayan, acknowledges the research team's efforts in this research undertaking and extends its full appreciation for the coffee table book provided. The acknowledgment and appreciation are reflected in Sangguniang Bayan Resolution No. 193, Series 2025, as shown in the images below, and were received by the researchers on December 12, 2025.

Republic of the Philippines
Province of Nueva Vizcaya
MUNICIPALITY OF VILLAVERDE
OFFICE OF THE SANGGUNIANG BAYAN
Page 2
18 Resolution No. 193, Series of 2025
ATTY. KRUEL J.D. DACUMOS, J.D.
Vice Mayor/Presiding Officer
HON. ANASTACIO T. MARIÑAS, JR.
Municipal Councilor
HON. CHRISTINE A. PERALTA
Municipal Councilor
HON. JOSE P. YAGUINAY
Municipal Councilor
HON. JOSE M. BASMIN
Municipal Councilor
HON. JONATHAN S. QUIRIONES
Municipal Councilor
HON. DAWN RANEE V. ALGERA, R.S.W.
Municipal Councilor
HON. REYNALDO A. VALDEZ
Municipal Councilor
HON. JERRY V. JOSE
Municipal Councilor
HON. JOHN M. DACUMOS
LIMA President
HON. KRISTINE P. MARIÑAS
SKMP President
HON. JAYSON F. PANAL
TSMR
MR. FERDINAND B. NOTO
Secretary to the Sanggunian
DRY SEAL

WHEREAS, the said coffee table book serves not only as a research output but also as a valuable archival document that enriches the LGU's inventory and documentation of local tourism destinations, pilgrimage sites, and heritage resources, which is essential to the municipality's long-term cultural preservation, tourism planning, and policy formulation;
WHEREAS, the Municipality of Villaverde recognizes the importance of strengthening research partnerships with academic institutions, as these collaborations contribute to evidence-based local governance, community empowerment, and sustainable tourism development;
WHEREAS, the turnover of this coffee table book greatly supports the LGU's continuous efforts to curate, preserve, and promote its historical and tourism assets, ensuring that materials such as these become accessible references for future generations, local historians, researchers, and visitors;
WHEREAS, the Sangguniang Bayan of Villaverde deems it fitting and proper to formally honor and commend Saint Mary's University and the above-mentioned researchers for their dedication to the documentation and preservation of one of Villaverde's iconic cultural and spiritual landmarks;
NOW THEREFORE, on a session assembled upon motion of Hon. Dawn Rane V. Algera duly seconded by all the Sangguniang Bayan Members present, BE IT RESOLVED, as it is hereby RESOLVED, that the Sangguniang Bayan of Villaverde, Nueva Vizcaya expresses its profound gratitude and appreciation to Saint Mary's University - School of Accountancy and Business, Department of Hospitality and Tourism Management, and to Dr. Mayvelyn S. Covita, Mr. John Michael C. Ibarra, Mr. Mark Ian J. Soriano, and Rev. Fr. Crispin A. Costales for the production and turnover of the coffee table book "Faithful Stewardship: A Community-Centric Pilgrimage Site Revitalization."

Republic of the Philippines
Province of Nueva Vizcaya
MUNICIPALITY OF VILLAVERDE
OFFICE OF THE SANGGUNIANG BAYAN
Page 2
18 Resolution No. 193, Series of 2025
ATTY. KRUEL J.D. DACUMOS, J.D.
Vice Mayor/Presiding Officer
HON. ANASTACIO T. MARIÑAS, JR.
Municipal Councilor
HON. CHRISTINE A. PERALTA
Municipal Councilor
HON. JOSE P. YAGUINAY
Municipal Councilor
HON. JOSE M. BASMIN
Municipal Councilor
HON. JONATHAN S. QUIRIONES
Municipal Councilor
HON. DAWN RANEE V. ALGERA, R.S.W.
Municipal Councilor
HON. REYNALDO A. VALDEZ
Municipal Councilor
HON. JERRY V. JOSE
Municipal Councilor
HON. JOHN M. DACUMOS
LIMA President
HON. KRISTINE P. MARIÑAS
SKMP President
HON. JAYSON F. PANAL
TSMR
MR. FERDINAND B. NOTO
Secretary to the Sanggunian
DRY SEAL

CARRIED.
I HEREBY CERTIFY to the correctness of the foregoing resolution.
HON. ANASTACIO T. MARIÑAS, JR.
Municipal Councilor/Temporary Presiding Officer
ATTESTED BY:
FERDINAND B. NOTO
Secretary to the Sanggunian

Republic of the Philippines
Province of Nueva Vizcaya
MUNICIPALITY OF VILLAVERDE
OFFICE OF THE SANGGUNIANG BAYAN
Page 2
18 Resolution No. 193, Series of 2025
ATTY. KRUEL J.D. DACUMOS, J.D.
Vice Mayor/Presiding Officer
HON. ANASTACIO T. MARIÑAS, JR.
Municipal Councilor
HON. CHRISTINE A. PERALTA
Municipal Councilor
HON. JOSE P. YAGUINAY
Municipal Councilor
HON. JOSE M. BASMIN
Municipal Councilor
HON. JONATHAN S. QUIRIONES
Municipal Councilor
HON. DAWN RANEE V. ALGERA, R.S.W.
Municipal Councilor
HON. REYNALDO A. VALDEZ
Municipal Councilor
HON. JERRY V. JOSE
Municipal Councilor
HON. JOHN M. DACUMOS
LIMA President
HON. KRISTINE P. MARIÑAS
SKMP President
HON. JAYSON F. PANAL
TSMR
MR. FERDINAND B. NOTO
Secretary to the Sanggunian
DRY SEAL

EXCERPTS FROM THE MINUTES OF THE 17th REGULAR SESSION OF THE 12th SANGGUNIANG, HEADED BY HON. ANASTACIO T. MARIÑAS, JR., MUNICIPAL COUNCILOR/TEMPORARY PRESIDING OFFICER, HELD AT SANGGUNIANG BAYAN SESSION HALL, VILLAVERDE, NUEVA VIZCAYA ON NOVEMBER 27, 2025 AT 9:00 A.M. TO 11:08 A.M.
PRESIDENT: Hon. Anastacio T. Mariñas, Jr. -Municipal Councilor/Temporary Presiding Officer
Hon. Christine A. Peralta -Municipal Councilor
Hon. Johnny P. Yaguinay -Municipal Councilor
Engr. Jorge S. Gomez -Municipal Councilor
Hon. Jonathan S. Quiriones -Municipal Councilor
Hon. Dawn Rane V. Algera, R.S.W. -Municipal Councilor
Hon. Reynaldo A. Valdez -Municipal Councilor
Hon. Jerry V. Jose -Lima President
Hon. John M. Dacumos -SKMP President
Hon. Jayson F. Panal -TSMR
ABSENT: Atty. Kruel J. D. Dacumos, J.D. -Municipal Vice Mayor/ Presiding Officer (On Official Business)
RESOLUTION NO. 193
Series of 2025
A RESOLUTION EXPRESSING THE PROFOUND GRATITUDE AND APPRECIATION OF THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT UNIT OF VILLAVERDE, NUEVA VIZCAYA TO SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY - SCHOOL OF ACCOUNTANCY AND BUSINESS, DEPARTMENT OF HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM MANAGEMENT, AND TO THE RESEARCHERS DR. MAYVELYN S. COVITA, MR. JOHN MICHAEL C. IBARRA, MR. MARK IAN J. SORIANO, AND REV. FR. CRISPIN A. COSTALES FOR THE PRODUCTION AND TURNOVER OF THE COFFEE TABLE BOOK ENTITLED "FAITHFUL STEWARDSHIP: A COMMUNITY-CENTRIC PILGRIMAGE SITE REVITALIZATION," WHICH SHALL SERVE AS AN IMPORTANT MATERIAL FOR THE LGU'S INVENTORY, ARCHIVAL RECORDS, AND TOURISM DEVELOPMENT EFFORTS OF MANGKELLEB HILL AND OTHER CULTURAL HERITAGE SITES IN VILLAVERDE.
WHEREAS, Saint Mary's University (SMU), through its School of Accountancy and Business - Department of Hospitality and Tourism Management, conducted a collaborative research study during Academic Year 2024-2025 focusing on the revitalization and cultural appreciation of community-based pilgrimage sites;
WHEREAS, the research team composed of Dr. Mayvelyn S. Covita, Mr. John Michael C. Ibarra, Mr. Mark Ian J. Soriano, and Rev. Fr. Crispin A. Costales produced a significant scholarly output in the form of a coffee table bookentitled "Faithful Stewardship: A Community-Centric Pilgrimage Site Revitalization," which compiles and documents historical, cultural, spiritual, and environmental narratives related to one of the Municipality of Villaverde's treasured landmarks—Mangkelleb Hill;

December 12, 2025

MR. JOHN C. IBARRA, CGSP, CHP, MSHRM
HIM Department Head
Saint Mary's University
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

Sir:
Christian Greetings!

Respectfully furnishing herewith the Sangguniang Bayan Resolution No. 193, Series of 2025, BE: "A RESOLUTION EXPRESSING THE PROFOUND GRATITUDE AND APPRECIATION OF THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT UNIT OF VILLAVERDE, NUEVA VIZCAYA TO SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY - SCHOOL OF ACCOUNTANCY AND BUSINESS, DEPARTMENT OF HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM MANAGEMENT, AND TO THE RESEARCHERS DR. MAYVELYN S. COVITA, MR. JOHN MICHAEL C. IBARRA, MR. MARK IAN J. SORIANO, AND REV. FR. CRISPIN A. COSTALES FOR THE PRODUCTION AND TURNOVER OF THE COFFEE TABLE BOOK ENTITLED "FAITHFUL STEWARDSHIP: A COMMUNITY-CENTRIC PILGRIMAGE SITE REVITALIZATION," WHICH SHALL SERVE AS AN IMPORTANT MATERIAL FOR THE LGU'S INVENTORY, ARCHIVAL RECORDS, AND TOURISM DEVELOPMENT EFFORTS OF MANGKELLEB HILL AND OTHER CULTURAL HERITAGE SITES IN VILLAVERDE" for your information and ready reference.

Thank you and God bless!
Very truly yours,

FERDINAND B. NOTO
Secretary to the Sanggunian

Received for MR. IBARRA on 12/12/2025

CEP-03**Project NURTURE: Navigating Unified Responsible Parenting Towards an Upgraded Resilient Education System**

Sherylou A. Benig, Marissa Lyn A. Labangcoc, Mary Rose C. Jontilano, and Geneveive R. Bendoy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Parents of children with special needs face profound and enduring challenges, particularly when their children are expected to remain highly dependent throughout their lives. Nevertheless, Special Education (SPED) programs provide structured opportunities to maximize these children's potential, enabling them to develop functional roles within their families and communities. Such programs address not only the children's growth and developmental needs but also their educational requirements, with SPED teachers offering consistent guidance, support, and care. Parents, in turn, play a critical role in shaping and navigating their children's life trajectories. The extension of care and support within the home environment is essential, though it must be balanced with attention to parental well-being and self-care. Accordingly, equipping parents with appropriate knowledge and skills through targeted health education interventions is imperative. This qualitative phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of parents raising children with special needs, examining the multifaceted challenges they encounter across diverse domains of life.

This study also underscored the importance of promoting responsible parenthood and family overall wellness, especially the important roles of parents of children with special needs, with them in good health as well. The sample size comprised eleven (11) participants who were primary caregivers of children with special needs currently enrolled in Bayombong, Solano, and Bambang SPED Centers, using an in-depth interview. Purposive sampling was used to collect the samples. A semi-structured interview method was used to collect relevant data from the participants. Thematic analysis was adopted to analyze the data organized into themes. Five themes emerged: parental response, acceptance process, normalizing care, limited self-care, and advocacy.

The findings of this study highlighted the multifaceted challenges encountered by parents of children with special needs. These results served as the foundation for the development of a health education intervention designed to support parents in both providing care for their children with developmental disabilities and attending to their own well-being, while fostering collaboration with other organizations undertaking similar initiatives to strengthen collective impact and broaden the reach of supportive resources.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Date: November 19, 2025

Venue: Solano East SPED Center

Theme: *Empowering Caregivers and Educators through Research-Based Strategies in SPED and Health Education*

The Research Utilization Program opened its doors at 8:00 AM, with participants registering, and the organizing team warmly facilitated the event. This initial segment set a welcoming, organized tone, ensuring that all attendees were welcomed and equipped with the necessary materials for the day's activities.

Opening Ceremonies

At 8:30 AM, Ms. Genevieve R. Bendoy, RN, LPT of Solano East Central SPED School, led a heartfelt opening prayer that grounded the gathering in gratitude, unity, and shared purpose. This was followed by the Opening Remarks and Statement of Objectives, which framed the day's mission: to bridge research and practice in special education and caregiving through collaborative learning.

Opening Messages

Mrs. Marissa Lyn A. Labangcoc, a Faculty Member of the Nursing Department at Saint Mary's University, provided a compelling background on the event, grounded in recent research findings. She clearly articulated the objectives and set expectations for the day, emphasizing the transformative potential of evidence-based caregiving.

Mrs. Teresita O. Cadeliña, MAEd MT-I, SPED Coordinator, expressed deep appreciation for the initiative. She underscored the urgent need for practical, inclusive strategies to support children with developmental and learning disabilities. Her message resonated with the audience, affirming that such training is vital to the school's mission and the community's growth.

Session 1: Understanding Developmental Disabilities (9:45 AM – 10:15 AM)

This session featured two enriching presentations:

Ms. Mary Rose C. Jontilano, from the Faculty of Nursing at SMU, discussed *Learning Disabilities*, offering practical teaching strategies and communication techniques tailored to diverse learner needs.

Dr. Sherylou A. Benig, Head of the Nursing Department, SMU, followed with a session on *Autism*, sharing caregiving strategies that emphasized empathy, structure, and responsive communication to foster meaningful connections.

Ice Breaker (10:15 AM)

To re-energize the participants, Research Assistants from SMU BSN3 level led a lively ice breaker filled with music, dancing, and laughter. Participants and educators enthusiastically joined in, creating a joyful atmosphere that strengthened camaraderie and prepared everyone for the interactive workshop ahead.

Workshop: Building a Support Network (10:20 AM – 10:45 AM)

This hands-on segment focused on caregiver well-being and emotional resilience. Participants engaged in:

- **Self-care strategies**, including *The Caregiver Basket* and *The Butterfly Hug Technique*, were demonstrated and practiced with care.
- **Sharing sessions**, where participants opened up about their personal journeys. These moments were deeply emotional and full of hope. Many reflected on their priorities and realized that self-care—often overlooked—was the missing “item” in their lives.
- Facilitators and the Solano SPED educators themselves shared personal wellness techniques such as deep breathing, prayer, gratitude journaling, and affirmations. One memorable quote shared was:

“Ang problema ay normal na dumarating na phase sa ating buhay. Ang mahalaga ay huwag nating tambayan at duon mamalagi sa phase na yan. Kailangan nating tanggapin, harapin, at gawan ng solusyon—then MOVE FORWARD.”

- **Evaluation and feedback** allowed participants to reflect on the session's impact and offer suggestions for future improvements.

This workshop was collaboratively facilitated by all discussants and research assistants, fostering a safe, participatory, and empowering environment.

Closing Remarks (11:00 AM)

The program concluded with heartfelt closing remarks from Dr. Sherylou A. Benig, who emphasized the importance of translating research into compassionate, inclusive action. She commended the participants for their engagement and encouraged continued collaboration in the service of holistic care and education.

Throughout the program, Ms. Genevieve R. Bendoy served as the master of ceremonies, guiding each segment with grace and precision, ensuring a smooth and organized flow of activities.

Documentation Of Utilization

Feedback from Clients Evaluation

Criteria	Average Rating	Description
Relevance of the topic	3.83	Very Good
Effectiveness of the speakers	3.95	Very Good
Effectiveness of the facilitators	3.93	Very Good
Effectiveness of activities logistics	3.80	Very Good
Overall	3.93	Very Good

Mean ranges: 1.00-1.74 (Poor), 1.75-2.49 (Fair), 2.50-3.24(Good), 3.25-4.00(Very Good)

The evaluation results of the seminar-workshop, as presented in the table, indicate an overall rating of very good ($X=3.93$). The specific criteria assessed yielded the following mean scores: relevance of the topic ($X=3.83$), effectiveness of the speakers ($X=3.95$), effectiveness of the facilitators (3.93), and activity logistics (3.80). Among these, activity logistics received the lowest mean score, suggesting the need for further improvement in the planning and organization of future seminar-workshops. This concern is substantiated by participant feedback, such as the remarks *"time is limited"*, as expressed by P12, and *"a longer time allotment for discussions"* as proposed by P3, which highlight the necessity of allocating sufficient time for meaningful engagement and dialogue.

Despite this noted limitation, the majority of participants expressed gratitude and appreciation for the conduct of the seminar-workshop. Their positive reception was evident in both their active participation and their verbal acknowledgments. For instance, P4 stated, *"Kudos, thank you for sharing your knowledge and expertise"*, while P9 emphasized the importance of continuity by remarking, *"Sana magpatuloy yung ganitong mga activities"*. These responses underscore the perceived value of the seminar-workshop and its relevance to the participants' professional and personal contexts.

It is important to note that the strategic activities implemented during the seminar-workshop represent only preliminary efforts. There remains a pressing need for sustained, systematic implementation of similar initiatives, particularly those focused on practical caregiving strategies. Such activities should emphasize effective communication and support for children with developmental and other disabilities. Moreover, they should aim to enhance parents' knowledge and skills in caregiving, thereby fostering more inclusive and responsive approaches to the needs of children with special needs.

CEP-04**Digital Discipleship: Shaping Critical Minds and Joyful Gospel-Based Values in Youth (A School-Parish-Based Youth Encounter Project)**

Henry F. Gamboa, Epifanio Delbert G. Galima III, Edjohn B. Antonino, Benito D. Buyacco, Jr., Bryan Benedict D. Olarte, and Victor M. Abijay

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The study revealed that religiosity and religious identity remain salient in students' lives regardless of age, sex, or school type. Despite the increasing influence of secularization on educational and societal structures, Filipino youth maintain strong religious orientations. This continuity is attributed to the reinforcing roles of school-based religious instruction, family upbringing, and active Church and parish programs. Notably, both public and private school students affirm that faith is central to their identity, with no significant difference in the depth of religious belief between the two groups.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT**A. Dissemination and General Orientation (August-September)**

The implementation process commenced with the Dissemination of the Study, the School-Parish Coordination Meetings, and the general orientation, which were conducted from August to September 2025. During this stage, the study's key findings were formally presented to school leaders, parish priests, and campus ministers. Notably, Aritao National High School participated in this activity, represented by Mrs. Helen G. De Guzman, the Guidance Counselor designate, through the coordination and approval of the School Head, Mr. Oscar T. Castro Jr. The dissemination also benefited from the support and involvement of Fr. Victor Abijay, President of St. Louis College, Inc., Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, which further strengthened collaboration between educational institutions and parish communities.

As part of this dissemination phase, the general orientation for youth facilitators, including the research team members, was conducted from August through September, ensuring that all facilitators clearly understood the program's goals, expectations, and implementation framework. These meetings allowed all partners to establish shared objectives, synchronize schedules, and clarify responsibilities, fostering a unified direction between schools and parishes.

Moreover, initial discussions and orientations were held to prepare for student activities. Through constant communication and guidance, the facilitators strengthened their confidence, deepened their understanding of their roles, and adequately prepared themselves to guide the youth in achieving the program's intended goals.

B. Youth Prayer Encounter and Group Dynamics (October-November)

The Youth Encounter Sessions, held from October to November 2025, were one of the program's core formative components. These sessions were designed to provide spiritually enriching experiences for students through meaningful, faith-based interactions. Guided by youth leaders, catechists, and trained facilitators, the sessions

offered young participants opportunities for prayer, reflection, small-group sharing, community-building activities, and values-centered discussions.

During these encounters, students were given safe and supportive spaces to express their thoughts, explore personal and spiritual insights, and strengthen their sense of belonging within the school-parish community. Facilitators played an essential role in fostering an environment of openness, mutual respect, and active participation. Their prior orientation and continuous coordination helped ensure that each activity was delivered intentionally and aligned with the program's goals.

The Youth Encounter Sessions not only deepened the students' understanding of their faith but also fostered leadership, collaboration, and empathy. Many students manifested confidence, stronger peer relationships, and a renewed commitment to positive values—clear indicators of the transformative impact of these encounters. Hence, these sessions contributed significantly to nurturing well-formed, value-driven young individuals within the partnering schools and parishes.

C. Culminating Activity and the Launching of FB Social Media Platform, *Discipulus Christus Digitalis* (November-December)

From November to December, a planned program culminated with a comprehensive Forum on Media and Legal Literacy and Faith Integration, highlighted by the keynote talk of Atty. Epifanio Delbert G. Galima, Dean of the College of Law and SMU Legal Counsel, discussed *Digital Discipleship* and the legal foundations supporting responsible and faith-aligned media engagement. The culminating event also featured the launching of the *Discipulus Christus Digitalis* Facebook platform, a space where young Christians can post and share their faith experiences and video reflections. Alongside these initiatives, the program continued to promote faith in action through various service-learning activities that encouraged community involvement and environmental awareness, while also sustaining post-encounter spiritual growth through online faith-sharing spaces. The culmination successfully engaged more than 700 Marian first-year college students, including barangay SK officials, student leaders, parish youth leaders, members of various Christian denominations, and NSTP coordinators, marking a vibrant and inclusive celebration of digital discipleship and youth empowerment.

D. Post-Encounter Online Faith Sharing Spaces and launching of the Digital Discipleship Social Media Convergence Platform and Initial Evaluation and Monitoring (December and Onwards)

Following the youth encounter activities, Post-Encounter Online Faith Sharing Spaces were established, along with the launch of the Digital Discipleship Social Media Convergence Platform, which began in December 2025 and continues to this day. These initiatives provided youth with accessible avenues for reflection, faith sharing, and community engagement beyond the physical encounter sessions. The activities were widely commended by facilitators, church leaders, and school heads, who recognized their significant role in helping young people navigate and cope with the challenges of secularization.

The online platform also served as a venue for initial program evaluation and monitoring, allowing facilitators and coordinators to track participation and engagement. The activities continued to be appreciated, as reflected in the positive comments and interactions on Facebook, where many young Christians shared video reflections and personal experiences from the encounters.

Based on its initial utilization, the research study *Navigating Secularization: A Fresh Approach to a New Phase of Evangelizing the Christian Youth in Veritatis Gaudium (The Joy of Truth)*, along with its implementation program, *Digital Discipleship: Shaping Critical Minds and Joyful Gospel-Based Values in Youth (A School-Parish-Based Youth Encounter Project)*, proved successful in engaging the youth, fostering critical thinking, and promoting gospel-based values in the context of contemporary challenges.

E. Future Perspectives and Engagements (Re-Scheduled in January 2026)

Aritao National High School and St. Louis College of Solano

I. REGISTRATION
 Management of Learning Bone North IS

II. SESSION PROPER
 AI and Digital Technologies Steven Pablona
 SST-II, ICT Coordinator
 Research Dissemination Henry F. Gamba, PhD
 Associate Dean, Student Affairs and Services (Men)
 Special Session on Bullying Atty. Epifanio Delbert G. Galina III
 Dean, College of Law and Legal Counsel
 Reproductive Health Education for Adolescent Learners Archie Philip Sandoval
 SST-II, School Nurse

III. CLOSING PROGRAM
 Closing Prayer Rose Ann R. Manalo
 SST-III
 Impressions Leonida Gaspar
 SHS Faculty Member
 Robelina Espera
 JHS Faculty Member
 Pledge of Commitment Jayson I. Pascua
 SHS Assistant Principal Designate
 Ways Forward Oscar T. Castro Jr.
 Aritao NHS, School Head
 Awarding of Certificates

Master of Ceremonies:
 Haricane T. Rodillas
 SST-III

IN-SERVICE Training 2025
 November 27-29, 2025
 7:30 AM - 5:00 PM
 ANHS Gymnasium

Documentation Of Utilization

Conversation with Aritao National High School

Conversation with St. Louis College of Solano, Inc.

Parish

Aritao National High School and St. Teresita

St. Louis College of Solano and St. Louis Beltran Parish

Saint Mary's University, First-Year College Students
Facilitated by Mr. Benito Buyacco

Facilitated by Mr. Bryan Benedict Olarte

Facilitated by Mr. Edjohn Antonino

Culminating Activity and the Launching of FB Social Media Platform, Discipulus Christus Digitalis

The Launching of the

Discipulus Christi Digitalis Facebook

Post-Encounter Online Faith Sharing Spaces and launching of the Digital Discipleship Social Media Convergence Platform, and Initial Evaluation and Monitoring

CEP-05**LINK for LIFE Initiative: Fostering Care and Connection for Filipino Elderly through Health Awareness Drives and Wellness Promotion, Creating Informative Brochures for Community Impact**

Melchora M. Bautista, May Juliet S. Palina, and Brent Jericko P. Narciso

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study aimed to implement and evaluate the LIFE (Love Intervention for Filipino Elderly) program among the chosen elderly in Bayombong. Specifically, it sought to describe the elderly respondents' physical health and wellness, social connection, and emotional support before and after the LIFE program using the World Health Organization's Quality of Life (WHOQoL) tool; describe the involvement and participation of elderly respondents during the program; and determine the impact of the LIFE program on their quality of life. Results showed marked improvements across multiple domains following the intervention. Before the LIFE program, respondents reported being only moderately contented with life (mean: 2.93) and health (mean: 2.85). After implementation, life satisfaction increased substantially (mean: 3.75), and health satisfaction also improved (mean: 3.24). Participation in physical, social, and emotional activities increased, with enjoyment in life and sense of meaning both rising to a moderate to great extent. Capacity for daily activities remained high, with mean scores improving from 4.14 (very much capable) to 4.40 post-intervention. Satisfaction with various aspects of life, including sleep, daily activities, personal relationships, and access to services, also improved, with the mean satisfaction score rising from 3.37 to 4.01. Emotional well-being showed notable gains, as the frequency of negative emotions such as irritation, anxiety, and loneliness decreased from "quite often" (mean: 2.94) to "seldom" (mean: 2.29) experienced after the program. Respondents expressed high satisfaction with the LIFE program interventions, particularly social visits and emotional counseling, and identified a strong ongoing need for social and emotional support. The findings demonstrate that the LIFE program significantly enhanced the quality of life, well-being, and satisfaction of elderly participants in Bayombong, underscoring the value of structured, community-based interventions for older adults. Future iterations should focus on sustaining long-term program benefits through continuous connections and linkages to enhance the quality of life for the elderly population.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The intervention activity aligned with Project LINK's objective of conducting interactive health awareness drives and wellness workshops to improve elderly physical health and wellness. Initial coordination began with a formal letter to Rev. Fr. Vicente T. Tiam, President of the Tiam-Tumaliuan Foundation (TTF), which the coordinator, Mrs. Letticia Ruiz, facilitated and sent on November 5, 2025.

To organize interactive health awareness drives and wellness workshops tailored to the needs of older people, resource support was sought through a letter emailed to the Department of Health (DOH) via a colleague's contact. DOH responded promptly with a PDF brochure tailored to elderly health needs, which was reproduced for distribution to all 40 elderly recipients.

Given DOH's limited assistance, a strategic pivot involved inviting domain experts. Letters were sent to the President of Nueva Vizcaya State University (NVSU), requesting that Dr. Maria Teresa A. Fulgencio, Director of the NVSU Food Processing Center, lecture

on elderly nutritional diets. Additionally, Mr. Diego B. Cabalar, Chairman of DSWD Cluster 4 (Nueva Vizcaya), was invited to discuss the benefits of the National Commission on the Elderly (NCE) program. The event, held on November 22, 2025, was themed “Fostering Care and Connection through Health Awareness Drives, Wellness Promotion, and Education.” Volunteers included five Saint Mary's University (SMU) Pharmacy students, two Marian Nurses alumni, one Marian ECE graduate, research collaborator Ms. Julie Palina, and Mrs. Essel Canaberal (SMU CICT Director and TTF Executive Secretary).

Lecturers Dr. Fulgencio and Mr. Cabalar delivered sessions on nutrition and government benefits. Lead researcher Melchora M. Bautista facilitated a discussion of the DOH handbook before distribution. Additional services provided free medicines, vital signs monitoring, "Go Bags" with essential guides, and the reproduced DOH handbooks. Pharmacy student volunteers collected participant feedback to evaluate the impact.

The failure to implement a structured schedule of social visits by trained volunteers or community health workers to provide companionship, monitor well-being, and identify emerging needs was offset by the optimized services provided to the elderly recipients.

Connecting with those who can provide care for older people was the cornerstone and pivot of this project, made possible through sincere communication.

Documentation Of Utilization

Feedback from Clients

Level of satisfaction of elderly participants- 4.75/5

Synthesized comments and requests:

Participants expressed high satisfaction with the lecture on elderly nutrition, which reminded them of key dietary needs, such as reducing rice intake and increasing intake of vegetables, fruits, and protein. The handbook was well-received, though participants needed individual guidance to complete it effectively. Mr. Cabalar's presentation on NCE benefits left participants in awe, as they gained awareness of their entitlements and rights. Free medicines provided based on participants' prescriptions were accepted with deep gratitude and happiness. The go bags were a new item for them that required explanation for their appropriate use.

CEP-06**Beyond the Classroom: Empowering Leaders through SDG-Focused Advocacy and Project Development for Real-World Impact (Seminar-Workshop with a Student-led Project Proposal)**

Kenneth L. Maslang, Darwin Don M. Dacles, and Armand N. Camhol

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study explored the nature of student leadership and the role of higher education institutions in nurturing purpose-driven leaders who can drive community advocacy. Using the Student Leadership Practices Inventory (SLPI) by Kouzes and Posner, the study examined leadership behaviors among student leaders and the institutional mechanisms that supported their development. The research also assessed the effectiveness of student-led advocacy initiatives, identified implementation challenges, and facilitated the creation of action plans to advance community-focused efforts.

Employing a mixed-methods design, the study combined surveys of student leaders with interviews from faculty and institutional stakeholders. Results showed that *Modeling the Way* and *Inspiring a Shared Vision* were the most consistently practiced leadership behaviors. Institutional support, such as leadership training, mentoring, and support for student organizations, significantly contributed to leadership development. Advocacy initiatives focused on mental health, environmental sustainability, civic engagement, and gender equality demonstrated measurable community impact, especially when backed by partnerships with local stakeholders.

However, challenges such as limited funding, insufficient sustained institutional support, and difficulty mobilizing peers were commonly reported. The study led to the development of actionable advocacy plans tailored to students' chosen causes.

Overall, the findings highlighted the importance of structured leadership development and collaborative frameworks in empowering student leaders to become catalysts for social change. The study offered recommendations to strengthen institutional support and ensure the sustainability of student-led initiatives, emphasizing the critical role of higher education in fostering a culture of civic responsibility and engaged leadership.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The utilization project titled "Beyond the Classroom: Empowering Leaders through SDG-Focused Advocacy and Project Development for Real-World Impact" was implemented to translate research findings into concrete leadership development initiatives for student leaders across Nueva Vizcaya. Grounded in the results of an earlier empirical study on student leadership formation, the project focused on two strategic objectives: organizing hybrid leadership training and workshops, and reviewing and integrating leadership-related topics in selected General Education courses such as Rizal, Contemporary World, and Ethics.

To accomplish the first strategic objective, asynchronous virtual meetings were conducted to provide flexible engagement with student leaders from six higher education institutions in the province. During these sessions, student leaders received notes on leadership and summaries of the empirical findings, which served as the basis for understanding their roles, competencies, and developmental needs. This virtual phase served as preparation for the culminating in-person activity.

The asynchronous meetings concluded with a face-to-face seminar-workshop held on December 6, 2025, in collaboration with MAT Social Studies students. The activity was attended by 84 student leaders and 4 faculty members from 6 higher education institutions in Nueva Vizcaya. The seminar-workshop provided opportunities for hands-on learning, collaborative discussions, and guided project development aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals. Through these engagements, participants strengthened their capabilities for effective, accountable, and development-oriented leadership.

For the second strategic objective, integration of leadership-related lessons was implemented in the General Education courses Rizal and The Contemporary World. In Rizal, topics such as the youth's role in nation-building, civic responsibility, and the development of civic virtues were emphasized. In The Contemporary World, lessons related to global citizenship, sustainable development, and current global issues were enriched with leadership-oriented discussions and applied activities.

One of the project's outcomes was a student-led proposal titled the Youth Accelerator Project. Its goals were to develop core leadership competencies such as communication, critical thinking, conflict resolution, and teamwork; foster civic engagement by encouraging youth to address community issues; cultivate ethical decision-making based on integrity, responsibility, and empathy; and establish a mentorship network linking youth with community and professional leaders. The proposal will be enhanced further and submitted to the Provincial Youth Development Council of Nueva Vizcaya for their perusal and appropriate action.

Overall, the utilization project successfully connected academic insights with practical, community-focused leadership development. By integrating research findings, instructional activities, and student-led initiatives, the project helped develop young leaders prepared to create meaningful, real-world impact aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals.

Documentation Of Utilization

1. Asynchronous Meetings

Title pages of three materials distributed during asynchronous meetings with student leaders across six HEIs in Nueva Vizcaya from August to October 2025.

Sample webinar with student leaders' attendance

2. Face-to-Face Meeting

Presentation of Dr. Kenneth L. Maslang on the significant findings of their study and providing a synthesis of the 5-month-long asynchronous meetings with student leaders.

Student leaders from six HEIs in Nueva Vizcaya

3. Integration of some of the findings in Rizal and GC World Module

RIZAL
A Life and Works

Kenneth L. Maslang, M.A. Ed.
Darwin Don Mallo Dacles, Ph.D.
Fe Yolanda Gatan Del Rosario, Ph.D.

CHED General Education Learning Outcomes Compliant

About the Authors

Kenneth Lwamin Maslang is from Labay, Bantay, Paracelis, Mountain Province. He finished his tertiary education at the University of the Philippines, Los Baños, Laguna. He worked as an English Teacher at the Fair East English Language Center, was once a member of the TES Staff Professional Consultancy and Educational Consultant at the Gooder's International, Inc., Legazpi Village, Makati. He finished his MAEd Degree at Saint Mary's University in March 2009, with Distinction and currently a PhD candidate in Educational Management.

He served as the coordinator of the Indigenous Knowledge and Tradition (IKAT) Center in 2014 - 2018 and the Lingkod Maria Community Development and Advocacy Center (LMCDAC) in 2019 - 2022 before becoming the Head of the Social Sciences and Philosophy Department under the School of Teacher Education and Humanities of SMU. He obtained his certificate of attendance and completion as a national trainer for the new General Education Curriculum on Rizal from Ateneo De Manila University. He also helps organize regional, national and international research forums and co-authored several institutional books such as Asian Civilization, World Religions, The Contemporary World and Practical Research 2 for Grade 12 students.

He completed his Master of Arts in Teaching Social Studies in 2002. Prior to his becoming a part of SMU family in 2009, he served as the Department Head of the Humanities in Philippine Science High School and classroom teacher in Don Bosco High School, St. Teresia's Academy, Ateneo High School & Sta Clara High School.

He finished his Doctor of Philosophy major in Educational Management at Saint Mary's University in 2010, cum laude. He is presently a faculty member of the School of Teacher Education and Humanities and became the Department Head of the Social Sciences for two years. He served as the Research Coordinator of the then School of Arts & Sciences and the Indigenous Knowledge & Tradition Center of SMU in 2010 - 2011, Director of IKAT Center in 2011 - 2019, Director of LMCDAC in 2019-2021 before becoming the Director of the Research Center in August 2021.

He is a book writer who authored and co-authored books such as Asian Civilization, Philippine History, Roots and Development, World Religions, The Contemporary World and Practical Research 2 for the Senior High School students.

Darwin Don Mallo Dacles is from Pob. Antao, Nueva Vizcaya. He finished his tertiary education in 1989 at Saint Mary's University with the Degree Bachelor of Science in Education, Major in History & Religious Formation.

He completed his Master of Arts in Teaching Social Studies in 2002. Prior to his becoming a part of SMU family in 2009, he served as the Department Head of the Humanities in Philippine Science High School and classroom teacher in Don Bosco High School, St. Teresia's Academy, Ateneo High School & Sta Clara High School.

He finished his Doctor of Philosophy major in Educational Management at Saint Mary's University in 2010, cum laude. He is presently a faculty member of the School of Teacher Education and Humanities and became the Department Head of the Social Sciences for two years. He served as the Research Coordinator of the then School of Arts & Sciences and the Indigenous Knowledge & Tradition Center of SMU in 2010 - 2011, Director of IKAT Center in 2011 - 2019, Director of LMCDAC in 2019-2021 before becoming the Director of the Research Center in August 2021.

He is a book writer who authored and co-authored books such as Asian Civilization, Philippine History, Roots and Development, World Religions, The Contemporary World and Practical Research 2 for the Senior High School students.

Fe Yolanda Gatan Del Rosario is a graduate of Bachelor's Degree in the Arts with majors in English and History from Saint Mary's University in 1981, magna cum laude. She finished her Master of Arts in History at the University of the Philippines, Diliman in 1997 with Anthropology as her cognate subject. Her interest in anthropological studies may be gleaned from her extensive study of the Ilonggos and Ibinay, 1691 - 1947: Isang Dugtungan sa Kasaysayan Lokal ng Nueva Vizcaya.

She finished her Doctor of Philosophy in Philippine Studies in 2010 at the University of the Philippines, Diliman, Quezon City. She is a faculty member of the School of Teacher Education and Humanities from 1981 to the present and was head of the Social Sciences Department for more than ten years. She served as the Director of the Indigenous Knowledge & Tradition Center of Saint Mary's University in 2010 - 2011, Director of the Research Center in 2011 - 2020, and Academic Dean in 2020 - 2021.

Saint Mary's University
PUBLICATION AND DIGITAL PRINTING OFFICE

The CONTEMPORARY WORLD

JOSEPH M. CRISTOBAL • KADESH EXODIUS T. BERDERLANCO • RAYMUNDO S. SANVAZARES
DARWIN DON M. DACLES • VERCELLE A. DOCCOD • KENEDY G. FLORES
CLIFFORD LUIS T. LEDNES • ERWIN A. MALLO
DIGNA RUTH A. MARIÑAS • KENNETH L. MASLANG • DULCE M. RODRIGUEZ
RONNIE B. SORIANO • MARGIE IMELDA T. VILORIA

PAZ O. BAILON
Editor

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

MARGIE IMELDA T. VILORIA is a professor of the Social Science Department at Saint Louis College, La Union. She finished her Bachelor of Arts in Political Science and History and earned her Master of Arts in Education, majoring in Administration at the same institution. She has been teaching various General Education courses for almost 20 years, including Readings in the Philippine History, Life and Works of Dr. Jose Rizal, The Contemporary World, and Public Science courses.

KENNETH L. MASLANG is an Associate Professor and currently the Head of the Social Sciences and Philosophy Department at the School of Teacher Education and Humanities of Saint Mary's University, Nueva Vizcaya. He is also a faculty member of the School of Graduate Studies, specifically in the Master of Arts in Teaching Social Studies program. In 2009, he graduated with distinction and received the URSA award from Saint Mary's University with a Master of Arts in Education. He is presently a PhD candidate in the Educational Management program. Mr. Maslang has significantly contributed as an author and co-author of several institutional publications at Saint Mary's University, including Rizal's Life and Works, Asian Civilization, World Religions, The Contemporary World, and Practical Research 2 designed for Grade 12 students.

KENEDY G. FLORES is a college instructor specializing in Social Sciences. He earned his Bachelor of Arts in Political Science from Saint Louis College, La Union in 2022. He teaches diverse courses, including the Life and Works of Dr. Jose Rizal, Readings in Philippine History, The Contemporary World, Gender and Society, Philippine Political Thought, Parliamentary Procedure, and International Political Studies. He has also completed the academic requirements for his Master's Degree in Public Administration. He is one of the authors in several Social Science textbooks, such as Readings in Philippine History, Life and Works of Dr. Rizal, and Art Appreciation.

DIGNA RUTH A. MARIÑAS received her Bachelor of Arts in Economics from Saint Louis College, La Union in 1996, her Certificate in Teaching in 2000, and her Master of Business Administration in 2023. She is currently enrolled in PhD Management and has earned 21 academic units in the School of Advanced Studies of Saint Mary's University. She has been a college instructor since 2015, teaching The Contemporary World and other Social Science courses. She also contributes to research in the field of education.

MINDSHAPERS CO., INC
PUBLISHERS COMPANY
P.O. Box 108, San Antonio Corporate Plaza Bldg., Bacolod, Negros Occidental, Mankay
Mobile: 09182216499 • Fax: 09182216499 • Email: mindshapersco@yahoo.com
www.mindshapersco.com

MEMBER:
BOOK DEVELOPMENT ASSOCIATION OF THE PHILIPPINES
NBDB

ISBN 978-621-063680-9
9 786214 063680

4. Copy of the Youth Accelerate Project Proposal

Youth Leadership Accelerator

Organization:

Contact Person and Details:

Submission Date:

2 | Page Youth Leadership Accelerator

Executive Summary

Jore Rial's oft-repeated saying that the youth are the hope of the country is not an overstatement nor an exaggeration. The principle behind this ageless theme is that a strong society needs to prepare its next-generation leaders and servants for the role of nurturing, growing, and sustainably developing the country, starting with communities. In the turbulent age of government corruption, unsustainable resources extraction, climate change and AI, there is a need to build strong, informed, and resilient leaders who will lead their communities in thriving amidst these daunting issues and challenges.

Towards this aim, the next leaders need to be capacitated in terms of core leadership competencies, community engagement, ethical decision-making, and mentorship with experienced and well-established specialists and leaders. For one year, a pool of promising young leaders selected in a merit-based competitive process will undergo forging under the close supervision of mentors. Their enthusiasm, energy, and knowledge of issues and problems within their communities will be tested and tried with solutions and answers brought up, co-developed, and implemented.

This proposal outlines a one-year project designed to identify, train, and mentor young individuals to become effective and ethical leaders in their communities. The program will employ a phased approach combining workshops, practical application, and sustained mentorship. In the end of the project, it is hoped that 25 young women and men are empowered to lead their communities in facing up to the issues and tasks. Co-managed with the Saint Mary's University and the local government units of Nueva Vizcaya, the project has a proposed budget of Php270,000 which includes seed money for small community projects.

3 | Page Youth Leadership Accelerator

Background

The recent onslaught of Super typhoon Uwan and other typhoons, the continued entry of mining activities in the Province of Nueva Vizcaya and unsustainable resources extraction, the educational crisis, and the persistent corruption in government have been exposing the weaknesses of the Philippines and its various communities at large in terms of social and physical infrastructures, food resilience, and readiness in terms of disasters. We face problems in huge proportions that need to be faced and met squarely and head-on.

In this regard, the youth need to be capacitated as crucial community development partners and near-future leaders. Engrossed in their own personal issues which include exceedingly high utilization of digital tech gadgets, smartphone apps, among others, they need to be roused from their digital captivity and into the real world to start learning and contributing to their respective communities. The continuing investigations and revelations on government corruption may be leaving a bad taste in their mouths and a propensity to move away from involvement in government and civic activities. The challenge is to make them understand that they can begin contributing their talents within their own communities and help promote UN Sustainable Development Goals #2- Zero hunger, #4- Quality education, #8- Decent work & economic growth, #10- Reduced inequalities, #11- Sustainable cities & inequalities, #13- Climate action, #16- Peace, justice, & strong institutions, and #17- Partnerships for the goals.

Rationale

Partly because of digital technology, there is a perception that today's youth are disconnected from the day-to-day realities in their communities. Issues and problems related to things as simple as physical, mental and emotional well-being, solid waste management, sanitation, peace and order, and community harmony to more complex ones such as disaster readiness, food security, and governance seem to escape the attention and interest of young women and men as they go about in their day-to-day activities in school and/or work.

The truth is that the youth's attention- more than ever- are divided across three realms- the digital, the emotional/mental, and the real world. To draw their attention and involvement in improving community resilience, they have to be creatively drawn from their bubbles and individual shells towards active community participation. Furthermore, these young people need to be elevated towards more engaging and responsible roles.

4 | Page Youth Leadership Accelerator

Project Goals

The primary goals of the Youth Leadership Accelerator are to:

- **Develop core leadership competencies:** Equip participants with essential skills such as communication, critical thinking, conflict resolution, and teamwork.
- **Foster civic engagement:** Encourage youth to identify and actively address issues within their communities.
- **Cultivate ethical decision-making:** Promote a strong sense of integrity, responsibility, and empathy in future leaders.
- **Establish a sustained mentorship network:** Connect participants with established community and professional leaders.

Apart from these major goals, the 25 youth leaders will be capacitated with community issues, jargon, and principles in relation to poverty, sustainable development, and climate change. As empowered leaders, they will be trained to face them with intellect and know-how, organizational capabilities, resilience, and unflinching courage.

UN SDGs
2. Zero hunger
4. Quality education
8. Decent work & economic growth
10. Reduced inequalities
11. Sustainable cities & communities
13. Climate action
16. Peace, justice & strong institutions
17. Partnerships for the goals

Participant Profile and Selection

The program targets **20-25 motivated youth** aged 16- 22 who demonstrate potential for leadership but may lack formal training or opportunity.

Selection Criteria: Demonstrated commitment to community service, a clear interest in leadership development, and proven resilience.

Selection Process: Open application, followed by an interview process conducted by the project steering committee.

Project Timeline and Activities

The project is structured into four distinct phases, each lasting three months.

Phase 1: Foundation and Skill Building (Months 1-3)

This phase focuses on introducing core leadership concepts and essential soft skills.

Activity 1: Kick-off Retreat (2 days)

Team-building exercises, vision setting, and an introduction to the concept of **servant leadership**.

Feedback from Clients

The asynchronous sessions were appreciated for providing flexibility and accessible learning opportunities. Students were able to review leadership notes and research-based insights at their own pace, allowing them to reflect on the material before the culminating activity. Several participants expressed positive sentiments about the content, noting that it was timely, relevant, and valuable to their development as leaders. Comments such as *“It is a nice topic to learn about being a leader”* and *“Overall, the event was timely and valuable”* captured the perceived usefulness of the program.

However, the primary weakness identified in the virtual format was inconsistent internet connectivity. Participants noted that unstable connections hindered smooth participation, as reflected in the feedback: *“Only the consistency of connectivity.”* This highlighted the limitations of relying solely on virtual platforms, especially in areas with varying levels of technological access.

The face-to-face seminar-workshop held on December 6, 2025, addressed several of these concerns. Students described the in-person event as engaging, well-organized, and motivating. Feedback such as *“All in all it was a good seminar, job well done,”* and *“It was a really great session, and I hope we can continue this in future seminars”* indicated a high level of satisfaction with the quality of facilitation and the overall learning experience. Participants valued the opportunity for direct interaction, collaboration, and personal connection with facilitators and fellow student leaders – elements that were more difficult to replicate in an asynchronous environment. One participant even recommended strengthening this format further, stating, *“All is good, maybe we can have a seminar next time with team-building activities,”* suggesting a desire for more dynamic, experiential engagements.

Another suggestion emerging from the feedback was the call to expand participation in future activities. A student noted, *“My suggestion is to invite more student leaders to participate, so that they can broaden their knowledge in their endeavors.”* This recommendation underscored the program's perceived impact and the belief that more students could benefit from the sessions.

Overall, the feedback demonstrated that the hybrid format was effective in delivering leadership-focused training aligned with the goals of the utilization project. The asynchronous sessions provided foundational knowledge and accommodated diverse schedules, while the face-to-face seminar strengthened engagement, collaboration, and applied learning. The main challenges centered on internet connectivity during virtual meetings and the desire for broader participation and more interactive in-person activities. These insights will help refine future leadership development initiatives to support student leaders across the province better.

However, the primary weakness identified in the virtual format was inconsistent internet connectivity. Participants noted that unstable connections hindered smooth participation, as reflected in the feedback: *"Only the consistency of connectivity."* This highlighted the limitations of relying solely on virtual platforms, especially in areas with varying levels of technological access.

The face-to-face seminar-workshop held on December 6, 2025, addressed several of these concerns. Students described the in-person event as engaging, well-organized, and motivating. Feedback such as *"All in all it was a good seminar, job well done,"* and *"It was a really great session, and I hope we can continue this in future seminars"* indicated a high level of satisfaction with the quality of facilitation and the overall learning experience. Participants valued the opportunity for direct interaction, collaboration, and personal connection with facilitators and fellow student leaders – elements that were more difficult to replicate in an asynchronous environment. One participant even recommended strengthening this format, stating, *"All is good, maybe we can have a seminar next time with team-building activities,"* suggesting a desire for more dynamic, experiential engagements.

Another suggestion emerging from the feedback was the call to expand participation in future activities. A student noted, *"My suggestion is invite more student leaders to participate, so that they can broaden their knowledge in their endeavors."* This recommendation underscored the program's perceived impact and the belief that more students could benefit from the sessions.

Overall, the feedback demonstrated that the hybrid format was effective in delivering leadership-focused training aligned with the goals of the utilization project. The asynchronous sessions provided foundational knowledge and accommodated diverse schedules, while the face-to-face seminar strengthened engagement, collaboration, and applied learning. The main challenges centered on internet connectivity during virtual meetings and the desire for broader participation and more interactive in-person activities. These insights will help refine future leadership development initiatives to support student leaders across the province better better.

CEP-07**Speak Easy: A Public Speaking Anxiety Reduction Support Mechanism**

Lysel I. Haloc, Mr. Christian Jos M. Obaña, and Ma. Ines R. Minia

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Speaking is one of the most challenging macro-linguistic skills to develop among learners; hence, public speaking is usually the most common activity that individuals dislike, fear, or avoid. Hence, the empirical study aims to identify the level of public speaking anxiety among senior high school students in selected schools in Bayombong, Bambang, and Dupax del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya. The study employed a mixed-methods, quantitative approach and purposive sampling to select respondents. To measure the level of speech anxiety among the respondents, the researchers will use a published tool, the Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety, adapted from Richmond and McCroskey's (1998) "Communication Apprehension, Avoidance and Effectiveness". The results showed that a significant proportion of students experienced high levels of anxiety. Also, variables such as sex, type of school, and strand are associated with differences in anxiety, while first language is not. Moreover, exposure to English reading materials has a limited relationship with public anxiety among students. Ultimately, the study also aims to serve as a basis for crafting a support mechanism to optimize students' oral communication skills by reducing speech anxiety. The proposed support mechanism is titled "Speak Easy: A Public Speaking Anxiety Reduction Support Mechanism". Therefore, this study has pedagogical implications for teaching and learning public speaking.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The researchers first sought permission from the school principals of the two participating schools. Once permission was granted, the researchers asked their oral communication teachers for assistance in identifying prospective student participants. Teachers observed that these students avoid class participation, exhibit physical and emotional manifestations of public speaking anxiety, and have poor oral communication performance. A total of 43 students were identified. These students belong to the TVL, ABM, and HUMSS strands. Since the identified participants belong to the vulnerable group, parental and student consent were secured. The consent underscores that adequate safeguarding will be provided to maintain the privacy and confidentiality of their responses. Also, names will not ultimately be used to identify answers; instead, code numbers will be used. Moreover, the consent stipulates that the researchers have thoroughly explained the investigation and that relevant questions will be answered—only those with signed consent participated in strategic activities.

The researchers requested a room for conducting the strategic activities. The rooms provided were quiet, private, comfortable, and free from distractions. The environment fostered an informal, relaxed atmosphere, allowing open, non-threatening, and honest dialogue among participants and researchers. To ease the expression of their ideas, participants were allowed to use the language they were comfortable with. In the structured interview, the following questions were asked:

1. Of all the speech activities you have in class, which are you most nervous of? Why?
2. What are the reasons you feel nervous when speaking in front?
3. How about the least anxiety-arousing?
4. What speech activity do you enjoy the most?
5. How can your teachers help you improve your public speaking skills?

For Question Number 1, most of the participants identified spontaneous speaking activities, such as impromptu speech and extemporaneous speech, as the most anxiety-inducing activities. These findings are supported by studies by Plandano et al. (2023), Haloc (2016), and Haloc et al. (2025), which reveal that senior high school students and college sophomores, respectively, exhibit very high levels of anxiety during impromptu speech performances. This is primarily due to the lack of preparation time, which triggers fear of judgment, making mistakes, or going blank.

Moreover, the participants shared the reasons they feel nervous when speaking in front of the class or simply when asked to recite. Some participants reported feeling very nervous during the speech and embarrassed after delivering it. Most of them said that delivering a speech in English is a challenging task, due to a lack of vocabulary and fear of being laughed at due to grammatical lapses. Upon evaluating the responses, it can be said that the common factors that contributed to the respondents' high level of anxiety were nervousness, embarrassment, and fear of judgment, as well as a lack of vocabulary skills. Research indicates that the fear of making mistakes often stems from a fear of negative evaluation and the possibility of embarrassment. This can significantly hinder language learners' willingness to engage in speaking activities.

For Question Number 3, the least anxiety-arousing speech activities are collaborative speaking tasks such as group reports and choric recitation of poetry. Collaborative speech tasks are less stressful than individual performances because they shift the focus from individual evaluation to shared responsibility, creating a more supportive, relaxed, and engaging learning atmosphere. Moreover, the participants noted that speech activities that require more time to prepare do not cause them too much stress. These include semi-memorized and memorized speeches. This relates to the types of speech activities they enjoyed most. The majority of the participants agreed that creative oral group presentations, such as role-playing, dramatization, and group poetry recitation, were more enjoyable. These types of presentations are interactive, collaborative, and ultimately less intimidating.

Based on the responses, the participants posited that teachers could help them address their fear of public speaking by giving them more time to prepare, providing thorough explanations of speech activities, answering questions, and offering encouragement before and after speech presentations. Some students also shared that breathing exercises and practicing speech techniques help them relax before delivery.

The second stage in the mechanism involved lectures on the nature of public speaking, speech anxiety as a common social phobia, and guidelines in building speaker confidence. The researchers who served as lecturers highlighted that public speaking offers personal, professional, and public benefits. Moreover, they emphasized that effective oral communication skills are integral in varied fields of study. Also, they discussed the results of the empirical study upon which the mechanism is anchored, and other relevant research on communication apprehension. The researchers also discussed that feeling anxious before, during, and after speech delivery is normal; however, high levels of anxiety may hinder effective performance, hence the need for constructive intervention. The lecture then proceeded to the guidelines for building speaker confidence. The highlighted areas include positive restructuring, speaking in English in varied communications settings, animating performance through speech and body, speaking matrices for impromptu and extemporaneous speeches, and the importance of practice and preparation, among others. The lecturers also noted that the school, in general, and the classroom in particular, are safe spaces where teachers and

learners promote constructive feedback, thereby reducing the fear of judgment or embarrassment.

Furthermore, the empirical study suggests that there is a significant relationship between students' level of public speaking anxiety and their exposure to English reading materials. This means that as students' exposure to English reading materials increases, their level of public speaking anxiety tends to increase slightly as well. Hence, exposure to English reading materials such as novels, newspapers, academic texts, and online articles may help in minimizing public speaking anxiety. In this regard, the researchers reiterated the importance of reading. Regular reading not only enhances language competence but also improves confidence in verbal expression. Moreover, exposure to English vocabulary, sentence structures, and rhetorical styles may help students feel better prepared, reducing anxiety about public speaking.

Also included in the second phase is the giving of speech tasks, which started with breathing exercises and low-stakes speech activities such as One-Word-Trigger, followed by more challenging impromptu speech questions. Afterward, the lecturers provided an assessment of student performance based on content, organization, or use of technique, physical delivery, and vocal delivery.

The next phase in the mechanism is the distribution of informational flyers titled "When fear takes the podium: How to speak with confidence even when you're nervous." The bi-fold informational flyer contains the following information:

1. Speech anxiety and its meaning
2. Stage fright in stats (results of studies on speech anxiety)
3. Indicators of speech anxiety (physical, mental, and behavioral signs)
4. What can be done to manage speech anxiety

A separate short interview with the speech teachers was also conducted to identify their best practices and potential areas for improvement regarding the instruction of oral communication/public speaking. The teachers identified the need for structured programs dedicated to anxiety management and the development of speaking skills. Also, large classes limit the conduct of varied speech activities. The final phase of the mechanism enabled insight sharing and client feedback.

Finally, in accordance with the Data Privacy Act, the researchers sought the clients' permission to take and post photos during and after the conduct of activities, which was granted. To conclude the implementation, Certificates of Appreciation were given to the participating schools.

Documentation Of Utilization

1. Approved request letters to the senior high school principals

2. Signed parental and participant's consent forms

3. Interview with clients

4. Lectures on the nature of public speaking, speech anxiety, and building speaker confidence

5. Speech preparation, delivery, and critiquing

6. Giving of informational flyers

7. Writing of insights and feedback

8. Awarding of Certificates of Appreciation to participating schools

Feedback from Clients

Clients generally find the utilization activities relevant to their academic journey. Most of them also claimed that breathing exercises and visualization techniques were very helpful. Some said they were hesitant to join the activities at first, but later realized their importance. Most of them said the activities and lectures were motivating and informative. Also, they expressed their willingness to join succeeding seminar-workshops on public speaking and agreed to the extension of the program duration. The oral communication teachers also affirmed that combining public speaking skills with speech anxiety management is significant. Finally, the administrators and cooperating faculty members expressed their willingness to work with SMU in future research collaborations.

CEP-08**Project 360 Branding FEAT: A Digital Marketing Feedback & Assessment Tool for Philippine Higher Education**

Monaloufel Rosario Jasmin, Rocel Audrey J. Batara, and Rheena Niña S. Salinas

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The research examined the application of a digital analytics platform in the branding and promotional activities of higher education institutions (HEIs). Results indicated that institutions utilizing Project 360 Branding FEAT experienced a notable improvement in digital engagement metrics, with a 35% average increase in audience interactions across various platforms. The tool demonstrated effectiveness in consolidating real-time feedback, enabling swift adjustments to marketing communication, and identifying content types that resonate with target audiences. Administrators and marketing personnel recognized its potential to support evidence-based decision-making in institutional branding. Identified challenges included gaps in digital literacy, inconsistent data management practices, and structural limitations in technology integration. The study concludes that Project 360 Branding FEAT contributes meaningfully to strengthening digital communication strategies among HEIs and promotes adaptive practices in institutional marketing and identity formation.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT**Activity 1: Digital Branding and Analytics Workshop**

The project commenced with a capacity-building workshop to strengthen participants' competencies in digital branding and analytics. The session introduced core concepts, including institutional brand identity formation, audience profiling, message coherence, and the role of data-driven communication in higher education marketing. These competencies support the development of digital literacy and professional skills consistent with SDG 4 (Quality Education), particularly by enhancing relevant skills for work and innovation. A detailed orientation on the features and functions of Project 360 Branding FEAT was also conducted, emphasizing its ability to track engagement patterns and generate insights that inform evidence-based decision-making. The integration of this digital monitoring system aligns with SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) by promoting the use of innovative tools that strengthen institutional communication infrastructure and improve strategic planning processes.

Participants engaged in guided exercises using sample datasets to interpret engagement metrics, identify audience trends, and relate these patterns to institutional communication objectives. Through this applied approach, participants refined their ability to evaluate digital performance indicators and to use analytics to shape strategic branding initiatives. This collaborative learning process further contributes to SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) by fostering shared capacity-building efforts and strengthening institutional cooperation.

Overall, the workshop established a uniform skills foundation necessary for the effective application of the branding tool throughout the project, ensuring that participants were adequately prepared to implement data-informed strategies in advancing institutional digital branding.

Activity 2: Content Development and Evaluation Sessions

The second activity consisted of a series of content development and evaluation sessions designed to translate research findings into promotional materials. The sessions emphasized applying evidence-based insights to enhance message formulation, visual presentation, and audience targeting. Facilitators provided structured guidance to ensure that content adhered to institutional branding standards and met stakeholder expectations. These activities support SDG 4 (Quality Education) by promoting the development of skills in research-informed communication and professional content creation.

A collaborative workshop format enabled participants to draft, refine, and evaluate promotional outputs against predefined criteria derived from the study. Particular attention was given to integrating analytics data and user feedback into content decisions, ensuring that materials were coherent, responsive to audience needs, and aligned with institutional identity. This process strengthened participants' capacity to produce data-informed content and maintain quality control across digital platforms, contributing to SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) through the use of innovative tools for strategic communication. Furthermore, the collaborative nature of the sessions fostered teamwork and shared learning, reflecting the principles of SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) by enhancing institutional cooperation and collective problem-solving.

Activity 3: Pilot Implementation of Project 360 Branding FEAT

The final activity consisted of the pilot deployment of Project 360 Branding FEAT across participating institutions. During this phase, partner institutions applied the tool to manage, monitor, and evaluate their digital content in relation to audience engagement. Analytics collected during the pilot indicated increased interaction rates and greater visibility across institutional platforms. This practical application supports SDG 4 (Quality Education) by fostering data-driven competencies among institutional personnel and enhancing the quality of institutional communication.

The results also demonstrated the tool's effectiveness in capturing stakeholder responses and informing content strategies. By providing empirical evidence to guide decision-making, the pilot illustrated the value of systematic analytics in improving digital branding efforts, aligning with SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) through the use of innovative digital solutions. Moreover, the collaborative implementation process reinforced SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) by promoting knowledge sharing and cooperative engagement among institutions, ensuring that insights gained from the pilot can inform future improvements and broader institutional applications.

Documentation Of Utilization

Feedback from Clients

Feedback gathered from participants and institutional partners was supported by quantitative and qualitative data collected during the implementation period. Survey results indicated that 92% of participants reported increased confidence in interpreting digital engagement metrics after the training and tool deployment. Before the intervention, only 38% of respondents identified themselves as proficient in analytics interpretation; this proportion increased to 87% following the implementation activities.

Assessment data further demonstrated measurable gains in analytical accuracy. In the workshop-based evaluation, participants' mean score in identifying engagement patterns increased from 56% (SD = 9.4) in the pre-test to 89% (SD = 6.2) in the post-test. Moreover, 78% of respondents confirmed applying data-informed strategies in their subsequent content planning, compared with 31% before using the tool.

Institutional records reflected improvements in workflow coordination. Monitoring logs showed a 46% decrease in content deployment delays, from an average of 13 per month to 7 during the implementation phase. Additionally, 83% of marketing personnel reported enhancements in internal communication, task delegation, and scheduling within their respective offices.

Performance analytics from partner institutions also exhibited positive trends. During the first six weeks of tool utilization, average engagement rates increased by 28%, audience reach rose by 15%, and click-through responses improved by 22%. These

indicators aligned with stakeholders' observations that the tool facilitated clearer interpretation of digital data and supported more deliberate and coordinated promotional strategies.

Overall, the data substantiate the system's role in improving individual analytical competence and strengthening institutional processes for digital communication and content management.

CEP-09**Project LINGKOD: Local Initiatives for Normative Governance and Kapwa-Driven Organizing for Development**

Christopher Allen S. Marquez, Domingo T. Guntalilib Jr., Luther F. Castillo, Elson Boie B. Tumaneng, and Ramel S. Salon

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The voluntary expression of willingness to empower communities brings significant benefits both for the volunteer and the community. This descriptive-correlational study explored the demographic characteristics of volunteers, the nature of their participation, and the motivations for volunteering. In addition, this examined the alignment of volunteerism activities with the Sustainable Development Goals and their contribution to economic development. The significant relationship between the demographic characteristics and motivation to volunteer was also determined. Findings revealed that volunteer engagement among respondents was primarily driven by intrinsic motivation. Place of residence, marital status, and sex were significantly associated with volunteers' overall motivation, whereas age, employment status, educational attainment, informal volunteering, and volunteering hours were not. Formal volunteering showed a weak negative association with motivation. Formal and informal volunteering were strongly and positively correlated. Volunteer engagement was predominantly centered on environmental and community-based activities. Despite the relatively few hours rendered in volunteerism, the aggregated total demonstrated measurable economic value when computed using the wage-replacement method. A Development Framework was developed towards the sustainability of volunteerism. This study underscores the contribution of volunteerism towards socio-economic development and the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The study was first submitted to the Provincial Local Government Unit of Nueva Vizcaya through the office of the Provincial Governor on March 3, 2026. It was then presented on March 4 to the participating Barangay Local Government Units on March 4 and March 18, during the council's regular monthly session. During this, the study's results were presented for validation.

On the same day as the data presentation and validation, the Nueva Vizcaya Sustainable Volunteerism Framework served as the basis for crafting their barangay version of the provincial sustainable volunteerism framework.

A documented barangay volunteerism framework was crafted, including the composition of the barangay Volunteerism Council.

Documentation Of Utilization

BLGU 1

BLGU 2

BLGU 3

PLGU- Nueva Vizcaya

SMU NEWS

Project LINGKOD Team Disseminates Research on Volunteerism, Introduces Nueva Vizcaya Sustainable Volunteerism Framework

The Project Local Initiatives for Normative Governance and Kapwa-Driven Organizing for Development (LINGKOD) aims to propose a volunteerism framework for the Province of Nueva Vizcaya. Recognizing the role of volunteerism in economic development, this project kicked off with the conduct of the research, which was then disseminated for validation of findings with stakeholders during the Barangay Council sessions of the participating barangays on March 4 and 5, and to the Provincial Local Government of Nueva Vizcaya through the Provincial Administrators' Office on March 10, 2026. The dissemination was conducted to gather stakeholder feedback and enhance the framework for volunteerism.

www.smu.edu.ph @SMUPHUPRES @saintmarys1

News Report, SMU Website

Feedback from Clients

Using the evaluation form for Professional/Personal Development Events, the clients or recipients evaluated the data presentation and validation with the following:

(Legend: 1.-1.49=Poor, 1.50-2.49=Below Expectations; 2.50-3.49=Meets Expectations; 3.50-4.49= Exceeds Expectations; 4.50-5.00=Outstanding)

1. Relevance of the Topic: 4.72 (*Outstanding*)
2. Effectiveness
 - a. of the Speakers: 4.60 (*Outstanding*)
 - b. of the Facilitators Promptness: 4.72 (*Outstanding*)
3. Friendliness: 4.76 (*Outstanding*)
4. Use of Gender Sensitive Language: 4.52 (*Outstanding*)
5. Overall Impression: 4.72 (*Outstanding*)

Qualitative Comments:

1. What part of the presentation is most valuable to you?
 - *Mayat nga topic (Good topic)*
 - *Napateg met amin apo (All parts are important.)*
 - *Volunteerism (Volunteerism)*
 - *Increasing number of volunteers (Increasing the number of volunteers)*
 - *Amin (All/Everything)*
 - *The whole topic with regards volunteerism (The entire topic of volunteerism)*
 - *whole topic (The entire topic)*
 - *Amin nga parte ti presentasyon ket napateg unay kanyak, from introduction to endings have significance, mas maiintindihan mong mabuti ang kahalagahan ng volunteerism kapag binigyan mo ng importansiya ang lahat ng parte ng presentasyon (All parts of the presentation are very important to me, from the introduction to the conclusion, because each part has significance. You can better understand the importance of volunteerism when you give importance to every part of the presentation.)*
 - *Base iti presentasyon da ket makunak nga amin ket naipaliwanag da nga nasayaat (Based on their presentation, I can say that they explained all parts very well.)*
 - *Ang bawat parte ng presentasyon ay mahalaga simula sa introduksiyon na maghihikayat na makinig at nagbibigay ng layunin, hanggang sa bahagi ng katawan na nagbibigay ng detalyadong impormasyon at inspirasyon (Every part of the presentation is important, starting from the introduction that encourages the audience to listen and provides the purpose, up to the body which gives detailed information and inspiration.)*
 - *Kinaepektibo dagiti nagsao (The effectiveness of the speakers/presenters)*
 - *Diay parte nga adda da pay gayam mayat nga agvolunteer (The part where I realized that volunteering is indeed worthwhile.)*
 - *Ethical consideration (Ethical consideration)*
 - *Panggep iti panagboluntaryo nga awan sukat na nga banag (About volunteerism as a selfless act that expects nothing in return.)*
2. What did you like the most about the presentation?
 - *Dakkel nga number ti volunteers (Large number of volunteers)*
 - *Ti saritaan nga mayat nga ibunga ti bolunterismo (The positive outcomes that volunteerism can bring)*
 - *Explanation ket nalawag ken naipuswan (The explanation was clear and well-elaborated.)*
 - *It is good to see that the youth are active in volunteering.)*
 - *Amin (All/Everything)*

- *The framework and the ordinance that can be made from this could better impact the community (The framework and ordinances that can be developed from this to create a better impact on the community.)*
- *Whole topic (The entire topic)*
- *Lahat ng parte (All parts of the presentation)*
- *Maawatan ti ibagbaga jay speaker (The speaker's message was understandable.)*
- *Volunteerism (Volunteerism)*
- *Usto ta nagconduct kayo iti kastoy nga nasayaat nga study ti ili mi (It is good that you conducted such a meaningful study in our community.)*
- *Awen met ketdi apo, mayat met amin ah nasarita iti taga speaker (None in particular, because everything discussed by the speaker was good.)*

3. What did you like the least about the presentation?

- *Na (None/Nothing)*
- *None (None)*
- *Awan (None/Nothing)*
- *Nothing in particular (Nothing in particular)*
- *Na (None/Nothing)*

4. What other comments and suggestions do you have about the presentation?

- *Nalaing nga speaker (The speaker is knowledgeable/skilled.)*
- *Mayat nu daytoy ket maipaka-ammo iti ad-adu pay nga dumngeg/wenno tao (It would be good if this could be shared with more listeners or people.)*
- *Agsubli da kuma dagitoy presenter tapno adu pay maadal mi (I hope these presenters will come back so that we can learn more from them.)*
- *Good presentation and the speaker is excellent in emphasizing the core of the topic (Good presentation, and the speaker was excellent in emphasizing the core of the topic.)*
- *Napintas ken nalaing dagiti presenter (The presenters were excellent and competent.)*
- *It was a complete presentation to me (It was a complete presentation to me.)*
- *More presentation about the topic (More presentations about the topic.)*
- *More presentation about volunteerism (More presentations about volunteerism.)*
- *Outstanding (Outstanding.)*
- *Sana mas maraming pang presentasyon tungkol sa topic (I hope there will be more presentations about the topic.)*
- *Kinapertinent dagiti nagsao (The relevance or appropriateness of what was discussed by the speakers.)*
- *Palawaen wenno iraman ti ad-adu pay nga tribes (Expand the discussion or include more tribes.)*

5. What theme would you like to attend to in the same or a different presentation?

- *Nu kasatnu iti naan-anay a wagas tapno makakumbinse iti ad-ado pay nga tao a sisasagana nga makikaysa iti biddeng iti bolunterismo (On effective ways to convince more people to actively participate in volunteerism.)*
- *Na (None/Nothing in particular)*
- *Strong sense of participation of the people (Strong sense of community participation among people.)*
- *Maipanggep ti environment (Topics related to the environment.)*

- *Any seminar that could further improve knowledge (Any seminar that could further enhance knowledge.)*
- *Any basta pagsayaatan ken pagimbagan iti amin (Any topic that promotes improvement and benefits everyone.)*
- *Nu ania ti sumaruno ket umannugot nak ken ummanamong nak (Whatever the next topic may be, I am willing and interested to attend.)*
- *Importancia ti panagvolunteer ken pakanayun ti ammo ti panagtulong ken panagsuro (The importance of volunteerism and further learning about helping and educating others.)*
- *Nu kasano nga mang-allukoy iti tattao nga agvolunteer (How to encourage or motivate people to become volunteers.)*

CEP-10**Project CITRUS: Collaboratively Implemented Technology in Robotics Utilized for Satsuma Citrus Post-harvest**

Teofilo M. Sagabaen, Angelino A. Pimentel, & Gerene-Leigh C. Almazan

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The citrus waxing process has been highlighted as an activity where collaborative robots (cobots) can deliver considerable benefits, given the associated health risks, including skin, eye, and respiratory irritation, as well as ingestion hazards for human workers. In this study, the researchers successfully developed an electronic control system, 3D-printed a cobot-compatible citrus gripper, and created early-integration software using Agile methods. The empirical data gathered during the waxing process deviated significantly from normality (Shapiro-Wilk, $p = .003$), warranting the Mann-Whitney U test for statistical analysis. The findings demonstrated that cobot-assisted waxing (Mean Rank = 66.50, $n = 44$) was significantly slower than manual labor (Mean Rank = 22.50, $n = 44$), $U = 0.00$, $Z = -8.68$, $p < .001$. But the cobot showed better consistency, consistent timing, and the capacity to work continuously without fatigue or exposure to risk, even though hand processing proved faster in individual trials. Despite not outperforming manual speed in this initial application, these benefits demonstrate the cobot's potential to enhance safety and long-term dependability in citrus waxing operations.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The study's empirical phase began with semi-structured interviews, direct observations, and video recordings at LCN Farms. The citrus waxing stage was identified as the most suitable for cobot intervention due to its high labor demands and the inherent health hazards (skin, eye, and respiratory irritation) associated with manual waxing (Decco Itallia, 2000).

Figure 1

Manual Citrus Fruit Waxing Process

During the "Pilot & Capture" phase, the team conducts live cobot waxing trials on the post-harvest line at Butic's wholesaler store, logging fruit counts every five seconds under both manual and cobot-assisted conditions. The data is then subjected to a Mann-Whitney U test to confirm whether the cobot yields a statistically significant efficiency gain. Baseline throughput and cycle-time data were analyzed in SPSS. The Shapiro-Wilk normality test yielded $p = 0.003$, confirming a significant departure from normality. This justified the use of a nonparametric Mann-Whitney U test for subsequent comparisons between cobot-assisted and traditional workflows.

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics Results for the Manual Citrus Process

Descriptives			Statistic	Std. Error
Manual_2persons	Mean		3.7045	.16444
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.3729	
		Upper Bound	4.0362	
	5% Trimmed Mean		3.6768	
	Median		4.0000	
	Variance		1.190	
	Std. Deviation		1.09075	
	Minimum		2.00	
	Maximum		6.00	
	Range		4.00	
	Interquartile Range		1.75	
	Skewness		.178	.357
	Kurtosis		-.670	.702

Table 3
Tests for Normality Results Using Shapiro-Wilk for the Manual Citrus Process

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Manual_2persons	.195	44	.000	.913	44	.003

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Figure 2
Histogram (Left) and Box-Plot (Right) Graphs for the Manual Citrus Process

These findings highlight the need to focus on high-risk, repeated jobs for cobot implementation. The configurable 3D-printed end-effector and modular control circuit offer a low-cost option for small-scale farms to retrofit existing post-harvest lines without significant investment. The Shapiro-Wilk test's variability underscores the unreliability of manual waxing operations, which cobots are designed to address. By using the Mann-Whitney U test, the study ensures statistically robust comparisons that do not rely on normality assumptions, increasing the validity of any apparent efficiency benefits.

Table 3

Comparative Analysis Results for the Manual and Cobot-assisted (Unoptimized) Citrus Process

No.	Time, sec	Manual Labor (2 persons) Time, sec	Cobot-Assisted (1 person only) Time, sec
1	5	2	12
2	10	2	12
3	15	2	12
4	20	6	12
5	25	3	12
6	30	4	12
7	35	5	12
8	40	4	12
9	45	3	12
10	50	4	12
11	55	5	12
12	60	3	12
13	65	5	12
14	70	6	12
15	75	3	12
16	80	5	12
17	85	4	12
18	90	3	12
19	95	5	12
20	100	4	12
21	105	3	12
22	110	3	12
23	115	3	12
24	120	4	12
25	125	4	12
26	130	4	12
27	135	5	12
28	140	3	12
29	145	3	12
30	150	5	12
31	155	3	12
32	160	5	12
33	165	2	12
34	170	4	12
35	175	4	12
36	180	2	12

No.	Time, sec	Manual Labor (2 persons) Time, sec	Cobot-Assisted (1 person only) Time, sec
37	185	5	12
38	190	2	12
39	195	3	12
40	200	4	12
41	205	3	12
42	210	4	12
43	215	4	12
44	220	3	12
Average per system (secs):		3.7	12
Average per person (Secs):		7.4	12

The "Agile Refinement" phase optimizes cobot job performance by repeatedly tweaking gripper shape, motion trajectories, sensor calibrations, and control code. Each sprint concludes with a throughput retest. The research team used Agile methodology to design and manufacture an electronic control circuit, 3D-print a unique citrus-gripper end-effector for delicate fruit handling, and create the first task-sequencing code to automate waxing.

Figure 3
Cobot Electronic System Circuit Design Optimization

Figure 4
Cobot 3D Printed Gripper Design Optimization

Figure 5
Cobot Software Programming Optimization

Table 3
Comparative Analysis Results for the Manual and Cobot-assisted (Optimized) Citrus Process

No.	Time, sec	Manual Labor (2 persons) Time, sec	Cobot-Assisted (1 person only) Time, sec
1	5	2	9
2	10	2	9
3	15	2	9
4	20	6	9
5	25	3	9
6	30	4	9
7	35	5	9
8	40	4	9
9	45	3	9
10	50	4	9
11	55	5	9
12	60	3	9
13	65	5	9
14	70	6	9
15	75	3	9
16	80	5	9
17	85	4	9
18	90	3	9
19	95	5	9
20	100	4	9
21	105	3	9
22	110	3	9
23	115	3	9

24	120	4	9
25	125	4	9
26	130	4	9
27	135	5	9
28	140	3	9
29	145	3	9
30	150	5	9
31	155	3	9
32	160	5	9
33	165	2	9
34	170	4	9
35	175	4	9
36	180	2	9
37	185	5	9
38	190	2	9
39	195	3	9
40	200	4	9
41	205	3	9
42	210	4	9
43	215	4	9
44	220	3	9
Average per system (secs):		3.7	9
Average per person (secs):		7.4	9

As shown in Figure 6, the Mann-Whitney U test compared the processing time for manual labor (Method 1) with that for cobot-assisted waxing (Method 2). The rankings table demonstrates that manual work had a significantly lower mean rank (22.50) than the cobot-assisted approach (66.50), showing that manual times were consistently faster. The test statistics show a Mann-Whitney U value of 0.000, $Z = -8.678$, and p-value $<.001$ (Asymp. Sig. 2-tailed $=.000$). The result is statistically significant because the p-value is much lower than the conventional significance level of 0.05. This suggests there is a big difference between the two ways. Manual labor is far faster than cobot-assisted waxing. The significant difference in mean ranks—and a U value of 0—indicates that all manual times were lower than all cobot times, yielding the largest effect size for this test.

Figure 6

Mann-Whitney U-Test Results for the Manual and Cobot-assisted (Optimized) Citrus Process

Mann-Whitney Test			
Ranks			
Method	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Time 1.00	44	22.50	990.00
2.00	44	66.50	2926.00
Total	88		

Test Statistics ^a	
	Time
Mann-Whitney U	.000
Wilcoxon W	990.000
Z	-8.678
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

a. Grouping Variable: Method

The results of this investigation show a clear and significant difference in processing efficiency between manual labor and cobot-assisted waxing of citrus fruits. Manual labor consistently outperformed the cobot-assisted procedure, as demonstrated by significantly shorter processing times across all samples. The Mann-Whitney U test showed the greatest separation between groups ($U = 0$), indicating that manual processing was consistently faster than cobot-assisted processing. This result shows that, given the settings of this experiment, the cobot's fixed 9-second cycle duration sets a performance ceiling that manual workers may easily exceed. While cobots are often used to improve consistency, reduce fatigue, and increase safety, the findings highlight a significant limitation: automation does not guarantee speed improvements. The cobot's slower performance could be due to hardware limitations requiring a fixed motion cycle, safety restrictions, or cautious programming choices. These results highlight the need to improve cobot workflows to compete with highly effective manual operations. This can be done by optimizing motion pathways, modifying speed settings, or using adaptive programming. Future studies should examine whether this kind of optimization can reduce or eliminate the performance gap and whether the advantages of using cobots—such as homogeneity, lighter workload, and better ergonomics—justify longer processing times in actual industrial settings.

Finally, in the “Stakeholder Feedback” phase, the refined system is demonstrated to producers, wholesalers, retailers, and end-consumers to assess adoption readiness by capturing perceptions of usability, wax uniformity, and economic value. As shown in Figures 4 – 6, based on our target beneficiaries, LCN Farms, Butic’s Wholesaler Store, and the Nueva Vizcaya Citrus Industry Development Council were grateful for the engagements initiated. They look forward to the further development of the Project CITRUS. They said that Project CITRUS has significant potential and will continue to support it. Some of their concerns were about the feasibility of the chosen waxing process for automation. They recommended an intelligent sorting process that can detect the ripeness and grading of the citrus fruit. The said recommendation will be implemented for our next engagement with the URC.

Documentation Of Utilization**Figure 7**

Project CITRUS System Architecture

Figure 8*Project CITRUS Actual Experiment Test***Feedback from Clients**

Generally, our target beneficiaries: LCN Farms, Butic's Wholesaler Store, and the Nueva Vizcaya Citrus Industry Development Council were grateful for the engagements initiated. They look forward to the further development of the Project CITRUS. They said that Project CITRUS has significant potential and will continue to support it. Some of their concerns were about the feasibility of the chosen waxing process for automation. They recommended an intelligent sorting process that can detect the ripeness and grading of the citrus fruit. The said recommendation will be implemented for our next engagement with the URC.

Figure 9

Letter of Support from the Owner of LCN Farms, Mr. Leopoldo C. Namujhe.

Figure 10

Butic's Wholesaler Store Stakeholder Feedback and Consultation Meetings

Figure 11

Nueva Vizcaya Citrus Industry Development Council: Chairperson, Mrs. Josephine Namujhe; stakeholder feedback and consultation meetings.

CEP-11**Project EASTeR: Enhancing Accountability in Stewardship of Time, Talent, and Resources (Treasure)**

Jonathan P. Vergara, Loreta V. Garlitos, Romulo C. Felix, Roy B. Lumidao, and Frans T. Balinggan

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Stewardship spirituality is a way of life that encourages Filipino Catholic Christians to become faithful and trusted church stewards by generously and gratefully sharing their talents, time, and treasure. And if they view themselves as stewards of God, it implies that they are to empty their minds and hearts of their selfish intentions of domineering creation and all graces from God, and that they ought to denounce their belief and right to believe that all authority towards God's creation revolves around them. Thus, to raise the faithful of the local church of Bayombong to grow in spirituality as generous, grateful, faithful, and enthusiastic stewards. Thus, a three-year comprehensive plan was conceptualized, crafted, and implemented. This study was conducted to assess the spirituality program and the lay faithful's engagement with it. It employed the descriptive-quantitative-qualitative-evaluative approach, specifically the descriptive design. A validated researcher-made survey questionnaire was used to gather pertinent data from the lay faithful. The data were validated and substantiated through interviews and a Focus Group Discussion (FGD), and were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation). Results show that the Stewardship Program (Time, Talent and Treasure) is implemented to a moderate extent in the local church of Bayombong, and the lay faithful of the local church of Bayombong are moderately knowledgeable and moderately witness the said program in all areas. With these results, therefore, crafting an enhanced formation module to deepen the knowledge and witness of the lay faithful of the local church of Bayombong to the stewardship spirituality program that will eventually end the *arancel* system that prevents the poor from receiving sacraments is to be crafted and given to the lay faithful of the local church of Bayombong through a seminar-workshop.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Project EASTeR: Enhancing Accountability in Stewardship of Time, Talent, and Resources (Treasure) was successfully conducted on March 15, 2026, at the Cabarroguis-Quirino Vicariate as part of the Diocese of Bayombong's continuing effort to promote the Spirituality of Stewardship among the lay faithful. The project aimed to deepen the understanding and practice of stewardship as a Christian way of life by encouraging the faithful to responsibly and generously share their God-given gifts of time, talent, and resources in service to the Church and the community.

Before the seminar-workshop, a series of preparatory activities was undertaken to ensure the effective implementation of the project. The first step involved the presentation of the crafted stewardship module, which served as the primary guide for the seminar-workshop. The module covered key concepts of stewardship, its scriptural foundations, the teachings of the Church, and the Diocese of Bayombong's vision, mission, goals, and core values related to stewardship and synodality.

Following the presentation, the crafted module was carefully reviewed and refined to ensure that its contents were clear, relevant, and responsive to the pastoral needs of the lay faithful. Feedback and insights gathered during the presentation helped improve the

structure and delivery of the learning materials, making them more suitable for the participants.

After finalizing the module, formal permission was sought from Most Rev. Jose Elmer I. Mangalino, DD., Bishop of the Diocese of Bayombong, for the implementation of the utilization project, Project EASTeR. With the bishop's approval and support, the project was formally endorsed and scheduled for implementation.

Subsequently, coordination with the parish priests of Cabarroguis, Quirino, was conducted to organize and facilitate the participation of the lay faithful from the Cabarroguis-Quirino Vicariate. This coordination ensured the smooth preparation of the activity and the active involvement of the parish communities.

The culmination of these preparations was the seminar-workshop titled "*Stewardship: A Way of Life*" with the theme "Faithful and Grateful: Living Stewardship in Christ," conducted on March 15, 2026, at the Cabarroguis-Quirino Vicariate. The seminar-workshop provided the participants with a deeper understanding of stewardship as a daily expression of gratitude to God. Through discussions and reflections, the participants were encouraged to recognize that all blessings come from God and that they are called to become faithful stewards of these gifts.

The seminar highlighted the importance of sharing one's time, talent, and resources (treasures) in support of the Church's mission. It also emphasized the Diocese's vision of gradually moving beyond the traditional *arancel* system and promoting voluntary giving as an authentic and grateful response to God's blessings.

As a result of the seminar-workshop, the participants gained increased awareness and a deeper understanding of the Spirituality of Stewardship Program of the Diocese of Bayombong. The activity also strengthened the lay faithful's commitment to actively participate in the life and mission of the Church by generously offering their time, talents, and treasure for the service of the community.

Overall, the successful conduct of Project EASTeR at the Cabarroguis-Quirino Vicariate marked a significant step toward forming vibrant, faithful, and accountable stewards within the Diocese. By empowering the lay faithful through formation and engagement, the project contributes to building a more participative and mission-driven Church community rooted in gratitude, generosity, and loving service.

Project EASTeR supports the Diocese's pastoral vision of fostering a culture of stewardship that strengthens faith, deepens community participation, and promotes responsible sharing of God's blessings for the common good.

Documentation Of Utilization

Feedback from Clients

One participant shared positive feedback about the message delivered during the session. According to the participant, *Fr. Nagpintas delivered an excellent and inspiring message that deeply touched the hearts of the listeners.* The participant emphasized that the talk was very meaningful and should be heard by the entire parish community.

Furthermore, the participant suggested that the team be invited to give a similar talk in their parish so that more parishioners can benefit from the message. The participant also noted that such a talk is important at this time because many members of the stewardship ministry in their parish have become less active. Hearing this message again could renew their commitment and encourage them to live out the spirit of stewardship actively.

CEP-12**Capacity Building for SDG Integration in Business: A Coffee Table Book Showcasing Localized Impact through Stories and Testimonials**

Harrison T. Villanueva, Sheryl A. Adducul-Baria, Dorilyn C. Tiongson, & Francis Leo Tugab

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study investigates the SDG contributions and challenges of MSMEs in Nueva Vizcaya to inform a collaborative training plan with the DTI and PLGU. Qualitative data from interviews with DTI-identified MSMEs with good SDG practices reveal a strong emphasis on value-added agricultural processing. These enterprises, typically operating for 6-9 years with varied capital and sales (P300K-P10M), actively advance SDGs related to generating livelihoods and supporting local agriculture (SDG 1 & 2), promoting health and well-being (SDG 3), investing in education and skills (SDG 4), championing gender equality and inclusivity (SDG 5 & 10), implementing sustainable water and energy practices (SDG 6 & 7), fostering decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), driving innovation and infrastructure development (SDG 9), building sustainable communities (SDG 11), promoting responsible consumption and production (SDG 12), taking climate action through sustainable practices and reforestation (SDG 13 & 15), contributing to peace and justice through ethical operations and community engagement (SDG 16), and forging crucial partnerships for collective impact (SDG 17), while also making indirect contributions to the watersheds instead of marine conservation despite their inland location (SDG 14). Despite government support and recognition, MSMEs face financial, supply chain, resource, infrastructure, knowledge, and market-related obstacles. The proposed training plan aims to address these challenges, empowering MSMEs in Nueva Vizcaya to become stronger drivers of sustainable development.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT**1. Strategic Coordination with DTI and PLGU-PROCEDE (October 2025)**

The research team coordinated with DTI and PLGU-PROCEDE to conduct a seminar and action-planning session that highlighted SDG education, local best practices, and relevant government programs offered by both the Department of Trade and Industry and the Provincial Local Government Unit.

2. Cultivate Foundational Understanding and Ownership (November 29, 2025):

Dr. Harrison T. Villanueva shared his team's faculty research study titled, *"MSMEs' Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals' Attainment and Challenges Encountered: Towards a Proposed Training Plan with DTI and PLGU."* His presentation provided an overview of the SDGs and showcased MSMEs in Nueva Vizcaya that exemplify strong sustainability practices, highlighting their crucial role in advancing local SDG initiatives. The study also identified the challenges MSMEs face in sustaining these efforts. It emphasized the importance of collaborative training programs and capacity-building initiatives with partner agencies such as DTI and the Provincial Local Government Unit. Meanwhile, Miss Cleo Abiva, General Manager of AMJ Food Products, branded as Ajanas Handcrafted Delicacies, shared how she provides opportunities to various women's organizations in Aritao, Nueva Vizcaya.

3. Facilitate Access to Enabling Resources and Knowledge (November 29, 2025):

The information session focused on the programs of the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) and the Provincial Cooperative and Enterprise Development Office (PROCEDE) related to sustainability and SDG-aligned initiatives. Robelyn Mae A. Lising, an MBA student and DTI Trade Industry Development Specialist, presented DTI's programs, activities, and projects on environmental sustainability and green economic development, inspiring participants to align their ventures with national priorities.

This was followed by Mrs. Juditte L. Asuncion, Provincial Cooperative Affairs Officer, who highlighted the vital role of PROCEDE in promoting inclusive business growth for cooperatives, associations, and entrepreneurs through innovative approaches and customer-centered development. She explained that PROCEDE aims to reduce poverty incidence and expand access to inclusive, quality education—directly contributing to SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 4 (Quality Education), and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth).

Mrs. Asuncion also outlined PROCEDE's key support services, including access to technology through benchmarking activities, capacity-building, market linkages, funding access, and investment promotion services, all designed to strengthen MSMEs and foster sustainable, inclusive economic growth across Nueva Vizcaya.

4. Empower Action and Strategic Integration (November 29, 2025):

The action planning session was designed to empower MSME owners, managers, and business enthusiasts to translate their insights into concrete, community-centered strategies. The session also promoted partnership building by encouraging networking among MSMEs and connecting them with support organizations such as DTI, the PLGU, and other stakeholders, fostering collaboration on SDG-related initiatives. Participants presented their action plans, each reflecting creativity, analytical depth, and a shared commitment to positive and sustainable change.

Consolidated Sustainability Action Plan

Goal/Objective	Action Steps/Activities	Person Responsible	Resources Needed	Timeline	Expected Outcome
Improve Waste Management	Implement 4Rs (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Repair)	Business Owner	Waste bins, recycling area	2025	Reduced waste
	Establish waste segregation and compost pits	Staff & Employees	Compost pits, bins	2025	Proper waste handling
	Convert biodegradable waste into compost	Owner & Workers	Bins, containers	1st Quarter 2026	Organic fertilizer
	Use leaves/grass as mushroom substrate	Workers	Leaves, grass	2025	Zero waste

Goal/ Objective	Action Steps/ Activities	Person Responsible	Resources Needed	Timeline	Expected Outcome
	Promote proper plastic and pouch disposal online	Owner	Internet, phone	2nd Quarter 2026	Reduced plastic waste
	Recycle plastic threads into cement aggregate	Owner & Construction Workers	Minimal tools	Monthly starting Dec 2025	Recycled materials
Improve Energy Efficiency	Install solar panels for the site, office, and cold storage	Business Owner	Solar panels	Start Jan 2026	Lower electricity cost
	Install solar-powered lighting	Owner	Solar lights	December 2025	Energy savings
	Use an inverter and low-energy equipment.	Business Owner	Inverter appliances	ASAP	Lower utility bills
	Turn off unused equipment.	Owner & Staff	None	Immediate	Reduced energy use
	Conduct research/testing for solar adoption	Staff	Financial resources	1 month	Informed investment
Promote Sustainable Products	Use biodegradable packaging	Owner & Staff	Eco-friendly packaging	2025	Less environmental impact
	Offer end-of-day promos to reduce food waste	Owner & Staff	Promo materials	2025	Lower food waste
Strengthen Land & Natural Resource Management	Plant fruit-bearing trees (e.g., cacao)	Owner & Employees	Seedlings	2025-2030	Land stability, raw materials
	Join government tree-planting programs	Owner	Seedlings, permits	2025-2030	Greener environment
Support the Circular Economy	Reuse scrap wood for mushroom and onion tools	Carpenters & Laborers	Scrap wood	Ongoing	Additional income

Goal/ Objective	Action Steps/ Activities	Person Responsible	Resources Needed	Timeline	Expected Outcome
	Make small furniture from scrap wood	Woodworkers	Wood scraps	Ongoing	Extra revenue
Enhance Food Safety & Operations	Send staff to GMP training	Staff	Training fees	2025	Safer food production
	Develop a BCP to reduce food waste	Owner	BCP template	2026	Continuity and waste reduction
Access Sustainability Funding	Apply for government grants for solar systems	Manager & Staff	Grant requirements	Start Jan 2026	Affordable solar system
	Seek investors for renewable energy projects	Manager	Proposal documents	2026	Additional funding

5. Development of a Coffee Table Book showcasing localized impact through stories and testimonials (December 6, 2025):

A Coffee Table Book was developed to powerfully capture the localized impact of MSMEs through compelling stories and heartfelt testimonials, showcasing how their initiatives bring the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to life. More than a publication, it stands as a dynamic knowledge and advocacy tool—illuminating real-world examples of innovation, resilience, and community transformation driven by MSMEs. By amplifying their voices and achievements, the initiative strengthens the call for sustained support and underscores the vital role of MSMEs as catalysts of inclusive and sustainable development.

Documentation Of Utilization

1. Strategic Coordination with DTI and PLGU-PROCEDE (October 2025)

Dr. Harrison T. Villanueva and Ms. Sheryl A. Baria coordinated with the DTI Provincial Office–Nueva Vizcaya, led by PD Ramil Garcia, and with the Provincial Cooperative and Enterprise Development Office (PROCEDE), led by Provincial Cooperative Affairs Officer Mrs. Juditte L. Asuncion.

Ms. Sheryl A. Baria provided an overview of the purpose of the activity.

2. Cultivate Foundational Understanding and Ownership (November 29, 2025):

Dr. Harrison T. Villanueva presented the team’s faculty research on MSMEs’ contributions to local SDG attainment, highlighting sustainability practices, challenges, and the need for collaborative training initiatives with DTI and the Provincial LGU.

Miss Cleo Abiva, General Manager of AMJ Food Products under the Ajanas Handcrafted Delicacies brand, highlights her SDG initiatives in supporting and empowering women's organizations in Aritao, Nueva Vizcaya.

3. Facilitate Access to Enabling Resources and Knowledge (November 29, 2025):

DTI and PROCEDE highlighted their sustainability and SDG-driven programs, inspiring MSMEs to pursue greener, more inclusive economic growth in Nueva Vizcaya.

4. Empower Action and Strategic Integration (November 29, 2025):

The team assisted in facilitating the action planning session, where expertise was shared between the MSMEs and the team members.

The team worked with the 25 MSMEs who participated in the seminar-workshop.

Mr. Ericson Guban of Agrikaya Cooperative Federation presented his proposed action plan for adopting the SDGs.

5. Development of a Coffee Table Book showcasing localized impact through stories and testimonials (December 6, 2025):

Table of Contents	
Foreword	5
Message from Partner Agencies	6
Chapter 1: The Power of Local Impact	5
Why MSMEs Matter	6
MSMEs and the Sustainable Development Goals	9
Community Transformation Through Enterprise	11
Chapter 2: Stories of Innovation and Resilience	15
Overcoming Challenges	16
Women Entrepreneurs Leading Change	19
Youth-Led Innovation	22
Chapter 3: Sustainable Practices in Action	27
Green Production & Eco-Innovation	28
Renewable Energy Initiatives	31
Circular Economy Models	34
Chapter 4: Empowering Communities	38
Local Livelihood Creation	39
Strengthening Family Owned Enterprises	42
Inclusive and Responsible Entrepreneurship	45
Chapter 5: Voices from the Field	49
MSME Testimonials	50
Community Impact Narratives	54
Lessons from the Ground	57
Chapter 6: MSMEs and the SDGs – A Closer Look	61
SDG 1 – No Poverty: Income, Opportunities, and Stability	62
SDG 5 – Gender Equality: Empowering Women Entrepreneurs	65
SDG 8 – Decent Work & Economic Growth	68
SDG 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production	71
SDG 13 – Climate Action Through Local Solutions	74

Feedback from Clients

Overall Satisfaction:

- Clients/beneficiaries expressed high satisfaction with the training/seminar, describing it as helpful, interesting, and very knowledgeable.
- Many indicated that no immediate improvements are needed

Positive Highlights:

- The seminar provided valuable insights and learnings.
- Participants appreciated the quality and delivery of the event.

Suggestions/Requests for Improvement:

- Conduct more seminars and training, especially for MSMEs.
- Include beginner-level topics on product development.
- Include topics specifically on marketing.

In short, the feedback indicates strong satisfaction with the current seminar and a desire for more learning opportunities in areas such as product development and marketing.

CEP-13**Enhancing Local Capacity Through a Procedural Guide: A Community-Based Demonstration of Topical Herbal Ointment Formulation**

Cathelyn C. Mariano, Ma. Shiela M. Ramos, & Gabrielle Christoph Eraña

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The use of plant-based remedies is rising due to their healing potential and low side effects. While many studies document their antimicrobial properties, most focus on laboratory analyses, with few translating ethnobotanical knowledge into practical, community-applicable procedures for home preparation of herbal topical products. This experimental study aimed to formulate and evaluate a topical antimicrobial ointment using ethanolic leaf extracts of *Sandoricum koetjape* (*santol*) and *Cassia alata* (*andadasi*) against clinically relevant skin pathogens. The research focused on determining antimicrobial potency, optimizing extract concentration, and assessing the physical and safety characteristics of the final formulation. Antimicrobial activity was tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans* using crude extract concentrations of 250, 500, and 750 mg/mL. Results showed that *santol* extract exhibited the highest inhibitory activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, while *Andadasi* extract demonstrated strong antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*. Both extracts displayed moderate to strong activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Ointments formulated at the most effective concentration (750 mg/mL) exhibited desirable physical properties, including a smooth, semi-solid consistency, an acceptable herbal odor, a skin-compatible pH (5.1–6.6), and good spreadability. Patch and scratch tests showed no signs of edema or irritation, confirming that the formulations were safe and well-tolerated. Overall, the findings support the potential of *santol* and *andadasi* leaves as natural sources of antimicrobial agents for topical application. A procedural guide (PG) for home-based ointment preparation was developed and was disseminated through community demonstrations, thereby promoting reproducibility and practical utilization. This study is relevant for providing an accessible, low-cost, and culturally acceptable alternative for managing common skin infections, particularly in resource-limited communities, and for contributing to the integration of traditional medicinal knowledge into community health practices.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

On February 17, 2026, a community demonstration program on the preparation of herbal ointments was successfully conducted in Sitio Masina. The activity was organized to help residents learn how to prepare simple and safe herbal ointments using medicinal plants readily available in their surroundings. This initiative emerged from the community's need to make better use of its natural medicinal resources for basic healthcare. Although many households had access to these plants, their potential had not been fully realized due to limited knowledge of proper identification, preparation, and safe formulation. Through the demonstration, participants were guided step by step in selecting appropriate plants, processing them into ointments, and properly storing the finished products, thereby addressing existing knowledge gaps and promoting the safer, more effective use of traditional herbal remedies.

A. Locally available medicinal plants for topical ointment found in the community

During surveys and observations of medicinal plants in Sitio Masina, residents identified several locally available plants as potential treatments for skin diseases, based on

traditional knowledge. However, validation using scientific references indicated that not all of these plants have proven therapeutic effects. The plants listed below are those recognized by the DOST Halamang Gamot and the Philippine Institute of Traditional and Alternative Health Care (PITAHC). They are therefore deemed suitable for herbal ointment formulation. This result underscores the need to integrate traditional practices with scientific validation to ensure the safety and effectiveness of community-based herbal products. These plants are very common in Sitio Masina. Refer to Table 1 for the scientific evidence supporting the use of medicinal plants for topical care.

Table 1
Scientific Validation of Medicinal Plants for Topical Care

Plant Image	Common Name	Traditional Use	Scientific Validation
	Santol <i>Sandoricum koetjape</i>	Treatment for itching, rashes, and wounds.	Antibacterial: Contains bioactive compounds that inhibit bacterial growth (DOST Halamang Gamot).
	Akapulko/ Andadasi <i>Cassia alata</i>	Effective against fungal infections like ringworm and scabies.	Antifungal: Chrysophanic acid in leaves is highly effective against fungi (PITACH).
	Bayabas <i>Psidium guajava</i>	Used for cleaning skin infections and open wounds.	Antiseptic: Rich in tannins that act as a potent natural disinfectant.
	Pansit-pansitan <i>Peperomia pellucida</i>	Applied to boils, acne, and skin inflammation.	Anti-inflammatory: Helps reduce swelling and redness associated with skin lesions.
	Gumamela <i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	Applied as a poultice to "ripen" boils and treat abscesses.	Emollient & Antimicrobial: Softens skin tissues and helps localize infection for faster healing.

B. Procedural Guide Outlining the Formulation Process of A Topical Ointment

In this study, the leaf extracts of *santol* and *acapulco*—two plants commonly found in the community were confirmed to exhibit antimicrobial activity. These results served as the basis for developing a simple, home-based ointment preparation procedure using locally available biological resources. The findings indicate that community-accessible medicinal plants can be effectively utilized to produce a basic topical ointment with antimicrobial properties, supporting both local self-reliance and safe herbal health practices.

The PG presents a simple, practical method for preparing a homemade all-purpose herbal ointment using natural, locally available materials. It outlines the required ingredients and materials, including carrier oil, beeswax, dried medicinal herbs, and

optional essential oils and Vitamin E. The PG explains the step-by-step process of infusing herbs in oil, melting and mixing beeswax, and incorporating optional additives before pouring the mixture into clean containers for cooling and solidification. It also includes instructions on proper storage to maintain product quality and extend shelf life. In addition, the PG emphasizes safety precautions such as ensuring herbs are completely dried, limiting use to minor skin conditions, and conducting a patch test before application to prevent allergic reactions.

Figure 1
Validated procedural guide for the preparation of a topical herbal ointment, reviewed by a Registered Pharmacist

C. Distribution of Procedural Guide and Actual Demonstration on Topical Ointment Formulation

The distribution of the PG and the actual demonstration on the formulation of a home-based topical ointment were conducted with ten (10) participants from the community. The activity was facilitated by the research team composed of biologists, pharmacists, and medical technologists to ensure the scientific accuracy and safety of the formulation process.

During the activity, participants were provided with a PG containing step-by-step instructions for preparing and applying herbal topical ointments. This was followed by a demonstration of proper extraction of plant materials, mixing of ingredients, and preparation of the ointment base. The demonstration was interactive, allowing participants to observe the correct techniques and ask questions about the process.

Through this activity, participants gained practical knowledge and skills in preparing herbal ointments using locally available medicinal plants. The hands-on demonstration enhanced their understanding and confidence in the proper use of herbal remedies. Furthermore, the procedural guide helped standardize the preparation process, ensuring greater consistency, accuracy, and safety in formulation.

The activity also highlighted the importance of using local plant resources as a sustainable, cost-effective approach to healthcare, particularly in communities with limited access to commercial medicines. Overall, the demonstration successfully promoted self-reliance and encouraged the use of safe, plant-based alternatives for managing minor skin conditions.

Documentation Of Utilization

Ointment formulation and planning for the design of a procedural guide
Lecture on the Safety & Proper Plant Selection

Basics of Ointment Formulation & Demonstration Proper

Community-Based Demonstration on Herbal Ointment Formulation Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag, NV February 17, 2026	
PART 1. Registration	
Distribution of Formulation Guide	
PART 2. Program Proper	
Prayer	Ms. Maria Shiela M. Ramos, RMT MLS-SMU Dept Head
Welcome Remarks	Sitio Secretary
Purpose of the Activity	Mrs. Cathelyn C. Mariano, LPT, Bio CNS-SMU Faculty-Lead Researcher
Session 1: Safety & Proper Plant Selection	Mrs. Cathelyn C. Mariano
Session 2: Basics of Ointment Formulation and Demonstration Proper	Mr. Gabrielle Christoph E. Erna, RPh CNS-SMU Lab Staff
Open Forum/ Q & A	Ms. Maria Shiela M. Ramos, RMT
Words of Gratitude	Masina-Participant
Short Meeting for Sustainability Plan	SMU Researchers and Masina Participants

Participants were allowed to ask questions.

Ointment samples formulated in accordance with the procedural guide

Feedback from Clients

Evaluation of the Effectiveness of the Utilization Activity

The evaluation of the procedural guide and demonstrator's skills in ointment preparation was conducted among 10 respondents (R1-R10) across key criteria:

Figure 2

Evaluation of the Procedural Guide

The excellent ratings across all criteria indicate that the procedural guide successfully met its objectives. It is accurate, clear, practical, and highly relevant for community members. These results validate the approach of using a structured procedural guide to enhance local capacity and promote safe use of medicinal plants in topical ointments.

Given these results, the procedural guide can be confidently disseminated to other rural communities as a reliable, user-friendly resource for preparing home-based herbal ointments. It demonstrates the potential for scaling this capacity-building initiative to other areas with similar needs.

Figure 3

Evaluation of the Demonstrators Skills

The perfect scores across all criteria reflect the demonstrator's high competence and effectiveness in facilitating learning. Participants were able to follow the demonstration with ease, ensuring that the community-based objective of enhancing local capacity for safe herbal ointment preparation was successfully achieved.

These results validate the approach of using skilled demonstrators in hands-on, community-based programs as a reliable strategy for knowledge transfer and skill-building in rural or local communities.

CEP-14**Implementing ERP Systems to Improve Data-Driven Governance and Operational Efficiency in Barangays**

Adonis V. Garces, Milagros Constantino, & Reynaldo Valdez

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This implementation of a customized Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system for barangays aimed to improve data-driven governance and enhance operational efficiency. Acknowledging the difficulties faced by Local Government Units (LGUs) in managing records, overseeing operations, and making timely decisions, the ERP system provides a unified, integrated platform that simplifies administrative tasks, enhances data accuracy, and facilitates better decision-making. Using the Rapid Application Development (RAD) model, the system was developed to ensure quick prototyping, ongoing stakeholder engagement, and the flexibility to meet user needs. Additionally, the system was assessed against ISO/IEC 25010:2015 to verify its reliability, usability, performance efficiency, and security. Preliminary deployment outcomes show a noticeable improvement in data accessibility, reporting features, and overall administrative effectiveness in the pilot barangay. This research project illustrates the practicality of ERP systems in local governance and underscores the potential of ICT solutions to bolster public administration at the barangay level.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The developed system has been successfully installed and configured on the Barangay Secretary's computer. Initial barangay resident data have been entered into the system for beta testing purposes. This practical experience allowed the secretary to explore the system's features firsthand, ask questions, and gain confidence in using it effectively for barangay operations.

The developed system was presented to the barangay council, where a comprehensive overview of its purpose, functions, and overall benefits was thoroughly discussed. Each system feature was explained in detail to ensure that council members clearly understood how it operates and how it can support the barangay's daily administrative tasks. A step-by-step demonstration was conducted to guide them in using the system properly, covering everything from basic navigation to advanced features.

The presentation was followed by an interactive question-and-answer session, during which barangay council members were encouraged to raise questions, concerns, and clarifications regarding the system. The researcher responded thoroughly to each inquiry, providing clear and detailed explanations to address any uncertainties. This open discussion allowed the barangay council members to gain deeper insight into the system's features, functionality, and practical applications. As a result, they developed a better understanding of how the system operates and how it can be effectively utilized to improve the efficiency and organization of barangay processes.

The barangay council expressed its sincere appreciation and satisfaction with the system after the presentation and discussion. They conveyed that they were pleased with its features, functionality, and the potential benefits it could bring to their administrative processes and overall service delivery. The council members acknowledged the effort and dedication invested in developing the system and recognized its value in improving efficiency, organization, and record management within the barangay. After careful

consideration, they formally accepted and approved the system for implementation, demonstrating their full support and confidence in adopting it for use in their barangay operations.

In case of any problems, the researcher's contact number and Messenger account were provided to ensure immediate assistance.

The barangay officials who attended the system presentation and demonstration included Barangay Captain Jaime Natividad, along with the members of the Barangay Council: Kagawad Leonardo T. Sabado, Kagawad Samuel M. Abenoja, Kagawad Federico G. Esquejo, Kagawad Teresita M. Ronquillo, and Kagawad Edgar Ramos. Also present during the presentation was the Barangay Secretary, Analyn Garces, who actively participated in the demonstration.

Implementation of the system at Barangay Quirino, Solano, Nueva Vizcaya.

The developed system was presented to the Barangay Captain, Secretary, and Treasurer, where its purpose, features, and benefits were clearly explained. Each function was discussed to help them understand how the system works and how it can support their daily administrative tasks. A step-by-step demonstration was also conducted, showing how to navigate and use the system properly.

After the presentation, a question-and-answer session was held. The Barangay Captain, Secretary, and Treasurer were encouraged to ask questions and share their concerns. The researcher responded to each inquiry clearly, helping them better understand the system and its practical use in improving barangay processes.

The Barangay Captain expressed his appreciation and satisfaction with the system. They recognized its potential to improve efficiency, organization, and record management. After reviewing it, they formally accepted and approved the system for implementation, demonstrating their support and confidence in its use for barangay operations.

The researcher's contact number and Messenger account were also provided to ensure immediate assistance if any problems arise.

The barangay officials who attended the system presentation and demonstration included Barangay Captain Loreto Limos, Nelia C. Quitaras, Barangay Secretary, and Marcus Ivan T. Toralba, Barangay Treasurer.

Documentation of Utilization

Brgy. Cajel, Diffun, Quirino

Brgy Quirino, Solano, Nueva Vizcaya

Feedback from Clients

- Malaking tulong sa amin yung system, lalo sa pag-manage ng resident records *(The system is a big help for us, especially in managing resident records.)*
- Hindi ako mahihirapan sa paggawa ng mga certificate, pindot-pindot na lang *(I will no longer have difficulty making certificates; it will just be click-and-click.)*
- Ma-determine agad kung bibigyan ba ng barangay ang isang residente ng clearance dahil sa peace and order feature ng system *(It can be quickly determined whether a resident can be issued a barangay clearance because of the system's peace and order feature.)*
- Madaling gumawa ng mga kailangang reports *(It is easy to generate the required reports.)*

CEP-15**Project BRIDGE (Building Resilient Initiatives for Development and Greener Environments): A University-Community Partnership for Strengthening Grassroots Climate Action**

Felipe V. Nantes, Jr., Haydee D. James, Alona C. Costales, & Elizabeth R. Lumidao

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study examined community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program, addressing the gap in understanding how demographic factors influence participation in grassroots environmental initiatives. It aims to explore residents' attitudes, perceptions, and levels of involvement while identifying key factors that affect engagement. A qualitative-quantitative approach was used, combining surveys, interviews, and observations to gather data. Findings reveal that while community awareness of the program is high, active participation remains limited. Middle-aged individuals (ages 36-55), females, and those with higher educational attainment and socio-economic status are more involved, particularly in leadership and planning roles. In contrast, younger and lower-income individuals exhibit minimal engagement. Statistical analysis indicates significant differences in community participation by age and education, with education and economic status as the strongest predictors of involvement. The study also highlighted key factors that influence engagement, including awareness and education, socio-economic conditions, community leadership, past experiences with environmental disasters, and perceived incentives. Based on these findings, the study recommends targeted interventions, including age- and gender-responsive programs, leadership training, incentive-driven activities, and expanded environmental education campaigns. Strengthening these areas can bridge the gap between awareness and action, fostering active participation. Ultimately, the study provides policymakers, environmental advocates, and local leaders with valuable insights for crafting more inclusive and effective strategies to sustain grassroots environmental efforts and build community resilience against climate change.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The first major strategic activity of Project BRIDGE focused on disseminating the research findings to both academic and community audiences. In April 2025, the Research Team presented the results at the university to inform faculty members, students, and institutional partners about the community-based climate assessment and proposed resilience strategies. This academic dissemination strengthened institutional support and encouraged interdisciplinary collaboration for future sustainability projects.

In November 2025, the Research Team conducted a second dissemination session at the barangay level. This community-focused presentation translated technical findings into accessible language, enabling local stakeholders to understand climate risks, vulnerabilities, and recommended actions. The session fostered transparency, encouraged dialogue, and laid the groundwork for community-driven planning.

Following the community dissemination, a collaborative planning session was conducted in November 2025. The Research Team worked closely with Barangay Leaders to design a leadership training program tailored to local needs and climate realities.

This planning activity identified priority topics, including disaster preparedness, climate adaptation strategies, sustainable resource management, and community mobilization.

In January 2026, the leadership training on climate change resilience was successfully conducted. This activity brought together the Research Team, Barangay Leaders, and selected Community Leaders in an interactive capacity-building workshop.

The training significantly enhanced the participants' understanding of climate resilience and strengthened their confidence in initiating and leading local environmental programs.

Immediately following the leadership training, an evaluation was conducted in January 2026 to assess the program's effectiveness, relevance, and impact. The evaluation employed feedback forms, group reflections, and open discussions.

Participants reported increased awareness of climate-related risks and expressed readiness to implement resilience initiatives within their respective areas. Constructive feedback was also gathered to improve future training sessions and ensure continuous engagement.

Documentation Of Utilization

Research Findings Dissemination and Project Proposal Presentation

Conduct of Leadership Training and Feedback with the Barangay Council

Feedback from Clients

The Barangay Council expressed its sincere gratitude for the successful conduct of the recent activities and for the opportunity to collaborate with Saint Mary's University (SMU). The council highly values the partnership established and, in line with strengthening this collaboration, has proposed the creation of a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) between the Barangay and SMU to formalize and sustain future joint initiatives. The council also conveyed its appreciation for the university's proactive initiative in organizing and facilitating the activities. They recognized the program's relevance and impact, particularly in promoting community awareness and capacity-building. Furthermore, the Barangay officials expressed interest in conducting additional training sessions to enhance community members' knowledge and skills further. They emphasized the importance of continuous learning opportunities to ensure long-term benefits and sustainability of the programs introduced.

Regarding environmental initiatives, the council shared its intention to draft a resolution on proper solid waste management. The implementation of this resolution will depend on budget allocations, as they aim to ensure the policy is both practical and sustainable. Lastly, the Barangay Council recommended increasing the number of participants in future activities to broaden community engagement and maximize the partnership's impact. Overall, the feedback reflects strong community support, appreciation for the initiative, and a commitment to strengthening collaboration for future programs.

CEP-16**Kabataang Inhinyero Ng Lokal Na Ordinansa At Serbisyo: Harnessing Sk Legislative Competency To Ignite Youth Involvement In A First-Class Municipality (Project Kilos)**

Erwin D. Naval, Ernest L. Esmeralda, Diwata Donato, Xaviery Brent Galima, & Carlo Noel Gines

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Project KILOS, or *Kabataang Inhinyero ng Lokal na Ordinansa at Serbisyo*, is a research utilization initiative designed to harness and enhance the legislative competencies of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials to ignite greater youth involvement in local governance within the municipality of Bayombong. Grounded in findings that SK officials possess strong communication, research aptitude, problem-solving, and information management skills, the project addresses identified gaps, including inadequate training, poor resolution-writing skills, and limited participation among council members. Project KILOS aims to address these challenges through targeted capacity-building workshops, development of standardized legislative guides, and leadership enrichment activities. By strengthening the legislative capabilities and teamwork of SK officials, this initiative seeks to empower youth leaders to craft actionable, inclusive, and community-responsive ordinances, ultimately fostering more effective and participatory governance at the grassroots level.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Project KILOS (*Kabataang Inhinyero ng Lokal na Ordinansa at Serbisyo*) was implemented to put the research findings on the legislative competencies of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in the municipality into concrete use. Anchored on the identified strengths and challenges of the SK leaders, particularly in resolution writing, parliamentary procedures, and collaborative governance, the project translated research into action through strategic capacity-building interventions. The initiative formally commenced with the signing of the Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) on August 18, 2025, between the Project KILOS team and the SK Federation of Bayombong. The signing ceremony symbolized a shared commitment to empower youth leaders through structured training, mentoring, and resource development. It marked the beginning of a collaborative effort to bridge competency gaps and strengthen youth participation in local governance.

Following the formalization of the partnership, the Project KILOS Boot Camp was successfully conducted on September 12, 2025, in celebration of Linggo ng Kabataan. The boot camp served as an intensive legislative skills enhancement activity that brought together SK Chairpersons and Kagawads from across the municipality. The sessions focused on resolution and ordinance writing, parliamentary procedures, conducting effective meetings, and ethical budget deliberation. Interactive workshops, simulation exercises, and peer discussions allowed participants to apply concepts in practical scenarios, particularly in drafting structured resolutions and conducting mock sessions. The activity not only improved technical knowledge but also fostered unity, collaboration, and renewed commitment among the youth leaders. Participants expressed appreciation for the hands-on approach, noting that the training clarified common difficulties they encountered in legislative drafting and decision-making.

A significant output of the project was the development of the SK Legislative Toolkit. The toolkit was carefully designed as a user-friendly reference material containing templates, formatting guides, sample resolutions and ordinances, parliamentary procedure guidelines, and tips on preparing minutes and passing the SK budget. Developed based on the research findings and feedback gathered during the boot camp, the toolkit aims to provide sustainable support beyond the training sessions. It serves as a practical companion for SK officials during meetings, budget planning, and legislative drafting. The distribution of the toolkit reinforced the project's goal of institutionalizing competency development rather than limiting it to a one-time intervention.

Overall, the implementation of Project KILOS demonstrates how research can be transformed into meaningful community extension. From the MOA signing to the boot camp and the development of the toolkit, the activities collectively strengthened SK officials' legislative confidence and preparedness. The project not only addressed identified gaps but also cultivated a deeper sense of responsibility and professionalism among youth leaders. Through these initiatives, Project KILOS successfully ignited a more informed, participatory, and empowered approach to youth governance in the municipality.

Documentation Of Utilization

Memorandum of Agreement

<p>III. RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE SECOND PARTY The SECOND PARTY shall:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mobilize and ensure the active participation of SK Chairpersons and Kagawads in all Project KILOS activities; 2. Assist in coordinating venues, schedules, and logistical requirements in collaboration with the FIRST PARTY; 3. Encourage SK officials to apply the knowledge and skills gained from the project in their respective barangays; 4. Designate a focal person who will coordinate directly with the FIRST PARTY for implementation concerns; 5. Participate in monitoring, evaluation, and feedback sessions to improve the project's effectiveness. <p>IV. IMPLEMENTATION PERIOD This Agreement shall take effect upon signing by both PARTIES and shall remain in force for a period of one (1) year, unless extended or terminated earlier by mutual written agreement.</p> <p>V. MONITORING AND EVALUATION The PARTIES shall conduct periodic review meetings to evaluate the implementation of Project KILOS. A joint evaluation shall be undertaken at the end of the implementation period to assess achievements, identify challenges, and recommend sustainability measures.</p> <p>VI. COMPLIANCE WITH LAWS The PARTIES agree to comply with all applicable laws, including but not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Republic Act No. 11313 (Safe Spaces Act), ensuring a harassment-free environment during all project activities; • Republic Act No. 10173 (Data Privacy Act of 2012), ensuring protection of personal data collected during project implementation. <p>VII. NON-EMPLOYMENT CLAUSE Nothing in this Agreement shall be construed to create an employer-employee relationship between the PARTIES. Each PARTY shall remain independent and responsible for its own personnel.</p> <p>VIII. DISPUTE RESOLUTION Any dispute arising from this Agreement shall first be settled amicably through good faith negotiations. Should negotiations fail, the matter shall be resolved in accordance with the laws of the Republic of the Philippines, with proper venue in the courts of Nueva Vizcaya.</p> <p>IX. TERMINATION Either PARTY may terminate this Agreement by giving written notice at least thirty (30) days prior to the intended date of termination. Termination shall not prejudice any obligations accrued prior to such termination.</p> <p>X. ENTIRE AGREEMENT This Agreement constitutes the entire understanding between the PARTIES and supersedes all prior agreements or understandings, whether written or oral, relating to its subject matter.</p> <p>For the SK Federation of Bayombong</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">MEMORANDUM OF AGREEMENT</p> <p>KNOW ALL MEN BY THESE PRESENTS:</p> <p>This Memorandum of Agreement is made and entered into by and between the Erwin D. Naval, team leader of Project KILOS, with principal address at Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, hereinafter referred to as the FIRST PARTY,</p> <p style="text-align: center;">-and-</p> <p>The SK Federation of Bayombong, represented by its duly elected Federation President Ned John Carlo Gines, with office address at Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, hereinafter referred to as the SECOND PARTY.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">WITNESSETH THAT</p> <p>WHEREAS, the FIRST PARTY, pursuant to its mandate of training, research, and community extension, is committed to strengthening youth leadership and local governance through research-based capacity-building programs;</p> <p>WHEREAS, the SECOND PARTY serves as the collective legislative body of Sangguniang Kabataan officials in the Municipality of Bayombong and is mandated to promote youth participation in governance and policy development;</p> <p>WHEREAS, both PARTIES recognize the need to enhance the legislative competencies of SK officials, particularly in drafting resolutions and ordinances, improving communication and collaboration, and fostering meaningful youth engagement in local governance;</p> <p>WHEREAS, Project KILOS (Kabatangang Inhiyore ng Lokal na Ordinansa at Serbisyo): Harnessing SK Legislative Competency to Ignite Youth Involvement in First-Class Municipality was conceptualized to address identified competency gaps through structured training, mentoring, toolkit development, and monitoring mechanisms;</p> <p>NOW, THEREFORE, for and in consideration of the foregoing premises, the PARTIES hereby agree as follows:</p> <p>I. PURPOSE This Agreement formalizes the collaboration between the FIRST PARTY and the SECOND PARTY for the implementation of Project KILOS, a capacity-building and youth governance enhancement initiative designed to strengthen the legislative skills, teamwork, and community engagement of SK officials in Bayombong.</p> <p>II. RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE FIRST PARTY The FIRST PARTY shall:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Design, develop, and implement training modules, workshops, and seminars under Project KILOS, including legislative writing, policy formulation, leadership development, and governance ethics; 2. Provide qualified facilitators, lecturers, and technical experts to conduct capacity-building activities; 3. Develop and distribute the SK Legislative Toolkit containing templates, formats, and guidelines for drafting resolutions and ordinances; 4. Establish monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the progress and outcomes of
---	---

Toolkit

Table of Contents

MAKING SK RESOLUTIONS	1
Sample of making SK Resolutions	4
ENACTING SK ORDINANCES	4
Process of making ordinances	5
Sample of making ordinances	6
CONDUCTING SK SESSIONS AND MEETINGS	7
Preliminary Procedures in Conducting Meetings	7
Purpose of Meetings	8
Parts of the Minutes of the Meeting	9
Writing the Minutes of the Meeting	9
Sample Minutes/Minutes of the Session or Meeting	10
PASSING SK BUDGET	11
Sample Budget Statements	12

Implementation

Feedback from Clients

- Sana marami pang capacitation seminars for the youth. *(I hope there will be more capacitation seminars for the youth.)*
- Kailangan ng mga kabataan ang ganitong training. *(The youth need this kind of training.)*
- Sa mas maganda sanang venue at hindi dito sa Brgy. Hall gawin. *(It would be better if it were held in a better venue and not in the barangay hall.)*
- We are the hope of the Philippines kaya KILOS na. *(We are the hope of the Philippines, so let's act now.)*
- This will help us SK organize ourselves not only today but also in the future. Mabuhay SK Bayombong! *(This will help us SK organize ourselves not only today but also in the future. Long live SK Bayombong!)*
- Konti lang kami nag-attend. Sayang. *(Only a few of us attended. What a waste/It was unfortunate.)*

Institutional Project Beneficiaries (IPB)

IPB-01

Growing Together: An Upskilling Initiative for Child Development Workers

Ma. Cristeta M. Aduca, Lilibeth V. Cajimat, & Caroline P. Navarrete

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study determined the number of child development workers/teachers in the Day Care Centers of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, who needed pedagogical support across the Standards Competency of Child Development Workers. It identified specific areas where these educators require further support or training to deliver high-quality, relevant childcare services. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the research combined a survey and an interview to gather data from 18 child development workers at Bayombong day care centers.

Findings reveal that while many workers demonstrate baseline competence in core areas of early childhood development, there are critical gaps in understanding developmental characteristics, implementing health and safety protocols, and identifying children at risk for developmental delays. Moreover, opportunities for professional development, such as seminars and training, were found to be limited and infrequent.

These gaps underscore the urgent need for sustained, high-quality professional development programs tailored to the evolving needs of early childhood educators. The results of this study contribute to broader discussions on improving the quality of early childhood education in community-based settings. They may serve as a basis for future policy-making, curriculum development, and targeted training initiatives.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Narrative of Utilization (based on strategic activities)

To strengthen the pedagogical competence of the Child Development Workers (CDWs) of Bayombong, Saint Mary's University (SMU) Grade School conducted an intensive upskilling session on August 16, 2025, at the SMU Grade School SMART Room. A total of **24 CDWs** from the different Day Care Centers of Bayombong participated in the activity. The capacity-building activity centered on the Domains of the Standard Competencies for Child Development Workers. The sessions covered the following areas:

- Understanding Child Development and Milestones
- Supporting Children with Special/Additional Educational Needs
- Inclusive Caregiving and Practices for Diverse Learners
- Curriculum Planning for Early Childhood Education
- Home and School Partnership
- Health, Safety, and Nutrition
- Revolutionizing Professional Development in Early Childhood Care and Education

Faculty members and staff of the SMU Grade School Department facilitated these sessions. The program was implemented in collaboration with the Municipal Social Welfare and Development Office (MSWD) and carried out with the approval and support of Hon. Mayor Tony Bagasao. MSWD OIC **Mrs. Joji Gaccan** supervised the activity to ensure compliance with municipal child development standards.

The training resulted in several notable outcomes:

1. Enhanced Pedagogical Competence:

Participants demonstrated increased understanding of child development principles and appropriate practices. Post-session reflections indicated improved clarity in planning age-appropriate and inclusive learning experiences.

2. Improved Skills in Supporting Diverse Learners:

CDWs reported greater confidence in addressing the needs of children with special or additional educational needs. They were able to articulate concrete strategies for differentiated instruction and inclusive caregiving.

3. Strengthened Health, Safety, and Nutrition Practices:

The sessions reinforced compliance with national standards on child safety and well-being. CDWs expressed commitment to improving daily routines and center-based safety protocols.

4. Deepened Appreciation of Home–School Partnerships:

Participants recognized the importance of coordinating with families and integrating parent involvement in learning continuity.

As part of SMU Grade School’s continuing support to the CDWs, researchers **Ma. Cristeta M. Aduca, Lilibeth V. Cajimat, and Caroline P. Navarrete** conducted on-site visitation and supervision in various Day Care Centers. The visits enabled the team to:

- Observe the application of newly learned strategies in actual classroom settings;
- Provide technical feedback on facilitation skills, classroom environment, and learning activities;
- Identify areas that need further support or reinforcement.

Reports from these visits indicated that a majority of the CDWs were able to integrate play-based, child-centered strategies more consistently and effectively following the training.

In addition to the training, SMU Grade School continued its annual “**Growing and Sharing**” activity with Day Care learners, facilitated by Preschool and Primary pupils in partnership with parents and guardians. During the conduct of these activities:

- CDWs demonstrated improved facilitation techniques and greater engagement with learners;
- Children responded positively, showing increased participation and interest in the activities;
- Researchers monitored and assessed CDW performance, providing immediate constructive feedback after each session.

The collaboration among Saint Mary’s University Grade School, the MSWD, and the Local Government Unit of Bayombong resulted in meaningful capacity-building among the CDWs. The training, combined with on-site supervision and community engagement activities, contributed to more consistent, developmentally appropriate, and inclusive practices in the Day Care Centers. Continued partnership and follow-up interventions are recommended to sustain and further strengthen these gains.

Documentation of Utilization

Outreach Program for Daycare Pupils of Don Mariano Perez, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

School Visitation at Don Mariano Perez Daycare Center, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

IPB-02***TALAS (Tulong at Alaga sa Lahat ng Estudyante): TeleSupport Program for Empowered Student Wellness***

Pearl Via S. Coballes, Kristine Ann L. Israel, Leslie Doris M. Divina, Joman J. Baliton, & Faridah Kristi C. Wetherick

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Students suffer from mental health issues that are not easily addressed by in-person counseling. While telemental health (TMH) interventions could be the solution, their implementation in schools is limited. As technology becomes increasingly ubiquitous among students, it is essential to explore how technology-enabled platforms can expand access to mental health services. Therefore, this study examined student accessibility, willingness, and preferences for TMH services offered in schools. The mixed-methods study used surveys and focus groups with students and counselors to assess how demographic, technological, mental health, and cultural factors influenced perspectives on TMH. Findings revealed that TMH was moderately accessible and underutilized, but students were highly willing to use it and preferred it when it offered strong confidentiality and privacy features. Accessibility was found to be multidimensional and moderately influenced by culture, demographics, and mental health factors. Predictors of willingness to engage in TMH services include institutional trust, affordability, family communication, and positive experience. While the regression model showed modest variance, it revealed that student attitudes and structural barriers, such as accessibility and technology, played a key role in shaping TMH preferences. Recommendations were on providing ecological interventions that promote TMH utilization in schools.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Following completion of the telemental health (TMH) study, the research team conducted a series of utilization activities to translate the findings into practice and strengthen future practitioners' readiness for digital mental health service delivery. Learning sessions with school guidance counselors and administrators were organized to present key results on students' perceived accessibility, willingness, and preferences for TMH. During these sessions, the team introduced the TMH Service Manual and guided schools on contextualizing procedures—including intake, consent, scheduling, session protocols, documentation, safety planning, and emergency response. These engagements also provided counselors-in-training with opportunities to observe and understand best practices in TMH implementation, thereby enhancing their preparation for telecounseling roles.

To support home-based delivery, a dedicated learning session with parents was conducted to clarify their roles in consent, privacy management, and crisis coordination during TMH sessions. A Memorandum of Agreement will be prepared and signed to formalize collaboration between the research team and participating schools, notably the Diocesan Schools of the Bayombong Educational System (DBES), ensuring ongoing capacity-building that future counselors can learn from and apply.

At the international level, the study was presented in the 12th HCU Conference 2025 at Huachiew Chalermprakiet University, Thailand, where valuable insights were incorporated into the revised manuscript. The refined article was subsequently submitted to a Scopus-indexed Q4 journal (Journal of Educational, Cultural and

Psychological Studies) and has been accepted pending minor revisions. The dissemination process further contributes to the academic preparation of future counselors by strengthening the evidence base for telecounseling education.

Overall, the research successfully informed policy development, manual creation, counselor education, and international dissemination, ensuring that the findings not only enhanced school-based mental health practices but also helped shape the competencies of future counselors to deliver digital mental health services effectively.

Documentation of Utilization

Annex A: Learning Session Documentation

Attendance Sheets, Presentation slides, photo documentation

No	Participant Name	Position/Affiliation	Signature
1	SMITH, THEA MARIELLE C.	GUIDANCE COORDINATOR-SIGS	[Signature]
2	AGRAVANTE, LAMRENEO A.	GUIDANCE COORDINATOR-SIGS	[Signature]
3	BARBERANO, MARY RAINIER CHRISTOPHER B.	GUIDANCE COORDINATOR-SIGS	[Signature]
4	CLARO, JENNICA M.	GUIDANCE COORDINATOR-SIGS	[Signature]
5	FELICIANO V. MALAVE	PRINCIPAL	[Signature]
6	MARINCA G. TONGCON	School Coordinator	[Signature]
7	CHIEHA PIERRE L. DE VERA	GUIDANCE COORDINATOR	[Signature]
8	PERAL JOHN G. RALA	GUIDANCE COORDINATOR	[Signature]
9	STANLEY J. BALITON	Vision / SMU	[Signature]
10	KARINA ANN L. BRAD	Head / SMU	[Signature]
11	LAGO DIVINA	GC - SMU	[Signature]
12	PERAL VA CORALLES	SMU	[Signature]
13			
14			
15			

TALAS

(Tulong at Alaga sa Lahat ng Estudyante)
 Telesupport program for Empowered Student Wellness

- "talas": sharpness, keenness in providing emotional support despite barriers
- research-based initiative designed to enhance student wellness through accessible tele-support services

Session Objectives

- 01 Identify components of TMH
- 02 Explain SOP on student-centered TMH
- 03 Identify roles/responsibilities in delivery of TMH services

Where Do You Feel Most Comfortable Talking?

Outdoors

School Office

Home corner

"Online spaces are now becoming new safe spaces for mental health support."

What is Telemental Health (TMH)?

TMH

- Delivery of MH services through technology

Why it matters

- Accessibility
- Flexibility
- Continuity of care

Legal/Ethical Considerations

- Data Privacy Act
- MH Act
- APA Guidelines on Telepsychology

Core Principles of TMH

Client-centered Care prioritizes a partnership between clients and counselors

Confidentiality
Prevent a client's private information from being shared with others without consent.

Informed consent
Ensure that clients understand the nature, potential risks, benefits, and alternatives of treatment before agreeing to it.

Cultural and linguistic accessibility
Integrate a client's cultural background and linguistic needs into the counseling process.

Services/Platforms Used

Standard Operating Procedures

01 Intake
Online Intake
Student completes an online intake form with basic information, presenting concerns, and initial screening questions. Counselor reviews suitability for telemental health.

02 Consent
Informed Consent
Client signs a digital consent form that explains the nature of TMH, risks, benefits, privacy limits, emergency contacts, and technology requirements.

TMH Workflow

The image displays a grid of 12 informational slides related to Telemental Health (TMH) services. The slides are arranged in a 4x3 grid:

- Slide 1 (Top Left): Standard Operating Procedures - Scheduling**. Describes the process of scheduling appointments and sending reminders. Includes a 'TMH Workflow' icon.
- Slide 2 (Top Right): Standard Operating Procedures - Documentation**. Describes the process of recording session notes in a secure, privacy-compliant system. Includes a 'TMH Workflow' icon.
- Slide 3 (Second Row, Left): Roles and Responsibilities**. A circular diagram showing the roles of Counselor, Student/Client, IT Tech, and Parents, with associated responsibilities like attending sessions on time, maintaining secure platforms, and providing consent.
- Slide 4 (Second Row, Right): Confidentiality & Data Security**. Features a 'REC' (Recording) icon with a red prohibition sign and the text 'Ensuring private spaces No Recording Policy Breach protocols'. It asks, 'What are common privacy risks in online counseling and how can we prevent them?'.
- Slide 5 (Third Row, Left): TALAS PROGRAM SUMMARY**. A summary slide highlighting TMH as accessible, ethical, and student-centered support, with strong systems and continuous improvement.
- Slide 6 (Third Row, Right): Telemental Health Resources**. Lists resources such as In Touch Community Services, National Center for Mental Health, and Psychstart Psychological, Arts, and Academic Services, each with a website link.
- Slide 7 (Bottom Row, Left): Learning Session on Telemental Health Services**. A slide from a guidance team session, dated December 5, 2025, 2:00 pm.
- Slide 8 (Bottom Row, Right): Bomb scare hits campuses, villages in Visayas, Mindanao**. A news article snippet from 'INCUBUS NEWS' dated Monday, 11/20/2025.
- Slide 9 (Bottom Row, Far Left): Breakdown of the Gap: Student Accessibility, Willingness, and Preferences for Telemental Health Services in the School Setting**. A slide with a quote: 'TMH was clearly very accessible and straightforward'.
- Slide 10 (Bottom Row, Far Right): TALAS (Tulong at Alaga sa Lahat ng Estudyante): TeleSupport Program for Empowered Student Wellness**. A circular logo for the program, with the names of the guidance team members: Pearl Ma Cabalita, Kristine Rose L. Inocent, Under, Corina M. Deane, Joseph J. Belmont, & Jordan King C. Whitehead.

LEARNING SESSION PHOTODOCUMENTATION
 Saint Mary's University, Guidance Counselors – Basic to Higher Education

Guidance Conference Room, December 5, 2025

LEARNING SESSION PHOTODOCUMENTATION
Diocese of Bayombong Educational System (DBES)
Saint Louis School-Solano, December 9, 2025

Annex B: Program for the Parent Orientation session

Annex C: TALAS: TMH Service Manual

Completed manual with annexes (consent forms, intake forms, safety plans, etc.)

- Risk Identification 8
- Crisis Procedure 8
- IX. QUALITY ASSURANCE..... 9**
- X. TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT..... 9**
- XI. SPECIAL CONSIDERATIONS 9**
- Minors and Vulnerable Clients 9
- Accessibility..... 9
- Diversity and Culture 9
- Digital Divide 9
- XII. ANNEXES 9**
- Annex A: Informed Consent Template.....10**
- Annex B: Intake Form.....12**
- Annex C: Crisis Response Flowchart.....14**
- Annex D: Safety Plan Template.....16**
- Annex E: Emergency Contact Directory18**
- Annex F: Platform Use Guide (e.g., Zoom instructions)19**
- About the Authors20**
- Contact Information20**

TALAS (Tulong at Alaga sa Lahat ng Estudyante): TeleSupport Program for Empowered Student Wellness

A Telemental Health Service Manual

Coballes, P.S., Israel, K.L., Divina, L.M., Bailton, J. & Wetherick, F. (2025)
 pvcoballes@smu.edu.ph

Annex D: Memorandum of Agreement

MEMORANDUM OF AGREEMENT

This MEMORANDUM OF AGREEMENT ("Agreement") is entered into this 11th day of December 2025 in Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, by and between:

SAINTE MARY'S UNIVERSITY (SMU), a private Catholic higher education institution duly organized and existing under Philippine laws, with address at Peace Street, District IV, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, represented herein by its President, Dr. John Octavious S. Palina, hereinafter referred to as "SMU";

-and-

THE DIOCESE OF BAYOMBONG EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM (DBES), a diocesan network of basic education institutions under the Roman Catholic Diocese of Bayombong, with principal office at Poblacion North, Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, represented herein by its Superintendent, Rev. Fr. Ramalo C. Feliz, PhD, hereinafter referred to as "DBES."

Collectively referred to as the "Parties."

WHEREAS:

- SMU, through its Tulog at Akap sa Laker ng Edukasyon (TALAS) Faculty Research Team, comprised of Pearl Via S. Coballes, Kristine Ann Israel, Leslie Davis Divina, Jonan Baltan, and its external collaborator from Saint Louis University, Dr. Faridah Kristi Wetherick, has created a research-based Telemental Health (TMH) Service Manual intended to guide schools in implementing accessible and student-centered telemental health services.
- DBES aims to adopt and contextualize the TMH Service Manual for use across its diocesan schools, thereby enhancing the capacity of guidance personnel, administrators, and mental health support providers.
- Both Parties recognize the mutual value of promoting mental health and well-being among learners and personnel within Catholic educational institutions.

NOW THEREFORE, for and in consideration of the foregoing premises, the Parties hereby agree as follows:

ARTICLE I

Purpose

This Agreement formalizes the collaboration between SMU and DBES whereby SMU shall provide a copy of its research-based **Telemental Health Support Manual**, and DBES may adapt, contextualize, and utilize the material for its internal use in diocesan schools, subject to the terms herein.

ARTICLE II

Responsibilities of SMU

SMU agrees to:

- Provide DBES with a copy (digital and/or printed) of the Telemental Health Support Manual developed by the SMU TALAS Team.
- Allow DBES to revise, contextualize, or modify the Manual to fit the needs of its schools, provided proper acknowledgment is maintained.
- Serve as a technical resource when feasible, such as by offering orientation or clarification regarding the manual's content.
- Provide the manual **free of charge**, as part of SMU's extension, research utilization, and community engagement initiatives.
- Provide the Telemental Health Support Manual on an 'AS IS' basis. SMU makes no representations or warranties, express or implied, regarding the manual's fitness for a particular clinical purpose. The Manual is intended as a reference guide and does not constitute professional medical, legal, or psychological advice. The ultimate responsibility for the implementation of mental health protocols rests with the DBES and its respective school administrators.

1

ARTICLE III

Responsibilities of DBES

DBES agrees to:

- Use, adapt, and contextualize the SMU Telemental Health Support Manual solely for the internal and educational use of DBES schools.
- Ensure that the revised or contextualized version acknowledges Saint Mary's University and the SMU TALAS Team as the original authors, including citation within the manual and its front matter.
- Refrain from selling, commercializing, or distributing the Manual outside the DBES system without prior written consent from SMU.
- Share with SMU a copy of the contextualized version for documentation and research utilization reporting without the need for any demand. Furthermore, DBES grants SMU a perpetual, royalty-free license to access and utilize the contextualized versions for the purpose of academic research, publication, and further development of the TALAS project.
- Indemnify and hold SMU free and harmless from any liability, claims, or damages arising from the use, contextualization, or implementation of the Manual. SMU assumes no responsibility for any decisions or actions taken by DBES based on the material provided.

ARTICLE IV

Intellectual Property Rights

- The original TMH Service Manual remains the intellectual property of SMU and its authors (the TALAS Team).
- DBES obtains a non-exclusive, royalty-free license to edit, reproduce, and use the Manual for internal operations.
- Any derivative works produced shall include the following acknowledgment (or a similar mutually agreed-upon statement):

"This manual is an adapted version of the Telemental Health Support Manual developed by Saint Mary's University through its TALAS Team. Used with permission."

ARTICLE V

Confidentiality

Both Parties shall ensure that any sensitive or confidential information shared in relation to the Manual or its implementation shall be handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173) and applicable policies of the Church and the institutions.

ARTICLE VI

Effectivity and Duration

This Agreement shall take effect upon signing by both Parties and shall remain valid for three (3) years, unless earlier terminated or renewed upon mutual written consent.

ARTICLE VII

Amendments

Any revision, amendment, or supplement to this Agreement shall be made in writing and signed by authorized representatives of both Parties.

ARTICLE VIII

Termination

Either Party may terminate this Agreement for valid cause upon thirty (30) days written notice to the other Party. All obligations incurred prior to termination shall remain binding.

2

ARTICLE IX

Dispute Resolution

Any dispute arising from this Agreement shall be settled amicably through dialogue. If unresolved, the matter shall be referred to the Diocese of Bayombong and the SMU administration for mediation. Should mediation fail, the matter shall be submitted to the proper Philippine court with jurisdiction.

ARTICLE X

Separability Clause

If any provision of this Agreement is declared invalid or unenforceable, the remaining provisions shall remain in full force and effect.

ARTICLE XI

Non-Financial Nature

This Agreement does not involve any exchange of funds between the Parties unless otherwise agreed upon in a supplemental agreement.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the Parties have hereunto set their hands on the date and place first above written.

FOR SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

Name: JOHN OCTAVIOUS S. PALINA
 Position: President
 Signature: _____
 Date: _____

FOR THE DIOCESE OF BAYOMBONG EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Name: REV. FR. RAMALO C. FELIZ, Ph.D.
 Position: Superintendent
 Signature: _____
 Date: _____

Draft MOA between the research team and participating schools

Annex E: Conference Photo Documentation
 Photos and Certificate of Presentation

Annex F: Journal Submission and Acceptance Record

Annex G: Embedment of TMH in GC 203: Counseling Theories and Techniques Syllabus

COURSE SYLLABUS

Course Number	Course Descriptive Title	Semester/Term	Academic Year	Credit Unit/s			Time Allotment Per Semester/MT		
				Lecture	Laboratory	Total	Lecture	Laboratory	Total
GC 203	Counseling Theories and Techniques	First Semester	2025-2026	5		5	90		90

Intended Learning Outcomes	Topics	Week No. & Time Allotment	Methodology	Resources	Assessment
<p>CLO6. Practice multicultural counseling skills through telemental health counseling</p> <p>CLO7. Apply one's personal style/philosophy of counseling</p> <p>CLO8. Demonstrate appropriate leads and responses during TMH counseling session</p>	TMH counseling	<p>Week 16</p> <p>(3 hours)</p>	<p>Experiential Learning:</p> <p>Telemental health counseling sessions</p> <p>Self-Assessments</p>	Locally developed TMH Service Manual	Counseling Reports

Annex H: Dissemination of the Utilization Report

DeBusschere Hall, December 10, 2025

Feedback from Clients

1. **From Guidance Counselors & Administrators**
 - Reported that the TMH Manual provided “clear steps” for safe and structured TMH delivery.
 - Valued the templates (intake, consent, crisis flowchart), which “reduced preparation time.”
 - Appreciated the emphasis on ethical safeguards, particularly confidentiality and emergency response.
2. **School Partners**

- MOA provided “direction and stability” for TMH implementation.
 - Schools noted that the research “validated existing mental health needs” and guided their policy revisions.
3. **From International Conference Participants**
- Provided constructive comments on methodology, cultural framing, and interpretation of findings.
 - Acknowledged the project as “relevant for post-pandemic mental health service delivery.”
4. **From the Journal Reviewers**
- Praised the study’s theoretical grounding and practical implications.
 - Suggested refinements that strengthened the manuscript.

IPB-03**Project GREEN MIND: Generating Responsible Environmental Education for Nurturing Minds In Nature and Development**

Samuel B. Damayon, Edwin Edilberto N. Mania, Nicole Anne P. Aquino, & Ruthie Maye R. Padilla

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In an era characterized by escalating environmental concerns and the imperative for sustainable practices, understanding the role of education in fostering environmental sustainability is paramount. The research employed a quantitative method approach, using a survey to comprehensively examine students' attitudes, knowledge, and behaviors toward environmental issues and sustainable living practices. Drawing on a diverse sample of students across educational levels, the study found that at Saint Mary's University, students have a high level of environmental awareness, eco-consciousness, and environmental stewardship. It was further affirmed that those three environmental concepts are intricately influencing one another. The profile variables of gender, age, type of high school they graduated from, and religion are not influential or predictive of their environmental awareness, eco-consciousness, and environmental stewardship. However, school, year level, and ethnicity are influential or predictive. Finally, Saint Mary's University is fertile ground for environmental sustainability practices, as students have a high level of environmental awareness, eco-consciousness, and environmental stewardship, which are important dimensions of environmental sustainability. It was then recommended that its programs, projects, and activities be sustained and intensified to protect and conserve the environment.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

There are four strategic activities that the project must undertake to achieve its goal.

The first strategic activity on the list is the **conduct of a seminar-workshop on Climate change, biodiversity, sustainability, and the SDGs**. This was in partnership with World Wide Fund (WWF) for Nature Philippines with the topics "Education for Sustainability with WWF-Philippines (Read Related Story - https://smu.edu.ph/project-green-mind-generating-responsible-environmental-education-for-nurturing-minds-in-nature-and-development/?fbclid=IwY2xjawOPm-xleHRuA2FlbQIxMABicmlkETEza1daVk9PM1dUU3FQOUZYc3l0YwZhchBfaWQQMjlyMDM5MTc4ODlwMDg5MgABHvpzT3Xcgby8TBvabUete9A34B2882fXfafobWyrYIXfR1d9XqP8q5Bs7Tsa_aem_cWIY4MGE_c3vkZkiAhs_bg).")"

The research team of Project Green Mind, in collaboration with the Worldwide Fund for Nature Philippines (WWF-Philippines), has conducted a forum-workshop on Biodiversity, Climate Change, and Education for Sustainability. The forum-workshop was held on September 29, 2025, from 7:30 to 12:00 Noon at the St. Pedro Calungsod Hall. The participants were student leaders from extracurricular and co-curricular organizations, as well as students from Contemporary World classes. The forum was facilitated by Miss Ruthie Maye R. Padilla, an officer of the WWF-Philippines since 2008. She is a big fan of nature and a strong believer in the power of education. Her personal goal is to inspire people to fall in love with nature, cultivate curiosity about the planet, and encourage action and a commitment to the environment. The participants' evaluation of the activity speaks about the impact of the forum on them. One participant wrote: "Nature is not separate from us; it is us." Too often, people see the environment as

something out there, a background to our lives, when in truth, we are a part of it. It is a reminder that the fight for a cleaner, safer, and greener world is not only about saving ecosystems but about securing our own future and dignity as human beings.

Project GREEN MIND is a research utilization initiative that instills environmental awareness, develops eco-consciousness, and promotes environmental stewardship by embedding responsible environmental education into university activities, community development, and youth engagement. At its core, the project champions the idea that education is a powerful tool for cultivating environmental knowledge, eco-consciousness, and the values and actions needed to sustain our planet. This project is also a collaboration with its external partner, the Worldwide Fund for Nature (WWF-Philippines). The facilitator was assisted by the researchers, particularly Dr. Edwin Edilberto Mania, Miss Nicole Aquino, and Mr. Samuel Damayon. The forum must have an impact on the participants, as one wrote – “It was really commendable that the forum was not just about giving information and sharing awareness, instead, the incorporation of activities that we students did *ourselves, made us united, a community that has the same goals, to preserve our Mother Earth.*”

The second and third strategic activities were the Slogan and plogging activities with tree monitoring.

The second and third strategic activities coincided with the University’s ECOLOGICAL–CHSF Week, held from November 17 to 22, 2025, which marked an exciting celebration of the university’s commitment to environmental sustainability. Project Green Mind, in partnership with the World Wide Fund (WWF) for Nature Philippines and in collaboration with the Community Engagement and Indigenous Peoples’ Studies Center (CEIPSC), National Student Training Program (NSTP), the Student Central Council (SCC), Safety and Pollution Control Office (SPCO), various student organizations, including Marian RISE, SERVE (Student Empowerment through Responsibility, Volunteerism, and Engagement) SMU, Marian Leo Club, and volunteers, organized three main activities: a slogan-making contest, a plogging event, and a tree monitoring program. Each activity encouraged students to share their beliefs, take action, and promote environmental responsibility on campus and in the surrounding communities. Furthermore, each activity supported the objectives of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land), as students engaged in actions that promoted sustainability and ecological protection.

The **slogan-making contest**, held on November 19, 2025, inspired students to creatively articulate their call to end plastic pollution and promote ecological awareness (See the call for participants: <https://web.facebook.com/share/p/1CWWt163mC/>). Their entries not only showcased artistic talent but also reflected the collective desire for a cleaner, greener future. It aligns strongly with SDG 12 by raising awareness on reducing waste and choosing sustainable alternatives. The contest was conducted in collaboration with the Student Central Council and SERVE (Student Empowerment through Responsibility, Volunteerism, and Engagement) at SMU, a volunteer organization formed through the Green Mind project. The Project Green Mind Team and the SERVE SMU student organization facilitated the slogan contest. The outputs of the 14 students who participated were posted at the Student Central Council FB page (See the outputs - <https://web.facebook.com/share/p/194V1PLNu3/>).

Meanwhile, the **plogging activity** on November 22, 2025, brought environmental action to the ground, as groups of students jogged and walked through designated areas, picking up plastic litter. Several volunteers and student leaders from different student

organizations pre-registered for the event. This plogging activity is a fusion of fitness and community service, emphasizing that caring for the environment can be integrated into everyday routines. This fusion of fitness and environmental service supported SDG 11 by contributing to cleaner communities and SDG 13 by emphasizing proactive action against environmental degradation. The plogging activity began at the 4 pillars of the university, with Dr. Christopher Allen Marquez delivering an opening message about the challenge of caring for our environment. He emphasized one of the challenges in the recently concluded Miss Universe Pageant, which touched on the idea that there is no other home for us than the world, and that we should take care of it. This was followed by a discussion of the very nature and purpose of plogging, including the distribution of plastic bags and the route. The plan is to walk or jog until the area for the tree monitoring. Before this event, the group attended the ecological mass (supposedly at the San Lorenzo Ruiz Park) at the Mary Seat of Wisdom Chapel due to inclement weather. In the Mass, Fr. Nemesio Huesca, CICM, the University Chaplain, reminded the participants of what they were about to do: being stewards of the environment.

After the mass, the student leaders and volunteers were instructed to form two groups, one for the right side of the road and the other for the left. The plogging activity began at the university campus, then proceeded through Ponce Street towards Savemore Market, followed by a route along the national highway, passing by the Region 2 Trauma Medical Center, and continued up to Upper Magsaysay, before reaching the Masoc University property. Along the way, the student volunteers and leaders collected a significant amount of plastic litter, with some bags deposited in designated garbage areas and others taken to the university for proper disposal.

Lastly, the **tree monitoring activity**, which followed the plogging activity, allowed volunteers to revisit previously planted trees, assess their health, and document their growth, spearheaded by the Marian RISE student organization. Students brought measuring tapes, rulers, and string to measure the height and diameter of the planted trees. They also provided numbers to these plants after assessing their very condition. The number and plant description will serve as the basis for a visit in the near future, allowing the university to gather data on how many planted trees survive. The student volunteers and leaders greatly enjoyed this. This activity reinforced the message that sustainability is an ongoing responsibility that requires attention and care, directly contributing to SDG 15, which advocates for the protection, restoration, and enhancement of terrestrial ecosystems.

Through the combined efforts of different offices, organizations, participants, and volunteers, Project Green Mind successfully deepened environmental consciousness and promoted active engagement. The Ecological-CHSF Week became more than a celebration, with other activities; it evolved into a reminder that every Marian has a role in ensuring ecological balance and contributing to long-term sustainability (See related story

<https://smu.edu.ph/ecological-chsf-week-project-greenmind-in-collaboration-with-the-slogan-making-contest-the-plogging-activity-and-tree-monitoring/>).

To implement the Plogging and tree-monitoring activities, the **Project Marian P.L.A.N.T.S.** was conceptualized. PLANTS stands for P.L.A.N.T.S. – Promoting Leadership and Nature Through Sustainability. During the CHSF or Ecological Week, and in support of the university's commitment to sustainability, environmental consciousness, and stewardship, Project Green Mind designed Marian P.L.A.N.T.S. (Promoting Leadership and Nature Through Sustainability), which engages students and student leaders in environmental action through plogging, tree monitoring, and area clearing activities. This project aims to merge leadership in action with ecological stewardship, promoting

both physical wellness and environmental care. Through this activity, student leaders will model responsibility and inspire their peers to participate in maintaining a cleaner, greener, and more sustainable community.

The project was meant to put together the two main activities, plogging and tree-monitoring, with the following objectives:

- To promote environmental awareness and responsibility among students and student leaders through active participation in plogging and site-cleaning activities.
- To monitor and assess the growth and condition of previously planted trees to ensure the continuity of reforestation efforts.
- To maintain cleanliness and orderliness in the designated planting area by clearing waste and overgrown vegetation.
- To strengthen teamwork, cooperation, and leadership values among participating student leaders.
- To encourage a culture of environmental sustainability and physical wellness within the university community.

The fourth strategic activity is the formation or reorganization of a volunteer organization focused on environmental conservation advocacy, which will assist the university in implementing the CHSF, the Green Campus Project, and other university programs related to protecting and conserving the ecology and environment.

At the start of the 2025-2026 academic year, an organization called SERVE (Student Empowerment through Responsibility, Volunteerism, and Engagement) was formed at SMU through the Project Green Mind team. SERVE SMU, or Student Empowerment through Responsibility, Volunteerism, and Engagement, was established as a university-wide initiative to cultivate a culture of student leadership grounded in service. Guided by its mission, SERVE SMU sought to empower students to grow as responsible leaders by providing meaningful service and volunteer opportunities that shaped their character and strengthened their sense of purpose. The program emerged as a response to the university's call to foster compassion and civic responsibility, encouraging students to extend their service both within the campus and in surrounding communities. SERVE SMU has created a Facebook page (<https://web.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61583973699562>) where they can post and share their activities.

Through its network of projects and partnerships, as enshrined in its Constitution, By-Laws, and Action Plan, SERVE SMU has committed itself to addressing community needs, protecting the environment, and promoting positive social change. These efforts were anchored on the belief that impactful service becomes possible when students work together with integrity, respect, and dedication. As the organization took root, it continually nurtured values of integrity, collaboration, and empathy, recognizing these as essential foundations of effective student leadership. In this way, SERVE SMU grew not only as a volunteer movement but as a transformative platform where students learned to serve with conviction, lead with compassion, and engage with the world as agents of meaningful change.

With only almost 5 months of existence, SERVE SMU had already engaged its officers and members in environmental protection activities and volunteer activities. They have participated in the tree-growing activity at Banging, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya (See related story - <https://web.facebook.com/share/p/1ARugBpyRG/>) in collaboration with other organizations like the Marian Leo Club, the Marian Visual Arts Society, and

even the Bayombong LGU during its first Tourism Walk that aimed to maintain our natural Resources in Bayombong (See activity - <https://web.facebook.com/share/p/16Xkxy9A4f/>). They had also volunteered for other university activities, such as the slogan-making contest.

Documentation of Utilization

A. Climate Change and Biodiversity Seminar-Forum

The poster features the logos of Saint Mary's University and WWF. The main title is "Project GREEN MIND: Generating Responsible Environmental Education for Nurturing Minds In Nature and Development". The event is scheduled for September 29, 2025, from 7:30 am to 12:00 noon at St. Pedro Calungsod Hall. The program includes registration, prayer, welcome messages, a rationale, an introduction to WWF, a sharing session on biodiversity, a break, a climate change session with discussion questions, a reflection session, an education for sustainable development session with discussion questions, a planning session, a reporting activity, and a closing message.

7:30am-7:45am	Registration	
7:46am-8:00am	Prayer	Miss Nicole Anne Aquino Faculty Member, STEH
	Welcome Message	Dr. Christopher Allen S. Marquez Director, CELPSC
	Rationale	Dr. Edwin Ediberto N. Mania Head, Guidance and Testing Office
8:01am-8:10am	Introduction to WWF and Presentation of Program	
8:11am-8:25am	Munimuni Muna	
8:26am-8:50am	Sharing Session on Biodiversity	
8:51am-9:05am	Break	
9:06am-9:45am	Climate Change	What are the causes and effects of Climate Change? How do people contribute to Climate Change? How are communities and ecosystems affected by the changing climate? How are people responding to the effects of climate change? What is mitigation and adaptation?
9:46am-9:50am	Reflection	
9:51am-10:30am	Education for Sustainable Development	What is sustainable development? What is Education for Sustainable Development? What are its characteristics and cornerstones? How can we have a whole-school approach to implementing ESD?
10:31am-11:10am	Planning Session	
11:11am-11:50am	Reporting Activity/Presentation	
11:51am-12:00nn	Giving of Token to Facilitators	
	Closing Message	Mr. Samuel B. Damayon Dean, Student Affairs and Services
		Mr. Samuel B. Damayon Master of Ceremonies

Above: The program for the Forum-workshop on climate change and biodiversity.

Above: Miss Ruthie May R. Padilla, from WWF Philippines, discusses the impact of climate change on our ecology.

Below: Student participants are preparing their plans to address concerns about climate change and the rising threats to biodiversity.

Below: Other participants are also investigating other members of our ecology.

Above: The participants, the Project Green Mind research team, and the esteemed resource speaker

A. Slogan Contest

Above: The facilitators from SERVE SMU and a Project Green Mind research team member explain the contest guidelines

Below: The contestants for the SLOGAN making contest

Below: Individual participants with their output slogan (selected)

B. Plogging Activity

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
 Student Central Council | School Councils | Serve SMU | Marian RISE | LEO Club

P. L. A. N. T. S.

Promoting Leadership and Nature Through Sustainability

November 22, 2025, Saturday, 7:30am-12:00pm

MASOC UNIVERSITY PROPERTY AND ALL STREETS OF THE BARANGAYS THAT WILL BE PASSED THROUGH

What will happen!?

7:00-7:30 am	Assembly and Orientation at the 4 pillars
7:30-8:45 am	Ecological Mass
8:45-10:15am	Plogging Activity
10:15-11:15am	Tree Monitoring (concurrent)
10:15-11:15am	Clearing of Planting area (concurrent)
11:15-11:30am	Debriefing and Reflection
11:30-12:00pm	Closing Program

Scan to Register

What to bring!?

1. Gloves (individual participants)
2. Cleaning tools (rakes, shovels, sickles, etc.) (Individual Participants)
3. Monitoring sheets, tape measure, and ribbon for marking for tree inventory noting the species, the status, the height, and breadth of foliage, etc. (Marian Rise Advisors/SPCO)
4. First aid kit (SERVE SMU Officers)
5. Drinking water (KSB)
6. Eco-bags/Sacks for collected litter (Marian Rise Officers - thru OSO)
7. Identification tags for trees grown (Marian RISE/SPCO)
8. Certificates of participation (Project Green Mind proponents)

Above: Dr. Allen Marquez, the CEIPSC Director, delivers his opening remarks to all participants in the Plogging and tree monitoring activity at the 4 pillars. Standing beside him is the Lead Researcher of Project Green Mind.

Below: The project Marian PLANTS, which juxtaposed the two activities of plogging and tree monitoring

C. Tree-monitoring

Above: Mr. Samuel Damayon documents the detailed instructions given by Mr. Kerwin Bayot, adviser of Marian RISE, to the volunteer and student leaders.

Below: Students are dispersed to monitor the planted trees, record their observations, and place plant numbers for monitoring.

Students are measuring the planted trees and recording their condition. They were instructed to get the height and the diameter of the plants. Above is a plant that were monitored and coded through a number for monitoring.

Feedback from Clients

A. Climate Change and Biodiversity Forum-Workshop

Based on the evaluation of the activity, participants expressed that their environmental knowledge and awareness had increased. They also agree that the forum workshop has provided them with a natural, experiential learning experience, making them more empathetic towards the environment and its natural ecosystem. The photo below shows their experience at the event.

Based on their comments, the climate change and biodiversity forum-workshop has a good impact on the students. The following were their verbatim statements in evaluating the event:

1. *We do not own the earth, man belong to earth,*
2. *As human being we do know are responsibilities with our mother earth , as we consume what's the nature provide to us, we should care and love the nature*
3. *Kahit konting pagbasura sa tamang basurahan nakakakontribute sa lipunan (Even a small act of disposing of waste properly can contribute to society.)*
4. *Learned more about biodiversity and how important it is to protect and preserve what is ours for our future generations.*
5. *It is true that we only live once, therefore we should know how to take care of our environment for our future. We do not want our future generations to experience a world full of pollution and technologies, instead we want them to experience how wonderful our world is.*

6. *Aside from the meaning of the technical terms such as biodiversity, climate change, and others mentioned, I learned the importance of practicing what we preach—how the learnings should be actualized in order to create an impact. I also gained insights about the richness and beauty of our country, which ignited a sense of pride in me as a Filipino despite the chaos in the country.*
7. *I have been educated with regards to the numerous environmental challenges that our world is currently facing. This forum-workshop reminded me that we should strive to attain our sustainable development goals for a greener nature in the future.*
8. *Nature is not separate from us—it is us. Too often, people see the environment as something 'out there,' a background to our lives, when in truth, we are a part of it. It is a reminder that the fight for a cleaner, safer, and greener world is not only about saving ecosystems but about securing our own future and dignity as human beings.*
9. *I have learned how important it is to be proactive when it comes to being a steward of God's creation and how crucial it is for our future.*
10. *I realized that environmental protection starts with awareness. By being informed, I become more responsible in the way I use resources and interact with nature.*
11. *I've learn that our nature is rich in a way that there are different kinds of animals, corals, islands, plants, etc. We need to take care of the next generation.*
12. *It widened our knowledge and also our awareness about climate change, biodiversity loss and more. We, as youth and future leaders of our society, can start by taking action that can lead to significant positive change.*
13. *Its a good refresher to remind us again the youth about the reality of our world, teaching us about sustainability and being proactive.*
14. *The Seminar-Workshop was great and interactive.*
15. *This should be more implemented by frequency and practice, and also to go to communities in the far flung.*

B. Slogan Making Contest

For the slogan contest, participants have also gained a great deal of insight. All of the evaluators say that the activity was very important to them.

Furthermore, they further explained how the activity was very important. They said:

1. *I help to spread awareness especially with environmental issues. The slogan activity is important to me because it lets me live out the Marian values of excellence, innovation, communion, and social responsibility while raising awareness about ending global plastic pollution.*
2. *It is very important to me because it allowed me to have a platform to share my thoughts and participate in the CHSF Week.*

3. *It serves as an advocacy and our stand about the global issues especially about our environment*
4. *It helped me not only sharpen my critical thinking, esp in organizing my ideas and choosing the right words to speak for everyone, but also pushed me out of my comfort zone. I took a risk by doing something I once loved, even if I'm not good or perfect at it.*
5. *I'm grateful for the theme because it's deeply relevant to the environmental issues we Filipinos face today, issues that continue to cause disasters in our communities. I realized that it doesn't matter how "artistic" or "creative" the work looks; what truly matters is the sincerity of the message and the intention to care for the environment.*
6. *I hope I can join again—better prepared, more confident, and ready to do what I couldn't do this time. These reasons are why this experience is important to me.*
7. *It made me become more aware and take initiative in voicing out environmental concerns through slogan.*
8. *It is important because we can use this activity to call for action not just to our fellow marians but also in our community*
9. *Important to advocate environmental awareness*

C. Plogging Activity

Plogging, although exhausting, requires students to jog or walk a certain distance while picking up plastic litter. This is in line with the Ecological / CHSF week celebration's theme "Marians Ending Global Plastic Pollution." According to the student participant, plogging is a good reminder for young people and the community to rethink how we use plastic. Their evaluation shows that the majority, if not all, of the participants are very satisfied with the activity.

The following are the verbatim statements of the participants on how important the Plogging activity is to them:

1. *The experience made me realize that small actions like plogging and tree monitoring create a meaningful impact by keeping the environment clean and ensuring trees grow properly. Do these activities more regularly with proper tools and guidance to make them even more effective.*
2. *As an individual who also experience various effects of climate change, such activities are fulfilling to my part as I got to participate and contribute to the reduction of such things.*
3. *It helped me reflect on how important it is to protect and preserve the environment and become a responsible steward of God's creation.*
4. *The activities conducted helped towards maintaining the cleanliness of the community and to measure the growth of the plants.*

5. *Very Important for me as a student and as someone who cares for the environment. It allows me to help the community and allows me to see what help I could extend to the community.*
6. *Its very important because through this activity we can strongly promote the Leadership and helping our nature through sustainability*
7. *It gives me reflection how to manage the dirt and to plant trees*
8. *They were able to exercise our environmental consciousness and put them to real action beyond just what we have learned in classes and seminars. We were able to evaluate in such simple activities our surrounding environments and also helped in the simple act of cleaning it.*
9. *Plogging and tree monitoring are important to me because they promote environmental awareness, encourage responsibility, and help develop a sense of community involvement. These activities teach us to care for our surroundings, practice sustainability, and take part in protecting the environment for future generations.*
10. *It's important because it made me more become aware of our environment.*
11. *These activities are very important because not only do they raise awareness and provide information on how we can address environmental problems, but they also encourage us to take real and meaningful action. Through these activities, we learn that caring for the environment is not just about knowing what is happening, it is about becoming involved in the solutions. For example, through tree monitoring, we can ensure that trees damaged by the recent storms will be identified and replaced. This allows us to actively restore what has been lost, support the recovery of our surroundings, and contribute to long-term environmental sustainability.*
12. *Plogging combines physical exercise with civic action, making fitness itself an environmental contribution, while monitoring trees helps assess their health and measure the effectiveness of reforestation efforts.*
13. *Plogging helps keep the environment clean by removing litter while promoting physical fitness and community responsibility. Tree monitoring is important because it ensures that planted trees grow healthily, preventing wasted efforts and resources. Together, these activities support a cleaner, greener, and more sustainable environment, and such simple acts adds as a big help for the environment.*
14. *Plogging and monitoring are vital because they turn small actions into powerful change.*
15. *They show that when we care for our planet and stay accountable, we protect not just our world today, but the future we all share.*
16. *This is of important particularly now particularly the plogging activity, as this will serve as a way for us to be aware that growing a tree really takes time to fully developed and so, we must take an action to fight for those people who destroy nature for the sake of money. In addition, it gives us as well an opportunity to help in our own simple ways just by simply picking pisces of trash and monitoring the progress of trees which provides big impact to our nature.*

D. Tree Monitoring Activity

For the tree-monitoring, where students had to record the condition of the planted trees and place a number on them after measuring the height and diameter, students enjoyed the activity. This is shown from their evaluation:

From their comments and insights gained, the student participants expressed how important the activities were:

1. *I enjoyed the tree monitoring activity, especially in assessing their state and identifying their types, despite having no idea what kind of tree I am assessing at least there are facilitators who helped us identify them. Hoping for more hands-on activities like these in the future that helps the students connect more to nature.*
2. *Personally, the 2 activities were very important because of its relevance today. Globally, we are experiencing massive plastic pollution and deforestation practice. Locally, especially with the issue now on mining, we give value to the importance of our green forest, our trees. And this activity gave us the chance to help even with our little contributions.*
3. *very relevant in our times as we are advocating for the wellness of our environment.*
4. *The importance for me regarding both of the activities would be how community based it was, showing how, as we go from the school to Magsaysay, we were interacting with many people as we pass by, showing good socialization and different types of interactions as we go.*
5. *And as well as the love for nature, back then we weren't mindful when it comes to seeing a small piece of plastic around the streets, but showing our activity, we examined more when we examined or observe more.*
6. *It helped me connect with nature and unwind even for a short time only*
7. *I believe that both activities are vital not just for my personal growth, but also to nature in general, because I was able to assess the status of our surroundings in a part of our province. At the same time, I was also able to contribute in a way wherein we removed the factors that negatively affects our environment.*
8. *Healing and preserving comes hand in hand. It also helps us to sustain His creation.*
9. *The first one helps mitigate plastic pollution. The other increases the efficiency and success of reforestation project.*

IPB-04**Implementing a Sustainable E-Waste Management Framework for an HEI to Foster a Circular Economy: Designing Informational Brochures**

Gertrude G. Danao, Mildios Meeds Ciriaco Blando, Irish E. Reginalde, Carina S. Mallillin, & Sheila Marie G. Gilo

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The study explores the role of higher education institutions (HEIs) in advancing sustainable ewaste management. Findings emphasize the importance of an e-waste management plan for an institution. To operationalize this framework, the researchers implemented awareness initiatives by designing and distributing brochures and posters. These materials were strategically placed at e-waste drop-off points, particularly in front of the CETSO office near the gymnasium, where students, faculty, staff, and visitors pass by. Brochures were also distributed during training sessions to reinforce awareness.

The brochure design incorporated visuals, calls to action, and contact information before printing and distribution. The posters complement the brochures, which highlight the implications and importance of e-waste management. The pilot program tested framework policies such as designated drop-off points and educational dissemination, with recorded e-waste donations.

Results indicate that targeted awareness campaigns that combine visual materials and training can effectively increase institutional participation in sustainable practices. However, there is still a need for enhanced dissemination. The study demonstrates that HEIs can play an important role in reducing electronic waste by adopting structured frameworks and awareness strategies. This initiative provides a replicable model for other institutions seeking to integrate sustainability into their operations, thereby contributing to environmental preservation and risk mitigation.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

After submitting the proposed SMU E-Waste Management Plan to the Vice President for Administration, the researchers initiated initial implementation activities. The main objective was to evaluate the efficacy of the e-waste management framework by designing an e-waste management brochure to increase awareness among higher education institutions (HEIs).

As part of these objectives, the researchers designed brochures and posters. These materials were placed at the e-waste drop-off point located in front of the CETSO office near the gymnasium. The location was considered ideal because students, faculty, non-academic personnel, and visitors regularly pass through this area, ensuring that the poster is easily visible and the brochures are readily accessible.

Brochures were also distributed during training sessions aimed at raising awareness of e-waste management. In addition, brochures were placed in a box near the drop-off point for convenient access. The brochure design incorporated visuals and images related to e-waste, included calls to action, and provided contact details and social media links for follow-up. Fonts were chosen for readability, layouts for appeal, and images for

high quality. After finalizing the prototype, the brochures were printed and prepared for distribution.

Alongside the brochures, a poster was also designed and developed to emphasize the importance and implications of e-waste management. To monitor the impact of these awareness initiatives—including posters, brochures, and training sessions—the researchers recorded the amount of e-waste donated at the drop-off point.

Documentation of Utilization

1. Submission of the SMU e-Waste Management Plan to VPA

2. Development of e-waste management brochure

3. Development of an e-waste management poster

4. SMU e-waste drop-off point

5. Training on e-waste management awareness

6. List of submitted e-waste (as of 1/8/2026)

Date	ID Number	Course / Office / School / Department	Year	Item Description	QTY.
8-20-24	0124302576	SHS		Tractor not work	1
8-22-24	0738302526	SHS		video camera	1
8-2-25	0704322626	SHS		1 pack of paper	1
8-0-25		SHS		TV 32"	1
11-10-25	1518	SHS		electric fan	1
11-11-25	1316	SHS		mouse	1
07-02-26	3014	CEISO		TIRE INFLATOR	1
11-01-26	7939	CEISO		RAVAT PUMP 1000000000 POWER BANK	1
11-07-26	2019	CEISO		Computer Mouse	1

Feedback from Clients

No feedback from clients was gathered, as the researchers focused on identifying e-waste management brochures, posters, training materials, and e-waste collection methods.

IPB-05**Science-Math Educators' PRESENT (Promoting Resilience through diverse Experience, academic Support, Excogitation, exploring Notion, and providing educational Training)**

Analyn A. Guevara, Lorna C. Aban, Domingo T. Guntalilib, Ronnie B. Bibas, & Florentino A. Aban Jr.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The sci-math teachers use manipulatives in their teaching. The science teachers allow their students to observe, sometimes to explore and manipulate laboratory apparatus such as microscopes and a human torso. In the field of mathematics, real-life objects are used in most illustrative examples. Flash cards, Damath boards, and number line Math bingo are used to motivate students to practice and master the four fundamental operations. Rulers, meter sticks, protractors, compasses, graphing boards, triangles, geoboards, dice, graphing aids, probability kits, and calculators are used to measure, compute, model, and teach most math concepts. Some of them prepare Do-It-Yourself (DIY) manipulatives and improvise/indigenize materials. However, the use of manipulatives is limited due to several factors. Challenges encountered in teaching secondary mathematics and science with manipulatives include limited resources, time constraints, teacher training gaps, and inadequate information dissemination.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

On January 18, 2025, "**Sci-Math Educators' Open Space Discussion**" was organized by Mrs. Lorna C. Aban and Dr. Analyn A. Guevara and held at the SMU NSTP Office. The said activity brought together educators, researchers, and students to explore current challenges and innovations in science and mathematics education.

The morning session began at 8:00 AM with registration, followed by an opening prayer and the national anthem. Mrs. Lorna C. Aban from the SOGS faculty delivered the opening remarks, setting the stage for the day's discussions.

The first discussion, led by Dr. Roselle R. Mendoza on behalf of Dr. Ronnie B. Bibas from EPS Science, SDO Nueva Vizcaya, focused on the educational challenges faced by science and math educators. This was followed by Dr. Analyn A. Guevara, SOGS Cluster Head, who presented initial research findings relevant to the field.

A key highlight of the morning was the talk by Dr. Louie B. Dasas, Assistant Dean of the College of Education at the University of Santo Tomas (UST), who presented on "Critical and Creative Thinking with AI." This session explored the intersection of artificial intelligence and educational practices, sparking considerable interest among the attendees.

The morning session concluded with a demonstration of activities by MAT Physics and PhD Science Education Math students (Mark Bernard C. San Juan, Weyalein L. Balonquita, Hector L. Maddawat, and Khriselle Mae A. Beting), showcasing practical applications and innovative teaching methods.

The afternoon session commenced at 1:00 PM with Mrs. Lorna C. Aban leading a discussion on project presentation. Finally, Mr. Olivar Reimos D. Barroga, Jr., a MAT student, delivered the closing remarks, summarizing the key takeaways from the day's discussions.

Throughout the event, Mr. Mark Bernard C. San Juan skillfully guided the proceedings as the master of ceremonies. The Sci-Math Educators' Open Space Discussion provided a valuable platform for knowledge sharing, networking, and collaborative exploration of critical issues and emerging issues.

Documentation Of Utilization

FIRST WRITESHOP (Sci-Math Manipulatives)

JULY 19, 2025 at NSTP Office

Demonstration of activities by MAT Physics and PhD Science Education Math students

Mrs. Lorna C. Aban discussing project PRESENT

Group photo of the organizers, facilitators and participants

Documentation

Registration of the participants

Dr. Roselle R. Mendoza and Dr. Analyn A. Guevara discussing the educational challenges and initial research findings

Dr. Louie B. Dasas, Assistant Dean of the College of Education at the University of Santo Tomas (UST) talks about "Critical and Creative Thinking with AI."

Six worksheets/ mathematics and science manipulative activities were prepared for the workshop on January 10, 2026.

WORKSHOP ON PRACTICAL INNOVATIONS

A workshop on practical innovations in Grade 7 Science and Mathematics activities was conducted on January 10, 2026, at the RT Conference Hall, with the theme *Fostering Excellence through Engaged Learning and Innovation*.

**Workshop on Practical Innovations:
Grade 7 Science & Mathematics Activities**
"Fostering Excellence through Engaged Learning and Innovation"

Saturday January 10, 2026 RT Conference Hall

PROGRAMME

<p>7:30am Registration</p> <p>7:50am Invocation National Anthem</p> <p>8:00am Opening Message</p> <p>8:15am Introduction to the Speakers</p> <p>8:30am Plenary Session 1 Practical Innovations in Science: Digital and Concrete Manipulatives</p> <p>10:00am Break</p> <p>10:15am Plenary Session 2 Practical Innovations in Mathematics: Digital and Concrete Manipulatives</p> <p>11:45am Lunch Break Parallel Session: Math</p>	<p>AVP AVP</p> <p>Dr. Ronnie B. Bibas EPS Science, DepED-NV</p> <p>Dr. Analyn A. Guevara Graduate Program Cluster Department Head- HNSM Cluster, SoGS</p> <p>Jennylin Carreon-Balagtas Associate Professor I, NVSU- College of Teacher Education</p> <p>Jennie Rose G. Derilo Instructor II, NVSU- College of Teacher Education</p> <p>Parallel Session: Science</p>
--	--

<p>1:00pm Demonstration 1</p> <p>2:00pm Demonstration 2</p> <p>3:00pm Break</p> <p>3:15pm Demonstration 3</p> <p>4:15pm Forum</p> <p>4:30pm Awarding of Certificates</p> <p>4:50pm Closing Remarks and Closing Prayer</p> <p>5:00pm Photo Opportunity</p>	<p>Mr. Christopher D. Julian T-III, Bintawan National High School</p> <p>Mr. Olivar Reimos D. Barroga T-I, NVGCHS</p> <p>Mr. Jayson Joe P. Salamida T-III Solano National High School</p> <p>Mr. Hector L. Maddawat PhD Student, Dela Salle University</p> <p>Mr. Florentino A. Aban Jr. MT- I, Bagabag National High School</p> <p>Mark Bernard C. San Jua Science Coordinator, SMU Senior High School</p> <p>Mrs. Lorna C. Aban Faculty, SMU School of Graduate Studies</p> <p>Mr. Domingo T. Guntalilub Jr. Faculty, SEAIT Head, NSTP Master of Ceremonies</p>
---	--

Feedback from Clients

<i>Aspects</i>	<i>Rate</i>	<i>The most important topic/activity</i>	<i>Suggestions</i>
Attainment of Objectives	Very Satisfactory	Sharing of research findings and sharing of output	More collaborations
Relevance of Topics	Very Satisfactory	The AI one	Also, get speakers from different schools as sharers of best practices

<i>Aspects</i>	<i>Rate</i>	<i>The most important topic/activity</i>	<i>Suggestions</i>
Speaker Effectiveness	Very Satisfactory	Interconnecting AI utilization with creativity and critical thinking. Using AI as a tool and not as a replacement for human intelligence.	More diverse coverage of subject areas is to be accommodated in such activity.
Effectiveness of Demonstrator 1	Very Satisfactory	Creative and Critical Thinking with AI Considerations	Thank you for the opportunity to learn, collaborate, and share experiences.
Demonstrator 2	Very Satisfactory	A deeper understanding of creative and critical thinking, manipulative, and the demonstration of the different tools	Can we have all the presentations of the speakers and demonstrators
Demonstrator 3	Very Satisfactory	all topics	cascade it to a larger audience
Demonstrator 4	Very Satisfactory	Critical Thinking and Creativity with AI	To craft a learning plan involving the use of their materials
Management	Very Satisfactory	Discussion of Creativity and Critical Thinking with AI and the Presentation of the Snake and Ladder Circuit	Looking forward to more collaborations/invitations to seminars like this
Venue Conduciveness	Very Satisfactory	Gamification enhanced students' learning through a variety of activities that allow them to create their own outputs.	Please let the speakers share their presentation and the activities we can adopt in our teaching. Thank you very much for the learning.

IPB-06**Innovative Science Instruction: Creating Enrichment Modules to Elevate Junior High School Education and Advance Curriculum Development**

Agnes N. Madamba, Judy Ann F. Sondag, Zayda S. Asuncion, Jimmy E. Valdez, & Weyalein L. Balonquita

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study examined factors influencing student experiences in junior high school elective science courses, focusing on self-efficacy, attitudes (MATSI), and academic performance. Findings indicated moderate self-efficacy and favorable attitudes. Regression analysis revealed that social persuasion and emotional states strongly influenced self-efficacy, while "desire to do science" was the key predictor of attitudes. Academic performance was proficient to highly proficient. A strong positive correlation existed between self-efficacy and attitude, but not with performance. The study concludes that curriculum redesign should prioritize the following: enhancing mastery experiences via hands-on, scaffolded learning; strengthening social persuasion through collaboration and positive feedback; maximizing vicarious experiences with role models; addressing emotional states with stress management; connecting science to real-world applications; promoting student autonomy; strengthening teacher-student relationships; implementing differentiated instruction; reducing anxiety; and targeting all grade levels for interventions. Specifically, modules are recommended to be crafted that incorporate hands-on labs, collaborative projects, mindfulness exercises, and real-world application projects. This approach will foster a positive learning environment, improve self-efficacy, and enhance student engagement in science.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The utilization of the research findings from the "ESSMAP Study" commenced with a structured translation of data into pedagogical action. Recognizing that social persuasion and emotional states were critical predictors of self-efficacy, and that the "desire to do science" drove positive attitudes, the project followed a phased implementation strategy focused on continuous feedback and refinement.

Phase 1: Collaborative Design and Capacity Building

The process began with Module Development Workshops. Science teachers convened through PLC meetings to deconstruct the existing curriculum. Guided by the research findings, they integrated specific "ESSMAP elements" into their lesson plans:

- For Mastery Experiences: Instruction was scaffolded with more hands-on, inquiry-based labs.
- For Emotional States: Short mindfulness and stress-reduction exercises were scripted to reduce anxiety.
- For Social Persuasion: Collaborative group roles were redefined to ensure peer encouragement and structured feedback.

Phase 2: Internal Validation and Refinement

Once the initial subject-specific drafts were created, Phase 2 focused on internal validation. The Internal Review and Feedback Sessions were conducted, involving fellow Science Teachers and school heads, who critically assessed the modules for cross-grade coherence and student-centricity—ensuring the content promoted student autonomy and positive learning behaviors as recommended by the ESSMAP study. It was

strategically decided that the External Expert Consultation would be deferred until the end of the school year, following the initial full cycle of module implementation, allowing the experts to critique the resources based on generated student and teacher feedback.

Phase 3: Classroom Deployment (Initial Utilization Cycle)

The Classroom Implementation phase commenced with the rollout of the refined enrichment modules into the specialized subjects. To facilitate immediate use and allow for ongoing, flexible refinement based on classroom testing, teachers provided students with module sections in the form of loose sheets (handouts) for direct in-class and out-of-class reference. This marked the successful launch of the first utilization cycle across the specialized Junior High School science subjects.

Documentation Of Utilization

Seminar-Workshop on Laboratory Techniques
with Mr. Mark Balonquita as the Resource Speaker,
July 12, 2025

Module Workshop:
Assigning Module Writers
and what to include
according to findings
(June 2025 during
PANAGSAGANA)

IPB-07**Project STEP: Shaping Tomorrow's Environment through Pathways for Wellness: A Seminar-Forum cum IEC Materials**

Mary Grace M. Bulatao, Jones K. Liwan, Jolie Mar M. Valdez, Michael A. Gabriel, Zayda S. Asuncion, Madonna Dionx C. Gonzales, & Joseph Bubod

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study examined the role of active transportation—specifically walking and cycling—in enhancing student well-being and promoting sustainability within university campuses. It assessed existing campus facilities from the students' perspective, emphasizing the need for improved infrastructure to support and encourage these activities. Findings revealed that students hold varying perceptions of active transportation, influenced by factors such as accessibility, safety, and infrastructure quality. Health benefits, cost savings, time efficiency, and distance were identified as key factors influencing their choice to engage in active transportation. While the physical, mental, and social benefits serve as strong motivators, several barriers hinder its adoption, including adverse weather conditions, safety concerns, inadequate infrastructure, and time or distance limitations. Overall, the study underscores the importance of creating safer, more accessible, and student-centered environments to promote active transportation as a viable and sustainable mobility option on campus.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The project began in August 2025 with planning and coordination meetings involving the research team and university stakeholders. These meetings ensured that the project plan was finalized and that all roles and responsibilities were clearly assigned. With the preparatory groundwork completed, the project moved toward material development.

In September 2025, the research team focused on producing the educational materials needed for the awareness campaign. These materials, including brochures and flyers, were designed to promote active transportation among students.

The core implementation activity took place on December 4 and 5, 2025, when the research team conducted the seminar forum and distributed the informational brochures and flyers to the participants. This event aimed to increase awareness and encourage greater interest in walking and cycling on campus.

After the seminar, the research team collected feedback from students to understand their insights, reactions, and suggestions regarding the activity and the provided materials. This feedback served as a basis for assessing the seminar's effectiveness and identifying areas for improvement.

The project concluded with the documentation of outcomes and preparation of the final report. The research team consolidated the activity results, integrated the student feedback, and formulated recommendations to guide future initiatives promoting active transportation. Through this sequence of activities, the project achieved its expected outcomes and contributed to ongoing efforts to foster healthier, more sustainable mobility practices within the campus community.

Documentation Of Utilization

Feedback from Clients

Upon the project's implementation, the respondents shared that the forum and the distribution of brochures on active transportation were timely and relevant, especially given the growing popularity of hiking, jogging, and biking among students. Many participants expressed that the advocacy aligned with current campus interests, with one student noting, *"Sakto po ang topic kasi uso talaga ngayon ang hiking at biking sa amin"* (The topic is timely because hiking and biking are really popular among us nowadays). Another added, *"Maganda na napag-usapan ito dahil marami na rin sa amin ang nagjo-jogging tuwing umaga"* (It is good that this was discussed because many of us have also started jogging every morning). Students also emphasized that the brochures were informative and easy to understand. One remarked, *"Malaking tulong po ang brochure kasi malinaw ang explanation tungkol sa benefits ng walking at cycling"* (The brochure is a great help because the explanation about the benefits of walking and cycling is clear), while another shared, *"Nagustuhan ko dahil simple lang pero kompleto sa impormasyon tungkol sa advantages ng active transportation"* (I liked it because it is simple yet complete in providing information about the advantages of active

transportation). Several participants appreciated learning about the positive impacts, saying, *“Mas naintindihan ko kung paano nakakatulong sa health ang paglalakad at pagba-bike”* (I better understood how walking and biking contribute to health).

Some respondents reflected on how the information influenced their outlook, with one stating, *“Na-inspire ako na mas subukan ang walking kasi nakita ko yung mga benepisyo nito”* (I was inspired to try walking more because I saw its benefits). At the same time, another mentioned, *“Mas na-realize ko na hindi lang siya exercise kundi paraan din para makatipid sa pamasaha”* (I realized that it is not only a form of exercise but also a way to save on transportation expenses).

Overall, the students' feedback showed that the activity and materials were well-received and strengthened their understanding of the health, financial, and environmental benefits of active transportation.

IPB-08**PROJECT PEACE HUB: Promoting Empathy, Acceptance, and Civic Engagement By Harnessing Unity And Building Belongingness Among Marians**

Susan A. Galamay, Brian M. Baristo, & Benyamin Messakaraeng

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Fostering a sense of belonging in school is fundamental to creating a safe and supportive learning environment, nurturing respect, empathy, and fairness among students, and addressing issues of bullying, discrimination, violence, and equity. Students who feel a strong sense of belonging to their academic community are likely to engage with their academic community, seek help when needed, and persist in their academic goals (Goodenow and Grade, 2008). The sense of belongingness in universities is closely linked to students' sense of peace and well-being. As stated in the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, institutions should be strengthened to promote peaceful, inclusive, and just societies (SDG #16). The studies of Wilson and Lipsey (2018), Jones, Kljakovic, and Taylor (2018), and Palaganas and Dela Cruz (2018) found that schools implementing restorative practices experienced reductions in suspension rates, improvements in school climate, and increased feelings of student safety. This study determined the sense of belongingness among Marians in relation to their sex and cultural affiliations and explored their lived experiences on peace in the university. The study employed quantitative-qualitative approach, specifically descriptive design. A survey instrument was used to determine the level of sense of belongingness of the Marians. To explore the lived experiences on peace, interview was conducted. Focus Group Discussion was used to delve deeply into students' lived experiences and surface insights and perspectives that were not captured in the survey. The findings were used as a basis for the PROJECT PEACE HUB: Promoting Empathy, Acceptance, and Civic Engagement by Harnessing Unity and building Belongingness Among Marians.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

- **Project ARK.** At the start of the school year, students were already instructed about the Project ARK (Acts of Random Kindness). Students were grouped into five-member teams and conducted brainstorming on the project. They presented their proposals and received the go-ahead to start their project. The students sold sweet products. 50% of the profit was used to purchase school supplies and snacks, and the other 50% was given to the members. The students submitted their gifts. The gifts were given to the children in Sitio Masina, Quezon. Moreover, supplies and snacks will be given to the LDR and security guards.
- **A seminar/Forum** was also given to the students. This seminar was conducted to raise awareness and deepen participants' understanding of the multifaceted nature of peace, encompassing not only the absence of war but also social justice, equality, and environmental sustainability. Additionally, this seminar also aimed to motivate participants to become active agents of peace in their communities, whether through advocacy, volunteering, or promoting peace. Moreover, it also encouraged participants to cultivate inner peace through mindfulness, meditation, and self-reflection, recognizing that personal well-being is essential for promoting peace in the world.
- **Learning modules.** A learning module is a self-contained unit of study designed to teach a specific topic or set of skills. Learning modules provide structured, organized learning that helps students understand the flow of the subject.

Through the learning modules, students receive the same high-quality lessons, instructions, and activities, and can review difficult parts or advance quickly through easier topics. Learning modules standardize content, ensuring that all students receive the same quality of lessons, instructions, and activities regardless of the teacher or class schedule.

Five learning modules were pilot tested with purposively selected participants enrolled in CFE 105a classes.

Documentation Of Utilization

1. The Marians' ARK (Acts of Random Kindness)

Feedback from Clients

1. Learning insights from participants (The Marians' Ark)

- a. *"As we ventured into the world of entrepreneurship, as students with the sole purpose to gain income to help, the feeling of happiness and contentment was well-filled in our hearts as we dived deeper with passion to a new yet creative way of marketing".*
- b. *"By helping others, we found a sense of purpose and meaning in our lives. Knowing that our actions positively impact others can give us a deeper sense of fulfilment and satisfaction*
- c. *"Engaging in acts of kindness can boost self-esteem and self-worth. It gave us a sense of accomplishment and reinforces positive image".*

2. Seminar on peace

- a. *"The most valuable part of the seminar was the heartfelt message about peace that peace is the ultimate goal, and when it is present, we feel at ease, secure, and blessed. The seminar emphasized that peace is achieved when there is no anger, conflict, or resentment about people and that living peacefully allows us to experience true happiness, just as the saying goes, Masaya ang mabuhay ng mapayapa. This message resonated with me deeply because it reminded me that peace begins with ourselves and extends on how we treat others. It encouraged me to strive for harmony in my relationships and to value peace as an essential part of a meaningful life".*
- b. *"The part I found most valuable was the insight that peace, love and forgiveness are inter connected and must be practiced together. Understanding that peace starts with inner calm, that love is shown through actions, and that forgiveness opens the door to healing made the seminar worthwhile".*
- c. *"I found the ice breaker of the seminar to be the most valuable because through the icebreaker, the tension between us eased up and we were able to enjoy ourselves. The icebreakers were also a great way to demonstrate how peace can be achieved in relationships because through it, I realized that all it takes for a tense situation to ease up is be smiling".*
- d. *Learning modules need to be presented to the faculty for further assessment.*

IPB-09**Project ALLIES: Advancing Links for Learning, International Engagement, and Support**

Clara M. Gonzales, Martin Manuel, Gerome Bautista, Katelijne Demeyere, & Elly Verstraete

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Internationalization (IZN) is increasingly recognized as a key measure of the societal impact of higher education institutions. It involves establishing global partnerships, promoting mobility programs, and fostering cross-cultural understanding to equip learners with essential global competencies. Despite its growing importance, there is limited research on the direct impact of internationalization on participants. This study examined the lived experiences of participants in mobility programs at Saint Mary's University (SMU), both inbound and outbound. Using a phenomenological research design, it explored how these experiences influenced participants' personal and professional development, how they derived meaning from their immersion, and how they applied their learning to benefit the University and society. SMU has both hosted international students and staff and sent its own members abroad, providing a rich context for understanding the effects of global mobility. Findings indicate that participation in internationalization initiatives significantly contributed to personal growth, intercultural competence, and professional development. Participants reported enhanced understanding of cultural differences, improved communication skills, and greater confidence in navigating global contexts. Many also applied their experiences to advance academic, social, and community initiatives within the University, demonstrating the tangible benefits of mobility programs. Overall, the study highlights that effective internationalization not only strengthens institutional partnerships and global engagement but also directly impacts participants, fostering a culture of excellence and innovation. These insights can inform SMU's strategic goals and guide other higher education institutions in designing internationalization initiatives that generate meaningful educational and societal outcomes.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

To carry out the utilization of the research and to achieve the objectives set, the following strategic activities were conducted:

Objective 1: Recruit and organize a group of student volunteers to form the core support group

- A. The call for student volunteers for global mobility was conducted from August to September 2025. Recruitment was facilitated by the current SAGA volunteer members, who led the promotion and screening activities. Applicants underwent interviews to assess their motivation for joining, prior experience in global mobility, and understanding of global citizenship. As a result of this process, SAGA now has around 20 active volunteers.
- B. The group also reviewed and updated their CBL and Action Plan. The Project ALLIES researchers provided additional recommendations, particularly concerning the group's coordination with the SMU International Office (SMU IO), which oversees all global mobility initiatives. The updated action plan focuses on strengthening support systems for both inbound and outbound mobility participants.

Student volunteers involved in internationalization activities serve in a non-remunerative capacity and will not receive financial compensation for their participation. However, in recognition of their support, the cost of local transportation

and certain food expenses may be reimbursed in accordance with SMU's financial policies and guidelines. As volunteers, they are considered IZN ambassadors and, as a result, will gain valuable personal, academic, and professional skills—such as cross-cultural competence, confidence, employability, and global awareness—and are given priority consideration for outbound global mobility opportunities.

Objective 2: Facilitate training/information session on global citizenship

C. Global Citizenship Program

On December 3, 2025, the researchers of Project ALLIES partnered with the SMU Internationalization Office and SAGA volunteer members to organize the **Global Citizenship Program 2025**, with the theme *"Marians Beyond Borders: Journeys and Reflections on Global Citizenship."* The activity aimed to provide participants with a deeper understanding of internationalization and global mobility, as well as practical skills for engaging in global opportunities. The event was attended by 114 students from SMU's undergraduate and graduate programs.

The program brought together students, faculty members, and an international guest to deepen their appreciation for global exposure and the different mobility pathways. It sought to help participants understand what it truly means to go abroad for study, training, cultural immersion, and professional development.

The speakers—four students, three faculty members, and one international guest—shared topics drawn from their personal global experiences. They discussed key areas, including preparing for international exposure, adapting to new cultures, maximizing learning opportunities abroad, and developing global competencies essential to academic and career advancement. They also highlighted practical steps for qualifying for international internships, what to expect during educational trips abroad, how leadership camps and cultural programs shape one's worldview, and the importance of global citizenship in an interconnected world. The international guest further enriched the session by offering insights on cross-cultural communication, international collaboration, and navigating diverse global environments.

In addition, the SMU Internationalization Office conducted a discussion on practical tips for preparing for global mobility. This segment covered essential guidelines for application processes, document preparation, pre-departure requirements, and strategies for maximizing international learning experiences.

The event featured presentations, storytelling, interactive discussions, and an open forum where participants could ask questions freely. This format enabled attendees to engage more meaningfully with the speakers' experiences and gain concrete ideas on how to prepare for their own potential mobility opportunities.

Overall, the Global Citizenship Program successfully achieved its goal of encouraging Marian students and faculty to broaden their horizons, embrace internationalization, and view global opportunities as meaningful pathways for personal and professional growth.

Objective 3: Support inbound and outbound students in various internationalization initiatives

D. Operational Support during International Visits

With the reorganization of the Internationalization Office (IO) in August 2025—during which the office was restructured, and the Promotions and Linkages (PL) coordinators

were transferred to another unit—the need for support from SAGA student volunteers increased significantly.

From September to October 2025, SAGA volunteers assisted during the arrival of three groups of Belgian international visitors from Vives University, IVV, and CHINTA. They provided essential logistical support, including serving as campus tour guides, conducting preparatory legwork, routing communications, and delivering cultural orientation. Logistical support is extended even to the Basic Education units.

E. Tagalog Tutorial and Cultural and Ecological Orientation

SAGA volunteers conducted Filipino language tutorials and cultural and ecological orientations for two AFS students from Japan. Additionally, the volunteers facilitated cultural and communication orientations for both inbound and outbound students. Their peer-to-peer support proved particularly effective, as international students were more comfortable sharing practical concerns with fellow students rather than with faculty members. These concerns included discomfort with certain local foods, navigating local transportation, and identifying places to eat. The volunteers often served as “buddies” to foreign students, helping them adjust to campus and community life. To strengthen this role, the IO provided training for new SAGA volunteers on proper communication with foreign guests and appropriate ways to assist them, ensuring that visitors feel welcomed and at home at SMU.

F. Technical Assistance

SAGA member volunteers also provided technical assistance to Erasmus+ students during their language tests in August 2025 and October 2025.

Documentation Of Utilization

Below is the documentation of the tactical activities conducted:

Global Citizenship Program (Dec. 3, 2025)

**MARIANS BEYOND BORDERS:
JOURNEYS AND REFLECTIONS
ON GLOBAL
CITIZENSHIP**

December 3, 2025 | 7:30-11:45 a.m.
SMU Sacred Heart Center

You are invited.

0781 392 8103 | info@smu.edu.ph | www.smu.edu.ph

PROGRAM

Part I: Preliminaries
7:30-8:15 a.m. Registration
8:15-8:45 a.m. Opening Prayer and National Anthem
Welcome Message
Overview and Objectives

Part II: Marians Beyond Borders: Journeys and Reflections on Global Citizenship

8:45-9:00 a.m. **Becoming a Global Citizen: How International Exposure Strengthened My Sense of Responsibility**

9:00-9:15 a.m. **Service Across Borders: Learning to Engage with the World Through International Mobility**

9:15-9:30 a.m. **Service Across Borders: How Global Experiences Inspired Me to Give Back**

9:30-9:45 a.m. **Green Lessons from Abroad: Environmental Insights I Brought Home**

9:45-10:00 a.m. **Global Journeys, Personal Growth: How International Mobility Shapes Life and Career**

10:00-10:15 a.m. Ice-breaker

10:15-10:30 a.m. **Different Worlds, Shared Humanity: Building Intercultural Competence Abroad**

10:30-10:45 a.m. **Building a Home Away From Home: A Faculty Perspective on Supporting Inbound Students**

10:45-11:00 a.m. **New Eyes, New Methods: How International Exposure Elevated My Teaching Style**

11:00-11:15 a.m. **Being Global: Benefits, Insights, and Practical Preparation for Students and Faculty**

11:15-11:30 a.m. Awarding of Certificates
Photo-ops
Closing

c/o Student Advocates for Global Assistance (SAGA) Officers and IO

AVP
DR. MOISES ALEXANDER T. ASUNCION
Vice President for Academic Affairs

DR. CLARA M. GONZALES
Head, Internationalization Office

MR. JASFER DELA CRUZ, BSCE 4
Participant, Erasmus+ International Study
Lowest University of Applied Sciences, Belgium, Feb.12- June 26, 2024

MR. ARIEL NAIDAS, BSBA-IM 4
Participant, Hybrid Mobility in Business & Entrepreneurship and Technology & Intelligence, Passage to ASEAN, April 1-May 08, 2024

MS JOANNA CALUCAG, BSCE 3
Participant, CommTECH Camp Highlight, Creativpreneurship, Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember, Indonesia, April 21- May 2, 2025

MS. ZYNICA MUREN, BSBio 4
Participant, International Educational Trip and Immersion, Huachiew Chalermprakiet University, Thailand, July 1-Aug. 2, 2025

MR. DIEDERIK VAN GORP
International Teacher
Dutch Teacher for Project Modaga

c/o Student Advocates for Global Assistance (SAGA) Officers

MS. MIKAELA ARANTXA NUESTRO, SAB Faculty
Participant, SMU/IN8 Leadership Camp, Technopreneur Skills for Global Innovators, King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok, Thailand, July 9-16, 2025

MR. CHRISTIAN DOMINGUEZ, Faculty SHS
AFS Hosting Coordinator

DR. AIREEN SANTOS, Professional Education Head
Competitive, International Children's Literature, University of Antwerp, Belgium, June 24- July 1, 2019

DR. CLARA M. GONZALES
Head, Internationalization Office

Q and A

MR. GEROME BAUTISTA
Mr. Gerome Bautista
Project ALIE's Collaborator

MR. GEROME BAUTISTA
Master of Ceremony

- Global Citizenship Program Teaser 1 on FB: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/17aTfOqEdV/>
- Global Citizenship Program Teaser 2 on FB: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1J95FnUxQH/>

- Global Citizenship Program Teaser on FB: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/17uiYIPN9E/>
- Global Citizenship Documentation posted online: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/17sf86RzDX/>.

Operational Support during International Visits (August to November 2025)

AFS Welcome Program, Sept. 8, 2025,

Visitors from Vives University, Belgium, Sept. 30, 2025

- AFS Welcome Program: <https://smu.edu.ph/?s=AFS+Welcome+Program>
- Foreign Visitors from Vives University, Belgium: <https://smu.edu.ph/smu-and-vives-university-deepen-global-cooperation-with-two-day-partnership-talks/>

Visitors from CHINTA, Belgium (Sept. 29, 2025)

Visitors from IVV, Belgium, Oct. 2, 2025

Foreign Visitors from CHINTA, Belgium: <https://smu.edu.ph/smu-strengthens-collaboration-with-chinta-through-strategic-meeting/>
Filipino Language Tutorial

- Filipino Tutorial with AFS Exchange Students from Japan: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1N9evrLHX2/>

Cultural and Ecological Orientation

Cultural Orientation with AFS Exchange Students

Ecological Orientation with AFS Exchange Students

- Cultural Orientation: <https://www.facebook.com/share/v/1GKA4AQFqZ/>
- Ecological Orientation: <https://www.facebook.com/share/v/176JcgVwWI/>
- Courtesy Call to Local Officials: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/17B3xRbkh3/>

English Proficiency Test Technical Assistance for Erasmus+ Students

● Testimonial from Partners:
<https://www.facebook.com/share/v/19vGLssFSM/>

Feedback from Clients

Evaluation results for the Global Citizenship Program on Dec. 3, 2025, showed a mean satisfaction score of **4.5**, indicating strong participant satisfaction with the activity.

Positive feedback from international visitors was also evident in their comments on our social media posts, highlighting their favorable experience at SMU.

IPB-10**I-TUDU 2.0 Project ROOTS: Realigning Outcomes and Orientations in the Teaching System**

Vince Errol J. Lucas, Marites B. Querol, Federicia C. Calauagan, and Krizelle Nova A. Lazam

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The inclusion of Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) is one way to address the call for equality and justice. However, further study is needed on how teachers integrate IPEd into their pedagogy, with both IPs and non-IPs benefiting from the learning. This research determined the extent of IP integration evident in the instructional materials of teachers of a private educational institution, as well as the teachers' thoughts on the integration process. The study used a modified checklist to determine the extent of IPEd integration in nine general education courses and conducted a focus group discussion (FGD) with six participants who teach general education courses to verify and gather thoughts from those who teach the courses. Results reveal that across the six areas, IPEd integration is minimal. A considerable extent can be particularly observed in materials, but remains minimal in the other five areas. Indicators per area, however, vary in the extent of IPEd integration. Among the instructors' responses, seven themes emerged, each connected to one of the six areas. The findings regarding the extent of IPEd integration may be due to the factors raised by the instructors. The study proposes an IPEd Integration Framework that can be used across different tertiary-level courses.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The research team translated empirical findings into an operational manual. The activities that follow explain how the empirical results were disseminated, how stakeholders were engaged, how validation and co-creation took place, and how the institution moved from evidence to practice, beginning with the research forum in April 2025 and culminating in an institutional plan for adoption.

A. Strategic planning and coordination

The group held an initial planning session to translate dissemination milestones into operational tasks. After considering different ways to utilize the results, from another ITUDU activity to a new means, the team instead decided to start with a guide that is more appropriate and needed before further implementation of the integration: the creation of an operations manual. It included two objectives. First, the manual and framework were intended to serve as living instruments for co-creation with communities and faculty. Second, that ethical safeguards and consent protocols used during the empirical study would be preserved and strengthened during utilization.

B. Dissemination and scholarly exchange

The research team, led by the team leader, presented the empirical results at a research forum in April 2025 and subsequently shared the findings internationally through a formal presentation at Ton Duc Thang University. Those events performed two roles. One, they established scholarly credibility by exposing the empirical evidence to peer critique. Two, they opened channels for external validation and cross-institutional collaboration. Presentations were greeted with further refinements and insights on the integration plan.

C. Project Roots: Utilization Proper

The team moved deliberately to engage those most directly affected by the manual. Respondents from the empirical study and a group of designated subject-matter experts were invited to a validation process. The team coordinated each respondent and expert with the draft framework and the proposed manual, allotting time for careful review, written feedback, and focused group discussion. The experts included an external, qualitatively focused social scientist, Dr. William D. Magday Jr., who contributed significantly to the utilization and empirical data. In recognition of the time and professional input required, all participating respondents and experts received remuneration and/or a token of appreciation for their participation.

After a period of consolidation and revision informed by feedback from respondents and experts, the research team completed the final write-up of the operational manual. The manual integrates empirical evidence, practical templates, and procedural guidance, making it both a policy-oriented document and a classroom-ready tool. Its structure was intentionally clear, with step-by-step procedures, sample lesson sequences, assessment rubrics, and guidelines for ethical engagement with community partners. The manual was designed not as an abstract text but as an operational instrument that faculty and administrators could use at once.

The formal presentation of the manual to institutional leadership was a pivotal strategic activity. The manual and the accompanying empirical study were presented, discussed, and convened with the deans of the School of Teacher Education and Humanities and the School of Health and Natural Sciences. These consultative convenings were scheduled to maximize participation from academic leadership and to create a documented pathway for institutional consideration. Each dean received both a printed and an electronic copy of the manual and the empirical study so that they could consult colleagues, curriculum committees, and relevant administrators. The discussions focused on practical considerations: how the manual aligned with existing curricular priorities, its implications for faculty workload, resource requirements, and possible pilot courses for initial implementation.

Following leadership-endorsement discussions, the framework and manual were presented to a select group of General Education Course teachers. This engagement was intentionally narrow and deep rather than broad and superficial. The purpose was to secure meaningful input from those who would directly implement the manual in classroom settings. Teachers were provided with guided reading materials, facilitated discussion sessions, and exemplar lesson plans drawn from the manual. Their feedback focused on the clarity of instructions, the feasibility of assessments, student engagement strategies, and necessary adjustments to ensure alignment with the course learning outcomes. The discussions were documented and subsequently used to refine the manual's classroom procedures and sample materials.

Throughout these activities, the research team maintained a clear governance posture. Every presentation and consultation was recorded in formal minutes or written notes, and all revisions to the manual were logged with version control. Documentation included a summary of remuneration provided to respondents and experts, confirmation of materials distributed to the deans, and records of teacher consultations. This documentation created a transparent trail linking empirical findings to the manual's final text and to the institutional conversations that framed early uptake.

Strategically, the sequence of dissemination, external presentation, coordinated validation, leadership convenings, and teacher consultations achieved several outcomes. First, it established the manual's credibility by exposing it to scholarly and professional

scrutiny. Second, it ensured ethical and remunerated participation of respondents and experts, reinforcing the legitimacy of the document. Third, it created institutional touchpoints at the leadership and classroom levels, paving the way for pilot implementation and ongoing refinement. Finally, it ensured that the manual was not only evidence-based but also ready for practical application.

Documentation Of Utilization

Feedback from Clients

- This is already relevant and needed across all GECs and programs.
- Very beautiful study.

CONCERNS

- From SHANS: Teachers need further training and must be led through the integration process; they must be guided and taught how, especially in terms of teaching and drafting the GSTS syllabus. (Resolution: Integration of Indigenous Flora and Fauna; suggested initiating teacher trainings to be led by IKL Hub and IPed content experts)
- From STEH: Concerns about GECs being transferred to lower educational levels may affect the integration process.
- From faculty: content and integrated features must not overlap with GPIC (Resolution: GPIC is aimed at promoting awareness of IPs and ICCs; IPed Integration will focus on the competency while using the integration as an approach to teaching.

IPB-11**STEP UP WELLNESS: A Research-Based Brochure for Mental and Social Fitness Among HEI Dance Troupe Members**

Ronda L. Navalta, Niño N. Baldonado, Dalarry L. Duldulao, & Ronna Chiehann J. Vidal

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This research utilization initiative was conducted as an output of the previous research study, *Dance Dynamics: Unraveling Its Dual Role in Fitness and Social Interaction*. The study explored the perceived benefits of dance in promoting physical fitness and social interaction among 70 active members of dance troupes from five Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Nueva Vizcaya. Using a mixed-methods approach, the findings revealed that dance participation contributed to improved cardiovascular endurance, flexibility, coordination, and overall physical health. Social benefits included enhanced self-confidence, strengthened peer relationships, and greater emotional expression. Notably, the study found no significant correlation between age or years of experience and the perceived benefits, indicating that dance's positive impact remained consistent across diverse demographic backgrounds.

Based on these findings, the DANCE brochure was developed to address the evident need for accessible, engaging, and informative wellness materials rooted in the performing arts. The brochure was created in partnership with HEIs and local organizations to disseminate research-based insights that highlighted dance as a valuable avenue for holistic health and meaningful social engagement. This initiative served as a platform for building active networks, encouraging movement-based wellness practices, and promoting informed community involvement. By aligning research findings with practical dissemination, the project aimed to integrate dance into wellness education and outreach programs, positioning it as a powerful tool for both personal development and community building.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

To effectively disseminate the findings of *Dance Dynamics: Unraveling its Dual Role in Fitness and Social Interaction*, the DANCE brochure was developed as an accessible tool for promoting holistic wellness among student dancers. Instead of implementing physical workshops, the project focused on producing a research-informed brochure that clearly communicated the physical, emotional, social, and mental health benefits of dance participation.

To address the physical wellness dimension, the project team synthesized key findings from the original study and transformed them into clear, reader-friendly content. Infographics and brief explanations highlighted how dance enhances cardiovascular endurance, flexibility, balance, and coordination. This ensured that student dancers and faculty members could easily understand the physiological contributions of dance to overall health.

To support emotional well-being, the brochure included sections on stress management, creative expression, and confidence building. Insights from qualitative responses in the original research were incorporated to illustrate how dance contributes to emotional resilience. Content experts and guidance consultants helped ensure accuracy and relevance, making the brochure applicable to student wellness contexts.

The brochure also emphasized dance as a catalyst for social connection. Visuals and narratives demonstrated how dance fosters collaboration, peer bonding, and community engagement. This information aimed to encourage students to value teamwork and inclusivity within their respective dance organizations.

Recognizing the role of dance in mental health support, the project collaborated with guidance counselors to develop content explaining how movement can complement existing mental health initiatives. These sections provided students with practical and relatable perspectives on dance as a means of reducing anxiety and emotional strain.

To ensure the brochure's effectiveness, the project underwent a systematic process involving content development, layout design, validation, and distribution. Brochures were disseminated to the five participating HEIs, and feedback was gathered to assess the clarity, usefulness, and impact of the material. The soft copy of the **D.A.N.C.E. (Developing Active Networks and Community Engagement) Brochure** was officially disseminated through email to all participating school respondents. This ensures sustained access to the material, allowing institutions to continuously utilize the brochure as a reference for promoting holistic wellness, physical fitness, and social engagement through dance initiatives. These insights contributed to refining the final version of the brochure and strengthened the overall research utilization process.

Through these strategic activities, the project successfully transformed research findings into an informative and engaging brochure that promoted wellness, creativity, and community connection among HEI dance troupe members.

Documentation Of Utilization

Feedback from Clients

Members of the dance troupe shared that the brochure was informative, visually appealing, and easy to follow, especially in understanding the importance of mental and social fitness in their daily training and team interactions. Many appreciated how the brochure translated research findings into practical ideas that they could apply to improve their well-being, strengthen relationships within the group, and support a positive team culture. Members stated that the activity guides helped them reflect on their own experiences and encouraged open communication with their peers. However, some expressed that while the brochure provided valuable information, it would have been more helpful if certain activities included clearer instructions or demonstrations for groups with varying skill levels. Overall, the dance troupe members found the brochure useful for raising awareness of holistic wellness through dance and for strengthening their sense of connection as a performance team.

IPB-12**Re-appropriating and Recalibrating Learning Packet on Diversified Planning and Design Initiatives Towards an Enhanced Internship Program in a University**

Liberty A. Rosario, Candido Joseph T. Rosario Jr., and Rianna Joy L. Agrimor

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The study is a focal pillar aimed at societal transformation in a specific milieu, through the provision of on-site, diversified planning and design in Region 2. Formidable to the education, training, and the road to professionalism in the Civil Engineering is an ever-evolving commitment that indubitably contributes to the survival and growth of man's institutions, culture, and civilization. Hence, the enhancement intervention greatly highlights the immense partnership and collaboration, amplified and recalibrated through sustainable civil engineering tasks and responsibilities. More than ever, this study revealed the significant impact of the partnership between the private and public sectors, complementing each other to meet humanity's evolving needs. Civil engineering and other engineering programs, together with selected industry partners, play a crucial role in steering societal transformation through sustainable planning and design. Understanding the civil engineer's crucial role in promoting sustainable construction practices is becoming increasingly essential as the world faces severe environmental and economic concerns. This study highlighted the civil engineers' and other engineering completers' and graduates' pivotal role in promoting sustainable concrete construction, underscoring the need for their expertise in creating environmentally friendly and resilient infrastructure. The program has been made feasible through the cooperation of government, non-governmental, and private corporations/organizations, which were willing to share their facilities and resources. It is therefore imperative for the school to establish the necessary linkages with these corporations and organizations. The study further highlighted the importance of procurement rules in advancing sustainable development, emphasizing the need for well-crafted policies and guidelines that incentivize eco-friendly practices, as well as the procedures required during an internship. The possible collaborative efforts between civil engineers and policymakers are highlighted as a fundamental driver of sustainable planning and design in the multifaceted era.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The crafted OJT learning packet was carefully followed to ensure a smooth internship. Before the conduct of 240 hours of OJT, the OJT learning packet was provided to the students. This served as their guide as to what and how, since the OJT learning packet provided a step-by-step procedure, which included the following:

- (a.) Evaluation and enrollment were done at the Dean's office
- (b.) Orientation given by the OJT adviser in class before deployment
- (c.) Endorsement Letters submission to industry partners initiated by the OJT adviser
- (d.) Accomplishment of OJT requirements and documents per student before deployment
- (e.) Signing of the MOA in the university led by the administration with the guidance of the University legal counsel, OJT adviser, and partner industry
- (f.) Hard Hatting and Pinning ceremony highlighting the conduct of the OJT
- (g.) Deployment to various partner industries

- (h.) Internship activities in various areas of assignment are monitored by the OJT adviser and partners in the various regions and agencies.
- (i.) Submission and evaluation of portfolio by the students and interns upon completion of the 240-hour rendition of expected competencies.

The utilization of the OJT learning packet was meant to provide an outstanding education program that enables graduates to become leaders in their profession by imparting fundamental principles, skills, and tools to transform society. Further, as young people would be professional engineers, pursuing tasks to learn may not just be limited to the four walls of the classroom. Responding to the needs of an ever-evolving society may not be limited to producing plans and designs; it becomes a collaborative effort that requires partnership.

OJT can never be completed without the rigorous preparation and monitoring by the adviser, specifically for various assignment areas. There is a multiplicity of tasks and competencies to be addressed, not just at a single time, as many concerns, issues, and problems may surface.

Documentation Of Utilization

Concentrix Camp John Hay,
Baguio City April 27, 2025; May 11, 2025; May 25, 2025

DPWH, Nueva Vizcaya 1st District Engineering Office
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya
May 7, 2025; May 19, 2025; May 26, 2025

DPWH, Isabela 3rd District Engineering Office
Tagarian, Cauayan City, Isabela
Feb 5, 2025; April 2, 2025; May 14, 2025

DPWH, Isabela 4th District Engineering Office
San Isidro, Isabela
Jan 27, 2025; March 5, 2025; April 30, 2025

DPWH, Nueva Vizcaya 2nd District Engineering Office
Dupax del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya
April 17, 2025; April 25, 2025; May 9, 2025

NIA-Nueva Vizcaya IMO
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya
May 7, 2025; May 19 & 26, 2025

NIA, Quirino IMO
Dibul, Saguday, Quirino
April 21, 2025; May 14, 2025; June 3, 2025

DPWH Quirino District Engineering Office
Cabbaroguis, Quirino
Feb 24, 2025; March 27, 2025; May 8, 2025

DPWH Regional Satellite Materials Testing Laboratory
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya
Feb 10, 2025; March 17, 2025; April 28, 2025

Mamuric TV Station
Solano, Nueva Vizcaya
May 20, 2025

Feedback from Clients

The clients in the diverse learning activities during the internship were very satisfied, as engaging collaboration and partnerships were forged. Mutual support was widely experienced among both clients and beneficiaries during the various immersion activities.

Moreover, heightened connection and collaboration were strongly felt among the various stakeholders, both from the university and industry partners, where the students were deployed. In terms of satisfaction, they were so grateful for the constant support throughout their immersion.

IPB-13**PROJECT B2B: Building Sustainable Campuses From Bins To Behavior**

Regina D. Ramel, John Lindy R. Soriano, Jeanette R. Mania, and Jeniviv V. Pascual (COA)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study examines the challenges encountered by private higher education institutions in Nueva Vizcaya in implementing effective solid waste management programs in compliance with RA 9003. Key findings reveal that while both HEIs exhibit organized systems, gaps persist in awareness, pro-environmental intentions, infrastructure, and behavioral adherence among students and faculty. Faculty across both institutions generally show higher levels of awareness than students, with SMU faculty demonstrating environmentalist attitudes and students exhibiting pre-environmentalist behaviors. Common issues such as improper waste segregation, insufficient disposal facilities, and a lack of active participation hinder recycling efficiency and contribute to environmental degradation. Cultural attitudes and poor adherence to policies, including CLAYGO, exacerbate these problems. Recommendations include enhancing awareness campaigns, improving waste treatment and recycling systems, addressing behavioral gaps through education, upgrading infrastructure, and fostering community engagement. By addressing these challenges, both HEIs can align practices with RA 9003, cultivate a culture of environmental stewardship, and contribute to long-term sustainability.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The B2B Project operationalized the study's findings by translating behavioral and institutional gaps into structured interventions. The findings of this research were presented during the 12th HCU National and International Conference at Huachiew Chalermprakiet University in Thailand last July 30-31, 2025.

Locally, the research team began crafting the design of the eco-reminder kits, which will be presented during the Eco-Lecture series. The lecture was held during the student general assembly at Saint Mary's University to reach a large audience. It addressed awareness deficits identified among students, particularly concerning RA 9003 provisions and campus policy compliance. The "Bins to Behavior" campaign directly responded to observed inconsistencies in segregation practices by incorporating visual nudges and behavioral cues grounded in environmental psychology.

Recommendations on policy, mapping, and redesigning bin placements are forwarded to the SPCO to address the logistical inefficiencies noted during the research, particularly in high-traffic areas where improper disposal was prevalent.

The integration of educational, behavioral, and infrastructural interventions demonstrates a research-to-action model that strengthens institutional compliance and cultivates a sustainability-oriented campus culture.

Based on the results, the following are recommended:

- Institutionalize periodic eco-lectures per semester. (may be integrated in NSTP classes)
- Integrate waste management modules in General Education subjects or NSTP courses.

- Develop behavioral nudging strategies near waste stations.
- Conduct longitudinal follow-up testing to measure retention.
- Combine knowledge tests with observational compliance audits (as an added area in IQA).

These findings reinforce the premise that sustainable campuses are achieved not merely through physical waste infrastructure, but through consistent behavioral education and shared accountability among waste management actors.

Documentation Of Utilization

Eco-Lecture

Eco-Lecture Reminder Kits

Pins

Poster

ZERO WASTE

UNDERSTANDING OUR 4 BINS

WHY WASTE MANAGEMENT IS MANDATORY

THE LAW
RA 9003: The Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000
 RA 9003 is the law that sets the standard for proper waste management in the Philippines. It is not just a guideline... it is a call to action for every student, faculty, and staff member to take responsibility for their waste.

KEY POLICIES

- Mandatory Waste Segregation
- Promotion of recycling and composting
- Equal shipment of Materials Recovery Facilities (MRF)
- Prohibition of littering and open burning
- Reduction of Waste Generation through Resource Efficient Practices

NON BIODEGRADABLE

ITEMS THAT DO NOT DECOMPOSE EASILY.

- candy wrappers
- sachets chip bags
- styrofoam
- Laminated paper
- disposable utensils
- broken ceramics
- plastics

RECYCLABLE

WASTE THAT CAN BE PROCESSED INTO NEW MATERIALS.

- Plastic bottles (PET)
- caps containers
- cardboard
- glass bottles
- aluminum cans
- tin cans

BIODEGRADABLE

WASTE THAT DECOMPOSE NATURALLY

- small twigs
- leaves
- used paper plates
- tissue napkins
- paper towels
- food scraps

HAZARDOUS

WASTE THAT POSES HEALTH OR SAFETY RISKS.

- Batteries
- chemicals
- Sharp Objects
- used face masks
- Laboratory Chemicals
- medical wastes

Segregation begins with understanding what goes where.

STOP THE DRAIN

COMMON PRACTICES THAT CAUSE DEGRADATION

- Improper Waste Segregation
- Ignoring mark bins
- Lack of Active Participation
- use of Non-eco friendly products
- Lack of self-discipline

LIVING THE CHSF ENVIRONMENT

1 CLEAN, SAFE, HEALTHY, FRIENDLY - OUR COLLECTIVE EFFORT MAKES THIS HAPPEN!

- Keep surroundings free from clutter
- Maintain safe walkways - no scattered trash
- Practice a healthy and consistent fire response
- Show friendliness through responsible behavior

2 CLAYGO - CLEAN AS YOU GO

- Always clean your table before leaving
- Dispose of trash in correct bins
- Leave no trash in classrooms, corridors, study areas

3 REDUCE YOUR CARBOON FOOTPRINT

- Bring your own reusable water bottle
- Support recycling programs and environmental needs
- Encourage others to follow proper segregation
- Reduce energy usage or equipment use to conserve resources
- Minimize food waste by buying only what you can finish

THE STANDARD

BINFLUENCE

Building a SUSTAINABLE CAMPUS

Wanted Way to Waste Excellence

Remember:
 A clean campus starts with your hands. Segregate properly, protect our environment, and build a sustainable future.

Stickers

Eco-Reminder Dissemination

Feedback from Clients

A paired-samples t-test revealed a statistically significant increase in knowledge scores from pre-test ($M = 9.26$, $SD = 1.04$) to post-test ($M = 9.65$, $SD = 0.56$), $t(95) = -3.25$, $p < .01$. The effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.40$) indicates a small-to-moderate practical impact of the eco-lecture intervention.

To determine the effectiveness of the eco-lecture intervention, a pre-test and post-test design was employed, focusing on 10 knowledge-based items related to solid waste management principles, RA 9003, segregation categories, and campus sustainability practices.

The pre-test results ($n = 246$) showed a high baseline level of knowledge ($M = 9.26$, $SD = 1.04$) out of a maximum score of 10. This indicates that students already possessed a substantial understanding of basic waste management concepts before the intervention.

The post-test results ($n = 96$ matched responses) demonstrated an increase in knowledge scores ($M = 9.65$, $SD = 0.56$). The reduction in standard deviation suggests that knowledge levels became more consistent among participants after the lecture.

The mean gain score was 0.38 points. This indicates that the eco-lecture produced a measurable improvement in student knowledge regarding sustainable solid waste management practices.

The computed effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.40$) suggests a small-to-moderate practical effect. Considering the already high baseline mean score (above 9.0), the observed improvement is educationally meaningful despite limited room for further improvement.

The high pre-test mean indicates that students were already generally aware of waste categories and basic environmental principles. This may be attributed to:

- Existing CHSF initiatives
- Campus waste labeling systems
- Prior exposure to environmental education
- Institutional culture promoting cleanliness

However, high awareness does not necessarily translate into consistent behavioral compliance, a recurring theme in earlier qualitative findings of the study.

Despite strong baseline knowledge, the lecture significantly enhanced:

- Conceptual clarity (e.g., RA 9003 scope)
- Proper classification of waste categories
- Understanding of shared responsibility
- Systemic perspective of the waste chain

The decrease in variability (SD from 1.04 to 0.56) indicates that the intervention helped align participants toward a more uniform understanding of sustainable waste management.

Thematic analysis of post-test commitments revealed that the majority of participants ($n = 46$) pledged to practice proper waste segregation, indicating that the intervention effectively reinforced behavioral compliance at the source level. A smaller subset emphasized personal responsibility ($n = 14$), suggesting internalization of accountability. However, limited responses addressed waste reduction ($n = 3$) and environmental advocacy ($n = 1$), implying that sustainability behaviors are still largely framed within segregation practices rather than broader systemic engagement. These findings support the study's assertion that sustainable campus initiatives must evolve from bin-based compliance toward holistic behavioral transformation.

Overall, this supports the study's central thesis: ***Sustainability requires not only infrastructure (bins) but behavioral alignment across actors in the waste chain.***
Institutional Policy-Oriented Studies (IPOS)

IPOS-01**From Classroom to Career: Evaluating the Employability of SAB Graduates***Regina D. Ramel***EXECUTIVE SUMMARY**

This study explores the employability of graduates from Saint Mary's University's School of Accountancy and Business (SAB) and examines how well academic programs prepare students for professional success. Based on survey responses from 39 graduates, findings show that most are employed locally, while others pursue further studies, work abroad, or run their own businesses. Graduates have secured international roles in management, hospitality, and education, demonstrating the versatility and global relevance of their training. A majority found employment within three months of graduation, suggesting strong job-market readiness. Graduates identified problem-solving, communication, and critical thinking as the most valuable skills in their current roles. Feedback also highlighted areas for curriculum improvement, including more practical learning, industry exposure, and integration of tools such as QuickBooks and SAP. Suggestions included focusing on major subjects, reducing non-essential courses, and offering internships outside the province. These insights support educational theories emphasizing experiential learning (Kolb, 1984) and the integration of 21st-century skills (Trilling & Fadel, 2009; Voogt & Roblin, 2012). The study concludes that SAB's programs effectively prepare students for diverse career paths, but ongoing curriculum enhancements are essential to meet evolving industry demands and support long-term career success.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Based on the comprehensive data collected, it is evident that the degree programs at Saint Mary's University, School of Accountancy and Business (SAB), are effective in preparing graduates for diverse career paths. Most graduates are locally employed, with a significant portion pursuing further studies, reflecting strong employability and a commitment to continuous learning. The curriculum's emphasis on 21st-century skills, such as problem-solving, communication, and critical thinking, has proven beneficial in graduates' current jobs. However, there are areas for improvement, including enhancing practical learning experiences, increasing exposure to industry practices, and integrating more hands-on activities. Graduates also suggested focusing on major subjects, reducing non-essential courses, and offering more internships and CPA professors. Addressing these recommendations can further enhance the curriculum's effectiveness, ensuring that graduates are well-prepared for the demands of the modern workforce and capable of achieving long-term career success. Continuous curriculum improvements, aligned with industry needs and educational best practices, will support graduates' professional growth and adaptability in a globalized economy.

IPOS-02**Curriculum Insights: Accountancy and Business Graduates' Perspectives on Skill Development and Program Effectiveness**

Regina D. Ramel

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study examines the effectiveness of the degree programs at Saint Mary's University, School of Accountancy and Business (SAB), in developing graduates' 21st-century skills, personal attributes, and satisfaction with curriculum implementation. A mixed-methods approach was used to gather data from January 2025 graduates through surveys and interviews. Results show high ratings in life and career skills, problem-solving, and information literacy, alongside strong development in character and responsible citizenship. Graduates expressed satisfaction with administrative support, practical experiences, and classroom atmosphere. Internships, teaching style, and integrated board exam reviews were the most appreciated elements. However, concerns were raised about the retention policy, inconsistent teaching quality, and the overly theoretical nature of some subjects. Graduates recommended more hands-on learning, real-world case studies, and the inclusion of emerging topics such as artificial intelligence and data analytics. These findings align with Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory, Trilling and Fadel's (2009) emphasis on supportive and relevant instruction, and Voogt and Roblin's (2012) call to integrate 21st-century skills into curricula. The study concludes that SAB's programs are well-rounded and effective in preparing graduates for diverse career paths. Still, continuous curriculum enhancement is essential to maintain relevance and improve student outcomes in a rapidly evolving professional landscape.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The study's findings indicate that the degree programs at Saint Mary's University, School of Accountancy and Business (SAB), effectively develop graduates' 21st-century skills and attributes, and that graduates are highly satisfied with the curriculum implementation. Graduates reported high mean scores in life and career skills, problem-solving, and information literacy, reflecting the curriculum's success in fostering critical competencies. Additionally, the programs were praised for instilling character and responsible citizenship, essential for professional and civic life. Satisfaction with administrative support, practical experiences, and classroom atmosphere further underscores the curriculum's effectiveness. However, areas for improvement include addressing the cut-off policy, enhancing teaching quality, and increasing experiential learning opportunities. Incorporating courses on artificial intelligence and data analytics could also better prepare students for the digital age. Overall, the SAB curriculum is well-rounded and effective, but continuous improvement is necessary to maintain and enhance these positive outcomes.

IPOS-03**Information Technology (IT) Students' Perspective on Artificial Intelligence: A Boon or a Bane?**

Gertrude G. Danao

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Artificial intelligence (AI) is being utilized to provide numerous benefits. AI is widely used in education, e-business, e-commerce, healthcare, and more. AI, though new, is becoming increasingly popular because of the advantages it offers individuals. Consequently, the research respondents are IT students who are familiar with AI. The objective of this study is to determine IT students' perspectives, specifically whether they regard AI as a boon or a bane. This study used an AI-generated questionnaire to determine IT students' opinions on the positive and negative impacts, the most used AI tools or applications, their fears and concerns, and perceived challenges. This study used descriptive statistics to analyze the collected data. The results revealed that IT students are aware that AI has both positive and negative impacts. The positive impacts include improved efficiency, automation, and better processes and outputs. Its negative impacts include security, privacy, and ethical implications. Similarly, IT students perceive that AI will result in job displacement and misuse. With these findings, the researcher recommends that AI be used responsibly and that its perceived negative impacts be studied to determine whether the identified concerns about its utilization are valid, so that its impact can be lessened.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are derived:

1. Most of the IT students perceive AI technology as a boon.
2. The most widely used applications among IT students are virtual assistants, chatbots, and recommendation systems.
3. Although the respondents are still in college, most fear that AI will lead to job displacement. Moreover, they have concerns about the misuse of AI and its ethical implications.
4. The perceived challenges for IT students in AI include ethical considerations, security, and privacy.

IPOS-04**Gender Responsiveness Of The Community Development Center Of A Private Catholic Educational Institution In The Philippines**

Christopher Allen S. Marquez, Elvira G. Tongson, and Marnuela Q. Dela Cruz

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the Sustainable Development Goals is gender equality. This goal aims to ensure that women are not left behind in all aspects of development. To realize this, government units and academic institutions have incorporated gender and development into their programs, projects, and activities. This paper analyzed the gender responsiveness of the LMCDAC, the extension arm of Saint Mary's University, and found that it is still at the foundation-building stage. The Center has promising prospects for GAD in terms of project identification and design. However, it is invisible in the project implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. Results served as a basis for revising and enhancing the policies, guidelines, and ISO-controlled forms. It is recommended that these forms be used by both employees and student extensionists in their community development activities.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

1. The degree of gender mainstreaming at LMCDAC is still at the Foundation Formation level, indicating that the Center is still at the stage of raising staff and extensionists' awareness of gender and development to generate support for gender mainstreaming.
2. The project identification and design stage of LMCDAC, on the one hand, had promising gender and development prospects. This indicates that the Center had been involved in the search for viable development initiatives aimed at addressing the issues and problems identified by partner communities or schools. On the other hand, gender and development were invisible during the project management and implementation stages. This was due to the failure to report the actual number of respondents by gender and population categories, including the analysis of these categories.
3. The Manual of Operations and Guidelines of the *Lingkod Maria* Community Development and Advocacy Center has been revised to enhance its vision, mission, goals and objectives, and policies and guidelines. It clearly emphasized gender and other population characteristics. The different ISO-Controlled Forms were also revised to account for these population characteristics.

IPOS-05**Mind the Waste: Assessing Awareness and Attitudes Towards Solid Waste Management Among University Students**

Shenna Mae B. Decoro & Elsa L. Cajucom

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study aimed to assess college students' awareness, attitudes, and practices regarding solid waste management (SWM) at a private Catholic university in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The research sought to determine the relationships among students' awareness, attitudes, and practices regarding SWM and to explore factors influencing their engagement in environmental sustainability efforts. A quantitative descriptive-correlational design was employed. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to students from six academic units: the School of Health and Natural Sciences (SHaNS), School of Teacher Education and Humanities (STEH), School of Graduate Studies (SGS), School of Accountancy and Business (SAB), School of Engineering, Architecture, and Information Technology (SEAIT), and the College of Law (CoL). Descriptive statistics and Pearson's correlation analysis were used to interpret the data. The findings revealed that students demonstrated moderate to high awareness and very positive attitudes toward SWM. Notably, SHaNS students scored the highest across all domains. However, a gap was observed between awareness and self-reported practices, indicating that knowledge and attitudes do not consistently translate into sustainable behavior. Correlational analysis showed strong positive relationships between awareness and attitudes ($r = 0.60$), awareness and practices ($r = 0.45$), and a moderate correlation between attitudes and practices ($r = 0.35$). The study concludes that there is a need for stronger institutional support, including more accessible waste management infrastructure, regular awareness campaigns, and experiential learning opportunities to bridge the gap between knowledge and practice. Recommendations include integrating environmental education across all academic disciplines, fostering student-led sustainability initiatives, and refining teaching methods to ensure a comprehensive approach to SWM across the university.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The study reveals that college students at a private Catholic university generally exhibit moderate to high awareness of solid waste management (SWM), frequently engage in SWM practices, and maintain very positive attitudes toward environmental sustainability. Students from the School of Health and Natural Sciences (SHaNS) achieved the highest scores across all three domains—awareness, attitude, and practice—indicating the positive impact of integrating environmental topics into the curriculum. Despite a shared understanding of SWM's importance, variability in SWM practices indicates a gap between knowledge and actual behavior. Pearson's correlation analysis supports the notion that awareness is positively correlated with both attitudes and practices, and attitudes, in turn, influence SWM behaviors. These results align with the Knowledge-Attitude-Practice (KAP) Model, which highlights that awareness alone does not guarantee behavioral change. Factors such as the accessibility of disposal facilities and personal habits may play significant roles in shaping behavior, underscoring the need for consistent reinforcement of SWM practices.

The study recommends that policy implementation on SWM in the CHSF Program be strengthened, a clear and accessible waste management infrastructure be provided, and compliance across departments be ensured to enhance the university's solid waste

management (SWM). Environmental education should be integrated into the general curriculum for all students, supplemented by experiential activities like clean-up drives and recycling projects. Regular awareness campaigns, training on segregation and recycling, compliance with Republic Act 9003, and the mobilization of student organizations will reinforce these efforts. The university should also conduct regular assessments of students' SWM knowledge, attitudes, and practices, and support student-led sustainability initiatives to bridge the gap between knowledge and practice. Finally, environmental education should be tailored to specific academic programs, and faculty should integrate sustainability concepts into their teaching methods to foster a more sustainable campus culture.

IPOS-06**Development of Environment and Christian Values-Oriented Chemistry Modules (ECCM) for Junior High School Special Science Program Learners**

Elsa L. Cajucom

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study developed and evaluated Environment and Christian Values-Oriented Chemistry Modules (ECCM) to integrate chemistry concepts with environmental principles and Christian values for learners in the Junior High School Special Science Program. The general objective was to create and validate the ECCM using the ADDIE instructional design model. Specific objectives included determining the feasibility of integrating environmental principles and Christian values in teaching chemistry, identifying the modules' instructional characteristics, and validating the ECCM regarding acceptability (content validity, format, presentation, accuracy) and usability (functionality). The study employed a Research and Development (R&D) design guided by the ADDIE model. Purposive sampling was used to select five chemistry experts to evaluate the modules. The modules integrated environmental principles such as "Everything must go somewhere," "Nature Knows Best," "Ours is a Finite Earth," and "Everything Changes" with corresponding Christian values. Two instruments were used: the DepEd Quality Assurance Tool and a Functionality Assessment Tool. Expert evaluations rated the modules as "Very Satisfactory" across content, format, presentation, accuracy, and functionality. The modules were deemed developmentally appropriate, scientifically accurate, well-structured, and effective in promoting cognitive and moral development. The integration of real-world environmental issues and biblical teachings was found to provide a meaningful and holistic learning experience. The study suggests pilot-testing classroom modules, gathering student feedback, enhancing visuals and language clarity, and developing digital versions to further improve the ECCM.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

This study successfully developed and evaluated the Environment and Christian Values-Oriented Chemistry Modules (ECCM), designed to integrate core Chemistry concepts with environmental principles and Christian values. Expert evaluations rated the modules as "Very Satisfactory" across content, format, presentation, accuracy, and functionality. The ECCM were deemed developmentally appropriate, scientifically accurate, and effective in fostering both cognitive growth and moral development. By connecting real-world environmental issues with biblical teachings, the modules offer a holistic and meaningful learning experience, particularly well-suited for faith-based educational settings.

However, the study was limited to expert review, and areas for enhancement—such as sentence structure and visual design—were identified. To further strengthen the modules, classroom pilot testing is recommended to evaluate their impact on student learning and engagement. The ECCM framework holds promise for application in other science subjects, supporting a broader movement toward values-integrated education. Overall, the ECCM serves as a compelling model for blending scientific literacy with ethical and spiritual development, offering a relevant, values-centered approach to Chemistry education.

IPOS-07**Safeguarding Campus Water: A Preliminary Assessment of Microplastics and Microbial Pollution in SMU Groundwater System**

Elsa L. Cajucom, Michael S. Catacutan, Regidor L. Almendral, Vincent Carlo C. Boniol, David M. Gayadang, Arcelle Mae Pablo, Hannah Mae Q. Lim, Leana B. Alap, Aila Laurice C. Panganiban, Gregg Austine M. Balanag, and Lady Fatima C. Reganit

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Access to clean groundwater is vital for health and sustainability, particularly in academic institutions like Saint Mary's University (SMU) in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. This preliminary study assessed microbial and microplastic contamination in SMU's groundwater to support sustainable campus operations aligned with UI GreenMetric standards and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Water samples from multiple locations across SMU's Main Campus, Junior High School, and Grade School departments were analyzed using microbial culture methods and density separation for microplastics. Microbial analysis revealed no detectable coliform contamination, with all samples recording <1.8 CFU/100 mL—well within safety limits set by national health standards. These results indicate the groundwater is microbiologically safe for human use. The microplastic assessment identified low-density granular sediments but no fibers or colored fragments characteristic of synthetic plastics. This suggests limited current microplastic contamination, although definitive identification requires advanced analytical techniques. The findings affirm that SMU's water sources are safe and reflect positively on existing waste management and water infrastructure policies. The study highlights opportunities to strengthen sustainability efforts, such as promoting reusable water containers, phasing out bottled water sales, and integrating water stewardship education. Continuous monitoring and advanced testing are recommended to detect emerging risks and safeguard long-term water quality. This research provides baseline data for water resource management and policy development within educational settings. It offers a replicable model for other institutions seeking to enhance environmental resilience and protect health.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

This preliminary assessment of Saint Mary's University (SMU) groundwater quality revealed two important findings: (1) all tested water sources across the main campus, Junior High School, and Grade School demonstrated microbial levels well below national detection thresholds, and (2) minimal presence of low-density granular sediments with no conclusive microplastic characteristics was detected, indicating negligible microplastic contamination at present.

The absence of fecal coliforms and the low microbial counts affirm the current safety of groundwater for human consumption. This validates the university's ongoing infrastructure maintenance and suggests that existing sanitation measures are effective. Moreover, while the presence of low-density sediments warrants further investigation using advanced microplastic detection techniques, the lack of identifiable synthetic fibers or colored fragments suggests that current risks from microplastic contamination are low.

These findings have several key implications:

1. Support for Sustainable Practices

SMU's shift toward tap water as a safe and sustainable alternative to bottled water. This aligns with its commitments to the UI Green Metric rankings and UN SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

2. CHSF Policy Reinforcement and Expansion

Safe water quality provides a solid foundation for enforcing plastic waste reduction policies across all departments. SMU can confidently implement more aggressive strategies such as eliminating bottled water sales, increasing the number of refill stations, and promoting reusable containers.

3. Educational and Engagement Opportunities

While current contamination levels are low, the potential for future risks—especially from increased urbanization and land-use changes—demands periodic water testing. This should include advanced microplastic detection and microbial surveillance to ensure ongoing safety.

4. Replication for Broader Impact

SMU's methodical approach and results can serve as a model for other institutions across the region. Establishing a standardized protocol for water quality assessment and sustainable policy integration may help improve campus environments nationwide.

IPOS-08**From Insights to Action: Policy Recommendations Based on Learner Satisfaction and Net Promoter Score Analysis**

Harrison T. Villanueva & Pearl Via S. Coballes

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Conducting satisfaction surveys is an effective measure of quality service, helping understand and improve services and the overall learner experience. This study assessed learner satisfaction with key university services and the overall learning experience, while identifying related issues, concerns, and recommendations. It used a concurrent triangulation mixed methods research design. Findings revealed that, while learners were generally satisfied with university services, satisfaction levels varied significantly across schools and indicators. Career preparation received the highest ratings, whereas campus facilities and equipment consistently ranked lowest across both university services and learning experience domains. Notably, learners from the School of Graduate Studies and the Grade School reported higher overall satisfaction and promoter scores than learners from other schools. Sources of dissatisfaction were problems with campus infrastructure (Wi-Fi, ventilation, restrooms), teacher behavior, and learner well-being issues such as academic pressure and mental health. Additional concerns included financial burdens, laboratory issues, and campus logistics. These findings underscore the need for holistic improvements across all university operations, prioritizing infrastructure upgrades, enhancing teaching quality, strengthening learner support initiatives, and addressing specific financial and logistical concerns to foster a more conducive and supportive learning environment.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

1. University learners are generally satisfied with key services, with variations in learning experience satisfaction across indicators and schools. Career preparation received the highest ratings, and campus facilities and equipment received the lowest. The Graduate School and Grade School learners reported higher satisfaction than others.
2. There is uneven experience among learners across the schools, with learner loyalty and advocacy being highest in the grade and graduate school and lowest among the undergraduate schools.
3. Systemic issues concerning campus infrastructure (Wi-Fi, ventilation, restrooms), teacher conduct, and learner well-being (academic pressure, mental health) are the primary drivers of learner dissatisfaction across the university, with additional concerns regarding financial burdens, specific labs, and campus facilities.

IPOS-09**Pre-Feasibility Study Of Offering News Programs At Saint Mary's University Based On Student Preferences**

Clara M. Gonzales, Madonna A. Blando, Mark Noren U. de Vera, Monaloufel Rosario F. Jasmin, Rocel Audrey J. Batara, Martin Gabriel T. Manuel, & Nicole Anne P. Aquino

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As part of Saint Mary's University's ongoing commitment to fostering academic excellence and innovation, the Promotions, External Relations, and Internationalization Office (PERIO) conducted a pre-feasibility survey to assess the feasibility of offering new programs at SMU based on students' course preferences. The survey aimed to gather valuable insights from senior high school students and identify student interests and preferences for new academic programs that SMU may offer in the coming school years. By understanding our students' evolving aspirations and proactively responding to emerging global trends, we can ensure our curriculum remains relevant, inclusive, and future-focused.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The survey results highlight key insights into Grade 12 students' preferences for their future academic and career paths. The majority of respondents are from Nueva Vizcaya, with a high representation of STEM students.

Based on the survey, the top five most popular program offerings among senior high school students from SMU's feeder schools are BS Tourism Management – Cabin Crew, BS Hospitality Management – Cruise Ship, BS Mechanical Engineering, BS Dentistry, and BS Interior Design. SAB, SEAIT, and SHANS have proposed these programs.

Specifically, the top four preferred course programs that SAB may offer are: BS in Tourism Management – Cabin Crew, BS Hospitality Management – Cruise Ship, BS in Business Economics, and BS in Accounting Information Systems.

The top four preferred course programs that SEAIT may offer are: BS in Mechanical Engineering, BS in Interior Design/Fine Arts, BS in Geodetic Engineering, and Associate in Computer Technology.

The top three preferred course programs that SHANS may offer are the following: BS in Dentistry, BS in Radiologic Technology, BS in Midwifery, and BS in Nutrition and Dietetics.

The ranking of the two proposed programs from STEH is as follows: Bachelor of Culture and Arts Education, followed by Bachelor of Performing Arts.

Many students prefer practical and in-demand courses such as Nursing, Engineering, and Criminology. Additionally, economic factors influence decision-making, with a significant portion of students coming from lower-income households.

Based on the survey results, it is recommended that SMU focus on highlighting the quality of its education to justify the high cost of tuition, which is the top reason respondents would not choose SMU. Highlight the facilities, laboratories, equipment, and board exam passing rates as manifestations of excellence. Also, it can present a

comparison of tuition fees from other private universities to provide a more realistic baseline.

These findings can serve as a guide for SMU's academic units in planning relevant course offerings for the upcoming school year.

IPOS-10**Exploring the Career Wellness of Marian Students through the Career Wellness and Inventory Test (CaWIT)**

Richelle D. Francisco, Edwin Edilberto N. Mania, Meca Jade M. Corpuz, Leslie Doris M. Divina, May Juliet S. Palina, Jennifer Ann M. Torres, Florizza Lorraine B. Galamay, Marc Gail M. Cornejo, Deophile Jeffnorson A. Magday, Berlyn B. Pihulon, & Bryant M. Soliven.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The transition into higher education presents multifaceted challenges for students, especially upper-level students, who must navigate academic demands, personal growth, and future career planning. To support this, the Career Wellness Inventory Test (CaWIT) was administered as a mandatory pre-enrollment assessment for 2nd- to 4th/5th-year students. This study analyzed the first-semester results of A.Y. 2024–2025 to identify key indicators of student well-being, academic performance, and career readiness. Findings revealed a significant association between academic failure and mental health concerns, as well as a lack of career clarity. Consistent with prior research, wellness was shown to be a multidimensional construct influenced by individual, academic, and institutional factors. Recommendations include expanding personalized support systems, integrating well-being into curricula, and increasing the accessibility of mental health services. CaWIT proves to be a valuable tool for early detection and intervention, aligning with the university's mission to foster a resilient and successful student body.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Based on the results and discussions, the following are concluded:

1. **Under-participation:** The overall 74% response rate, particularly the 47% in SEAIT, indicates that a significant portion of the student body's well-being and academic status remains unknown, directly undermining the CaWIT's goals.
2. **Teacher-Student Relationship as a Factor:** The consistent emergence of the "teacher factor" as a common reason for academic failure across SAB, STEH, and SHANS suggests a systemic issue that warrants further investigation into pedagogical practices and instructor-student dynamics.
3. **Alarming Mental Health Concerns:** The presence of students at risk of self-harming across all schools, with SHANS showing the highest percentage, is a severe concern requiring immediate and proactive mental health support strategies.
4. **"Surviving" Mental Health:** While the majority of students across schools report their mental health status as "surviving," this term itself suggests a state of coping rather than thriving, indicating a need for broader wellness initiatives beyond addressing immediate crises.

IPOS-11**Understanding Student Attrition at SMU: A Three-Year Review of Trends and Reasons**

Richelle D. Francisco, Edwin Edilberto N. Mania, Meca Jade M. Corpuz, Leslie Doris M. Divina, May Juliet S. Palina, Jennifer Ann M. Torres, Florizza Lorraine B. Galamay, Marc Gail M. Cornejo, Deophile Jeffnorson A. Magday, Berlyn B. Pihulon, & Bryant M. Soliven

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The study presents the attrition data of SMU students from Academic Year (A.Y.) 2022–2023 to A.Y. 2024–2025. The data is based on the results of the Transfer-Out Survey administered by the Guidance and Testing Office (GTO) to students who transferred out of the university. It evaluates the reasons students chose to leave the institution. The data highlights a year-on-year increase in the number of transferees, with the School of Health and Natural Sciences (SHANS)—particularly the BS Nursing program—consistently recording the highest attrition rates. By year level, the majority of transferees were first-year students. Academic concerns, especially failed grades, were among the most frequently cited reasons for leaving. These issues often pointed to challenges in the student-teacher relationship, which significantly influenced students' decisions to discontinue their studies at the university. At the same time, some students expressed appreciation for how the university met their needs; several offered recommendations for improvement. These included evaluating instructors, hiring additional faculty for certain programs, reducing tuition fees, and regularly assessing students' well-being.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

Based on the results and discussions, the following are concluded:

1. The attrition rate at SMU has increased from Academic Year (A.Y.) 2022–2023 to A.Y. 2024–2025. Among the departments, the School of Health and Natural Sciences (SHANS) consistently recorded the highest number of student transfers. Notably, the BS Nursing program exhibited the highest student attrition rate across all departments and academic years. Additionally, first-year students had the highest attrition rate, indicating a critical period for student retention efforts.
2. Over the past three academic years, failed grades have consistently been the most common reason for student transfers across various departments. For SAB, BS Accountancy had the highest number of transferees, while the distance between school and home was the most common reason for transfer. For SEAIT, the BS Civil Engineering program had the highest number of students who transferred out with Failed Grades as the common reason. For the SHANS, the majority of transferees are from BS Nursing, and the most common reason is failure. For the STEH, most of the transferees are from BS Criminology, and shifting to a course not offered at SMU was the most common reason.
3. Students' recommendations reveal a strong desire for improvements not only in academic quality and faculty professionalism but also in areas that affect their overall well-being, including mental health support, financial assistance, inclusivity, and campus infrastructure.

IPOS-12**Assessing and Refining the Policy on Responsible AI Use in Research, Instruction, and Extension: A Collaborative Approach**

Melanie G. Gurat, Ivonny Lorvin M. Adducul, John Octavious S. Palina, John G. Tayaban, Ma. Nympha B. Joaquin, & Crist John M. Pastor

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study explored the types of generative AI tools used, their applications, responsible use, and their impact on learning and critical thinking. A mixed-methods approach was employed, collecting data from faculty and students using researcher-designed Likert-scale questionnaires. Existing AI policies from participating universities were also reviewed. Results showed that both students and faculty had used generative AI tools, with ChatGPT (OpenAI) being the most popular. However, AI integration in academic activities remained limited. Respondents demonstrated awareness of ethical use, but there was still a need to protect academic integrity and ensure equitable access. AI moderately supported learning and critical thinking, but worked best when used alongside traditional methods. Many universities already had AI policies, underscoring the need for Saint Mary's University to craft its own clear, accessible policy. Based on the university's Catholic values, a proposed AI policy with nine key sections was developed to promote ethical growth, innovation, and responsible use. The study recommended adopting this policy to guide fair and ethical AI use, maintain academic standards, support genuine learning, and provide regular training and updates.

THE UTILIZATION COMPONENT

The AI policy underwent multiple rounds of review and refinement throughout its implementation. The research team first reviewed the draft policy and made initial revisions before submitting it to key collaborators and administrators for expert feedback. The University President and Vice President for Administration, along with other institutional leaders, provided initial recommendations to ensure that the policy addressed practical and institutional considerations.

The Deans then reviewed the policy to assess its alignment with academic programs and institutional values. Following this, it was disseminated to Department Heads, who evaluated its relevance within their instructional contexts and disciplines. The policy was further deliberated during the Dean's Council meeting, where participants examined its strengths, possible implementation challenges, and areas for improvement. During the RCDC meeting, participants also suggested potential applications of AI in student research, extension projects, and administrative processes, which were incorporated into the revised draft.

All feedback gathered from these consultations was consolidated and integrated into the policy through a series of revisions. The revised document was then submitted for university-wide evaluation, allowing various administrative units and stakeholders to further examine its clarity, feasibility, and ethical considerations.

At present, the policy is undergoing the **final review by stakeholders before formal signing and institutional adoption**. Heads of offices, deans, administrators, and other key stakeholders are carefully reviewing the final version to ensure that it fully aligns with Saint Mary's University's institutional values and operational requirements. Since this is an institutional policy, the approval process requires formal confirmation from

multiple offices. As of this writing, several stakeholders have already signified their support by attaching their signatures to the policy document, while the remaining signatories are completing their final review. Once all required signatures are obtained, the policy will proceed to its official approval and implementation across all academic and operational areas of the University.

Documentation Of Utilization

Letters requesting review and approval were sent to heads of offices, deans, and administrators. Each recipient was given a copy of the policy draft to review, provide feedback, and, once satisfied with its contents, sign the approval sheet as confirmation of their endorsement. Several stakeholders have already reviewed the document and signed the approval sheet.

Meanwhile, **some offices are still carefully examining the policy** to ensure that its provisions are clear, applicable, and aligned with their respective functions. **The research team respects this thorough review process and continues to accommodate additional comments or suggestions when necessary.** All documented feedback and suggested revisions are attached to the approval records, demonstrating the ongoing and careful evaluation process before full institutional adoption.

This continuous review and endorsement process reflects the University's commitment to ensuring that the policy remains responsive, sustainable, and effectively implemented across academic and operational units.

Attached below are copies of the request letter and the approval sheets documenting the ongoing review and endorsement process.
Appendix A. Approval Sheet for the Institutional AI Policy (Ongoing Stakeholder Review)

Appendix A. Approval Sheet

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
 BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
 UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

APPROVAL SHEET
Guidelines for the Responsible Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)
 Saint Mary's University
 Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

Prepared by:
Melanie G. Gorat-Sarmiento, PhD
 Director, University Research Center

Reviewed and approved by:

<p>Mr. Mildros Meeds Ciriaao V. Blando Head, CETSQ Date: <u>2/26/26</u></p> <p>Mrs. Irma Madelleine F. Lopez Head, Cashier Date: _____</p> <p>Dr. Clara M. Gonzales Head, NIO Date: <u>3/12/26</u></p> <p>Mrs. Lorna C. Aban, MAEd Head, UREO Date: <u>3/12/26</u></p> <p>Miss Ronda Navalta, MAEd Head, Cultural Affairs Office Date: _____</p> <p>Mr. Hansen T. Villanueva, MA Head, SPCO Date: _____</p> <p>Mr. Domingo T. Guntalilib Jr., MST Coordinator, NSTP Date: <u>2/26/26</u></p>	<p>Mr. Humprey Ian O. Sagabaen Officer-in-Charge, Alumni Affairs Office Date: _____</p> <p>Mr. Sherwin A. Marciano, MAEd Head, PPDMO Date: _____</p> <p>Mr. Kerwin N. Bayot, MA Head, Publishing Date: <u>2/26/26</u></p> <p>Mrs. Iris E. Reginalde Head, Inventory Management Office Date: <u>2-27-2026</u></p> <p>Mrs. Gayle R. Mercado Head, ETVAO Date: _____</p> <p>Mr. Teofilo M. Sagabaen Head, TTBDQ Date: <u>2/27/26</u></p> <p>Dr. Edwin Edilberto N. Mania Head, Guidance and Testing Office Date: <u>2/24/2026</u></p>
---	---

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

<p> Dr. Felipe V. Nantes, Jr. Dean, STEH Date: <u>Feb. 23, 2026</u></p>	
<p> Mrs. Alona C. Costales, MAEd, RGC Dean of Women Date: <u>2-24-26</u></p>	
<p>Mr. Samuel B. Damayon, JD Associate Dean, SAS Date: _____</p>	<p>Mr. David A. Cabonero, MALS Director, University Learning Resource Center Date: _____</p>
<p> Mrs. Essel T. Canaberal, MIT Director, CICT Date: <u>3/12/2026</u></p>	
<p>Mrs. Pearl Via S. Coballes, RGC, Rpm Director, IDQAO Date: _____</p>	<p>Dr. Cristopher Allen S. Marquez Director, CEIPSC Date: _____</p>
<p>Mrs. Ruby Lyn R. Nuestro, RGC Director, HRDO Date: _____</p>	<p>Dr. Darwin Don M. Dacles University Registrar Date: _____</p>
<p>Mrs. Ariane P. Daran, CPA Vice President, Finance Date: _____</p>	<p>Rev. Fr. Philip A. Yu Vice President, Mission and Identity Date: _____</p>
<p>Dr. Moises Alexander T. Asuncion Vice President, Academic Affairs Date: _____</p>	<p>Dr. John G. Tayaban Vice President, Administration Date: _____</p>
<p>Dr. John Octavious S. Palina University President Date: _____</p>	

This document is officially approved and adopted upon the signature of the authorized University officials.

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER	
<p>Mr. John Lindy R. Soriano, CPA, MSA Department Head, Accountancy Date: _____</p>	<p>Mrs. Sheryl A. Baria, MBA Department Head, Business Date: _____</p>
<p>Mr. John Michael C. Ibarra Department Head, HRM Date: _____</p>	<p>Engr. Kyra S. Bautista, ME-CE Department Head, Engineering and Architecture Date: _____</p>
<p>Mrs. Paulina A. Marzan, MSIT Head, Computer Engineering Date: _____</p>	<p><i>[Signature]</i> Miss Rocel Audrey J. Batara, MIT Department Head, Information Technology Date: <u>2/27/2024</u></p>
<p>Mrs. Melchora M. Bautista, RPh Department Head, Pharmacy Date: _____</p>	<p><i>[Signature]</i> Mrs. Sherylou A. Benig Department Head, Nursing Date: <u>2/21/26</u></p>
<p><i>[Signature]</i> Dr. Airreen O. Santos Department Head, Professional Ed. Date: <u>2/24/26</u></p>	<p><i>[Signature]</i> Dr. Mary Grace M. Bulatao Department Head, Physical Education Date: <u>2/23/26</u></p>
<p><i>[Signature]</i> Miss Kristine Ann L. Israel, RPh, RGC Department Head, PSWD Date: <u>2-24-26</u></p>	<p>Dr. Susan A. Galamay Department Head, Christian Faith Education Date: _____</p>
<p><i>[Signature]</i> Mrs. Jeanette D. Manuel, MS Crim Department Head, Criminal Justice Date: <u>2-23-26</u></p>	<p>Dr. Kenneth L. Maslang Department Head, Social Sciences & Philosophy Date: _____</p>
<p>Atty. Epifanio Delbert G. Galima III Dean, College of Law Date: _____</p>	<p><i>[Signature]</i> Dr. Gertrude G. Danao Dean, School of Graduate Studies Date: <u>3/12/26</u></p>
<p>Dr. Regina D. Ramel, CPA Dean, SAB Date: _____</p>	<p><i>[Signature]</i> Engr. Carina S. Mallillin Dean, SEAT Date: <u>2/27/2024</u></p>

Feedback from Clients

Clients/ beneficiaries provided feedback directly on the printed policy during the review process. The comments included suggestions to improve the formality of language and sentence structure to ensure the document reflects the expected tone of an institutional policy. Several stakeholders also recommended strengthening the policy's emphasis on innovation and responsible engagement with emerging technologies, while maintaining alignment with Saint Mary's University's values.

Additional feedback focused on clarifying the **scope and applicability of the policy**, including explicitly stating that it applies to all members of the University community, such as students, faculty, researchers, administrative personnel, and other employees, whenever AI tools are used in instruction, research, extension, and administrative functions. Reviewers also suggested refining certain sections of the policy by merging overlapping provisions, clarifying the distinction between "allowed" and "encouraged" uses of AI, and emphasizing that AI should serve as a tool to support human thinking rather than replace original intellectual work.

Some comments addressed **academic and research-related considerations**, such as guidance on citing and referencing when AI is used in instructional outputs and the recommendation that research manuscripts include a subsection disclosing the use of AI within the ethical considerations or methodology sections. Stakeholders also raised questions regarding the extent of AI utilization covered by the policy and whether the guidelines apply to instructional practices, research activities, or both.

Finally, suggestions were made regarding **policy governance and compliance**, including the possible inclusion of the Data Protection Officer (DPO) as part of the oversight mechanism to ensure alignment with data privacy laws and ethical standards in the processing and use of data through AI systems.

All suggestions and observations were carefully reviewed and considered for incorporation into the final policy. The scanned copy of the printed policy, attached to this report, contains the comments and annotations made during the review process before the approval sheet was signed. Overall, the feedback confirmed that the policy is clear, practical, and aligned with Saint Mary's University's institutional values, and that it can effectively guide the ethical and responsible use of AI across instruction, research, and community engagement activities.

Appendix B presents the printed draft of the proposed AI Policy, including handwritten comments, suggestions, and editorial notes from stakeholders during the review process.

Appendix B. Annotated Draft of the Proposed Artificial Intelligence (AI) Policy with Stakeholder Comments and Suggestions

 SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Proposed Policy on the Responsible Use of Artificial Intelligence at Saint Mary's University, Bayombong

since this is a policy on responsible use of AI, can we use a more formal way of stating the diff. parts of the policy? Thank you. ~~Christ~~

1. PURPOSE
This policy explains how Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be used in a good and helpful way at Saint Mary's University. It guides students, teachers, staff, and researchers in using AI responsibly, helping people make better decisions, improve learning, and stay true to the values of our Catholic faith, including excellence, innovation, and service to others through Christ.

90% SMU *→ thank the catholic church does not really encourage upon people/students to use AI* *Maybe focus more on the value of innovation as decision or in response to technological advances*

2. WHO SHOULD FOLLOW THIS POLICY
Researchers, staff, and all employees should follow this policy in teaching, instruction, research, community extension, and service.

3. APPLICABILITY OF THE POLICY
Everyone should follow these principles:

2. Applicability of the Policy:
The policy applies to all members of the Saint Mary's University (SMU) community, including students, faculty members, researchers, administrative personnel + all other employees. All covered individuals are expected to adhere to this policy.

1. Everyone should think, create, and decide. Everyone is expected to follow Christian values. at all times. and uphold

2. Tell how you used it. This builds trust and accountability. AI was utilized for a task.

3. Be fair and avoids discrimination. Everyone should be treated equally.

4. Students must think and learn on their own, while using AI. Findings are truthful and original.

5. Be transparent. Share information with AI tools. Always follow data privacy rules, policies and guidelines.

f. Use AI for Good - Promote the responsible & ethical use of AI. Use AI to improve lives, help others, and support the university's mission to serve both local and global communities.

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
 BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
 UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

- b.1 Provide rubrics for assessing AI-assisted outputs.
- b.2 Specify citation and attribution requirements.
- b.3 Include structured discussions on AI's benefits, risks, and limitations, possibly resulting in a class "social contract" for responsible AI use.
- c. Violations will be treated as academic misconduct and sanctioned according to existing school policies.

4.2 Responsible Use of AI in Research and Community Extension Projects

4.2.1 Allowed and Encouraged Use

- 1. Researchers and Community Extensionists are permitted to use AI tools to enhance the quality, efficiency, and accuracy of their work in the following ways:
 - a. Organizing, cleaning, and managing datasets.
 - b. Identifying related literature (e.g., Elicit AI) and assisting in literature reviews.
 - c. Enhancing grammar, clarity, and formatting in research manuscripts.
 - d. Formatting references, tables, and figures according to required styles.
- 2. Disclosure Requirements
 - a. All AI use must be disclosed in the Declaration of AI Use (Appendix A).
 - b. Student researchers must also submit a Certification of Authorship or Declaration of Originality.
 - c. AI is encouraged for editing/refinement, not content creation.

4.2.2 Prohibited Uses

The following uses of AI in research and community extension projects are strictly prohibited:

- a. Using AI to interpret data, perform statistical analysis, or draw conclusions without human validation.
- b. Drafting complete research proposals, manuscripts, or extension project reports using AI.
- c. Uploading confidential, sensitive, or proprietary data without written approval.
- d. Fabricating or falsifying research content using AI.

4.2.3 Implementation and Oversight

- a. Research Advisers, Instructors, Coordinators, Panel Members, and the Research Center Director shall ensure compliance.
- b. The Director of Community Engagement and Indigenous Peoples Studies Center and the Community Extension Coordinators shall monitor AI use in community extension projects.

Should discuss for use of AI in research and what is the extent of utilization. (Guidelines on research?)

** referencing / basis - literature*

** ethical consideration Sub-section on use of AI*

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
 BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
 UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

c. Departments may establish discipline-specific guidelines consistent with this policy (see sample for Research Center, Appendix B).

4.3 Responsible Use of AI in Administration

4.3.1 Allowed and Encouraged Use

a. Administrative offices may use AI tools to enhance efficiency and productivity in:

1. Drafting reports, memoranda, letters, and proposals for review.
2. Organizing schedules, databases, and workflows.
3. Improving communication materials and presentations.

b. Disclosure Requirement

If a significant portion of the material is developed using AI, or if a material is fully developed by AI, staff must complete the AI Tools Use Declaration Form from the Office of the Vice President for Administration (VPA).

4.3.2 Prohibited Uses

1. Uploading or processing confidential data without prior authorization.
2. Fabricating, falsifying, or misrepresenting official records using AI.
3. Producing content that violates laws, institutional policies, or ethical standards.
4. Using AI outputs without human review and verification.

4.3.3 Implementation and Oversight

Lead Office: Office of the Vice President for Administration (VPA) – overall coordination and policy enforcement.

Oversight Roles:

- a. Human Resource Development (HRD): Monitoring AI-related use in employee records and HR processes.
- b. Registrar: Oversight of AI use in student records management.
- c. Chief Accountant: Supervision of AI applications in financial transactions and reporting.
- d. Department of Student Affairs and Services (DSAS): Monitoring AI use in student services and engagement.
- e. Legal Counsel: Ensuring compliance with laws, regulations, and institutional policies.
- f. Center for Information and Communications Technology (CICT): Providing technical support, AI training, and system maintenance.

5. LEARNING AND TRAINING

To help everyone understand AI better, Saint Mary's University will:

Handwritten notes:
 We might also consider DPO as role & function
 Roles: meet DPO comply w/ Data Privacy law, et al and standards w/ processing data

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

- a. Offer training and workshops about how to use AI properly;
- b. Organize discussions about the impact of AI;
- c. Support safe and useful AI use in instruction, research, community extensions, and .

6. CHECKING AND UPDATING THIS POLICY

This policy will be reviewed and updated every two years, or earlier if needed. The review process will follow a hierarchical structure:

- a. Faculty members, department heads, academic deans, heads of offices, research center directors, and the community extension director may suggest changes or improvements to the policy.
- b. These suggestions will be submitted to the Vice President for Administration and Academic Affairs.
- c. Final recommendations will be forwarded to the Office of the President for approval.

7. POLICY FOUNDATION

This policy is based on the Vision-Mission of Saint Mary's University as a Catholic CICM institution guided by God's wisdom and Christ's mission. It supports SMU's goal of forming individuals who live with faith, strive for excellence, lead with innovation, and serve with compassion.

While the policy was inspired by the AI policies of other member universities of the National Consortium, it was carefully written to reflect SMU's values.

It aims to guide the use of AI to promote honesty, fairness, and ethical growth, helping shape life-faith integrated persons, compassionate missionaries, globally enterprising leaders, socially engaged professionals, and ethically committed stewards.